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Content

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Instructions for Contributors

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References must be numbered consecutively as they are cited. References should be denoted numerically and in sequence in the text, using Arabic numerals placed in square brackets, i.e., [12]. List references in numerical order in the Reference list. References selected for publication should be chosen for their importance, accessibility. References first cited in tables or figure legends must be numbered so that they will be in sequence with references cited in the text. The style of references is that of Index Medicus and Vancouver style.

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- Only first words of article title and words that normally begin with a capital letter are capitalized.
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Blaxter PS, Farnsworth TP. Social health and class inequalities. In: Carter C, Peel JR, editors. Equalities and inequalities in health. 2nd ed. London: Academic Press; 1976. p. 165-78.

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Example:

Anderson JC. Current status of chorion villus biopsy. In: Tudenhope D, Chenoweth J, editors. Proceedings of the 4th Congress of the Australian Perinatal Society; 1986: Brisbane, Queensland: Australian Perinatal Society; 1987. p. 190-6.

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Book/Monograph on the Internet:

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Example of a Reference list

Example:

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2. Rau JG, Wooten DC. Environmental impact analysis handbook. New York: McGraw-Hill; 1980.
3. Richardson AJ. Traffic planning and modeling: a twenty year perspective. Aust Road Res. 1990; 20(1):9-21.
4. Meyer MD. Public transportation in the 21st century. In: Gray GE, Hoel LA, editors. Public transportation. 2nd ed. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall; 1992. p. 636-653.

List all authors when there are six or fewer; when there are seven or more, list the first three, then et al.

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*Lahita R, Kluger J, Drayer DE, Koffler D, Reidenberg MM. Antibodies to nuclear antigens in patients treated with procainamide or acetylprocainamide. N Engl J Med 1979; 301:1382-5. Book, personal author(s)

Ringsven MK, Bond D. Gerontology and leadership skills for nurses. 2nd ed. Albany (NY): Delmar Publishers; 1996, pp 30-45.

Book, editor(s) as author Norman II, Redfern SJ, editors. Mental health care for elderly people. New York: Churchill Livingstone; 1996, pp.

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Figures should be numbered consecutively according to the order in which they have been first cited in the text. Define in the legend all abbreviations that are used in the figure.

Review articles Each review article should concentrate on the most recent developments in the field. These articles aim to summarize and highlight recent significant advances in and ongoing challenges in the field. Authors should strive for brevity and clarity. The final structure of the review will, of course, depend on the title/focus but wherever possible, the following sections should be included.

Marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use among immigrant Arab Americans

Cynthia L. Arfken,¹ Hikmet Jamil MD,² and Bengt B. Arnetz, PhD²

Abstract

Background: Immigrant Arab Americans are less likely to drink and abuse alcohol than U.S. born non-Hispanic White Americans (reference group), but little is known about their drug use. If they are shown to have lower drug use, it may be due to immigration effects, presence of fewer risk factors, or cultural protective factors.

Aims: Describe marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use among immigrant Arab Americans and explore causal hypotheses.

Methods: The combined years of the 2002-2010 National Survey of Drug Use and Health were analyzed. Immigrant Canadian Americans served as a control group for immigration effects and immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans served as a control group for cultural effects.

Results: Arab Americans were less likely to have used marijuana and prescription drugs for non-medical reasons than the reference group or immigrant Canadian Americans. There was no difference in their use pattern compared to immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans. These relative patterns of use were consistent across gender, age, education and religiosity. There was no detected difference in marijuana abuse/dependence or prescription drug abuse/dependence between immigrant Arab Americans and the comparison groups.

Conclusion: These findings suggest that drug abuse/dependence among immigrant Arab Americans is a problem. The lower prevalence of marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use appears to be more influenced by cultural as opposed to general immigration factors. These data can be used to develop targeted prevention and treatment services.

The N Iraqi J Med, DECEMBER 2012;8(3):7-13

Keywords: Arab Americans, substance abuse, immigrants, prescription drug misuse, marijuana

Introduction

Drug use is costly to society through its impact on mortality, morbidity, criminal activity and social consequences [1]. The two classes of drugs most commonly used in the U.S. are marijuana (41.9% lifetime) and non-medical use of prescription drugs (20.4% lifetime) [2]. Efforts to prevent and treat drug use include broad population efforts and targeted efforts tailored to specific demographic groups [3,4]. Planning these tailored efforts requires cultural knowledge of the demographic groups coupled with data on group-specific drug use pattern.

For immigrants or 12.5% of the U.S. population [5], we would expect the prevalence of drug abuse and dependence to be lower than that of the U.S. born population based on analysis comparing all immigrants to those born in the U.S. [6]. Their analysis was conducted using data from the U.S. National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH), an annual probability survey designed to measure the magnitude of drug use and consequences in the U.S. [6]. The analysis, however, showed differences between countries of origin in the prevalence of current and lifetime drug use. The National Latino and Asian American Study, a national probability sample of Latinos and Asian Americans [7] found immigrants had lower prevalence of substance abuse/dependence than native born Latinos or Asian Americans [8,9]. Together, the results suggest that immigrants may be less likely to use drugs

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("healthy immigrant") or that immigrants may have a different risk profile. If the latter explanation is true, the lower prevalence may not necessarily generalize to all immigrants, especially those from countries torn by violence as trauma is a risk factor for drug abuse and dependence [10,11].

One immigrant group with little information on drug use and from countries torn by violence is Arab Americans. According to the latest three year findings of the American Community Survey, Arab Americans comprise 0.52% of the U.S. population [12]. Arab Americans have a higher proportion of males and a younger age structure than the general U.S. population [13], both of which are risk factors for experimenting with drugs. However, Arab Americans also have higher education achievement [13] and higher religiosity [14] than the general U.S. population, characteristics which are protective factors for drug use. Additionally, immigrant Arab Americans were born in countries with lower levels of marijuana and opioid use than the U.S. [15] which should be protective. The use pattern of immigrant Arab Americans may reflect other protective cultural factors besides these identified.

Previously, we examined alcohol use patterns for immigrant Arab Americans and compared them to that of U.S. born non-Hispanic White Americans, the reference group [16]. We found immigrant Arab Americans had lower lifetime, past year and current abuse/dependence than the reference group overall and by gender. That analysis, while providing data for targeted services, could not address the relative protective role of culture versus immigration. It did, however, argue that the lower prevalence was not due to distribution of one risk factor, namely male gender.

To obtain information for planning tailored drug prevention and treatment services for Arab Americans, we need to build upon the previous alcohol use analyses and compare the drug use patterns among immigrant Arab American to that of the reference group. To extend the analysis and address the relative role of immigration, we need to compare the drug use patterns for immigrant Arab Americans to that of other immigrant groups. One candidate comparison group would be Canadian Americans, who comprise 0.23% of the U.S. population [12]. The U.S. and Canada, while having differences, have similarities in culture and marijuana use [15]. Based upon these similarities, we would hypothesize that immigrant Arab Americans would have lower drug use pattern than immigrant Canadian American if drug use patterns reflect cultural factors as opposed to immigration factors. Thus the immigrant Canadian American group would act as a control for immigration factors.

Another candidate group for comparison would be people born in Iran, Afghanistan and Pakistan (in this study termed *other Middle Eastern*). We hypothesize that the drug use pattern for immigrant Arab Americans would not differ from that of immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans due to shared cultural factors. Thus the immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans would act as a control for cultural factors. Some immigrants from this area are also coping with exposure to traumatic events [16,17], and in these countries of origin there is high use of opioids but not of marijuana [15]. People who report heritage from these latter countries comprise 0.15% of the U.S. population [12].

Worldwide, the specific drugs consumed differ across countries [15]. Prevention and treatment efforts of different drugs have commonalities but they can also differ [18,21]. To control for which drug was used/abused, we will restrict analysis to marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use. Furthermore, the two drug classes do not have marked regional variation within the U.S. which might confound analyses of drug use patterns as many Arab Americans are heavily clustered in relatively few metropolitan areas [13].

The specific aims of this analysis are to describe the use pattern among immigrant Arab Americans for marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use; compare their use pattern to those of the reference group (U.S. born non-Hispanic White Americans) across risk/protective factors; and contrast the use pattern among immigrant Arab Americans to two other immigrant groups with the hypothesis that there would be significant differences with the use pattern of immigrant Canadian Americans (i.e., to test for immigration effects) but little/no difference with the use pattern of immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans (i.e., to test for cultural effects).

Methods

Data source: The National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH) was used to estimate marijuana and the non-medical prescription drug use patterns. This survey is conducted yearly, which allows the combination of multiple years needed to increase the precision of prevalence estimates for small demographic groups. To our knowledge, no other ongoing national survey has the potential to estimate drug use patterns for Arab Americans. The NSDUH, funded by the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, is the primary source of information on prevalence of alcohol, tobacco, and drug use and abuse in the U.S. civilian non institutionalized population (age 12 and older). The NSDUH has been administered yearly since 1991 but secondary data use is only allowed for surveys conducted since 2002. Due to the stigma

and legal issues surrounding drug use, confidentiality is highlighted in the survey. There are lead-ins stressing confidentiality and audio computer-assisted interviewing methods in English or Spanish. A public access database is available for analysis online. Unfortunately, this online database does not include country of birth or even region of birth. The Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration has a policy of approving limited special tabulated reports by the contractor charged with data collection and management of the survey. For this analysis, the program officer was provided with the list of 20 Arabic-speaking countries to define immigrant Arab Americans, three countries for immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans (Iran, Afghanistan, and Pakistan), and Canada (no race specified) for immigrant Canadian Americans. The reference group was defined as U.S.-born, White race, and not of Hispanic ethnicity. Due to confidentiality issues, the number of respondents from individual countries, such as from Iraq, cannot be disclosed.

In the NSDUH, the marijuana questions are introduced by: The next questions are about marijuana and hashish. Marijuana is also called pot or grass. Marijuana is usually smoked, either in cigarettes, called joints, or in a pipe. It is sometimes cooked in food. Hashish is a form of marijuana that is also called "hash." It is usually smoked in a pipe. Another form of hashish is hash oil. Following this lead-in, there are separate questions about ever use (Have you ever, even once, used marijuana or hashish), use in past year and month (How long has it been since you last used marijuana or hashish?) and symptoms consistent with DSM-IV diagnosis of abuse and dependence. These questions did not change over the time frame of this analysis.

For non-medical prescription drug use, the questions were introduced by: Now we have some questions about drugs that people are supposed to take only if they have a prescription from a doctor. We are only interested in your use of a drug if the drug was not prescribed for you, or you took the drug only for the experience or feeling it caused. The survey then goes on to ask about ever use, past use and symptoms consistent DSM-IV diagnosis of abuse or dependence by class of prescription drugs: pain relievers, tranquilizers, stimulants, and sedatives. Within each class, specific brands (along with an option of other) are asked while the participant is shown cards with the medications on them. Consistent with the increase in number of prescription medications available, the number of specific brands asked in the survey has increased over time. Questions also address symptoms consistent with DSM-IV diagnosis of abuse and dependence from prescription drugs.

The risk and protective factors of sex, age at time of interview, highest educational level completed (for those 18 or older), and religiosity (Your religious beliefs influence how you make decisions in your life - Strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree.) were included in the analysis. High religiosity was defined as strongly agreeing with the religiosity statement.

Analysis

The 2002-10 surveys (n=613,553) were analyzed with SUDAAN using the appropriate sample weights and accounting for the complex sampling strategy. All analyses were conducted by the contractor with output restricted to bivariate tables emailed to the program officer and then forwarded. The contractor indicated in the output if the significance test was less than .01 or .05 for comparisons of the immigrant Arab American group with each of the other three groups.

Results

Of the 613,553 participants in the 2002-2010 NSDUH surveys, approximately 1,200 (0.2%) were immigrant Arab Americans, 700 (0.1%) immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans, and 1,600 (0.3%) were immigrant Canadian Americans. The prevalence rates of individual risk and protective factors from NSDUH (Table 1) differed significantly between immigrant Arab Americans and the reference group. The immigrant Arab Americans also differed significantly from immigrant Canadian Americans on risk/protective factors. However, immigrant Arab Americans only differed significantly with immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans on education and religiosity. Point estimates show immigrant Arab Americans had a higher proportion of males and younger age distribution than the reference group and immigrant Canadian Americans. Immigrant Arab Americans also had the highest prevalence of high religiosity across the four demographic groups.

Table 2 shows the prevalence of lifetime, past year and past month marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use.

Immigrant Arab Americans had statistically lower prevalence of marijuana use regardless of time period than the reference group or the immigrant Canadian Americans. For non-medical prescription drug use, immigrant Arab Americans had significantly lower lifetime prevalence than the reference group or the immigrant Canadian Americans. However, there were no significant differences in prevalence of marijuana or non-medical prescription drug use for any time period between immigrant Arab Americans and immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans. As these

differences in prevalence may reflect the distribution of risk and resiliency factors, a stratified analysis was conducted. Table 3 shows the statistically lower prevalence of gender and religiosity-specific lifetime use for both marijuana and non-medical prescription and non-medical prescription drug use for immigrant Arab Americans compared to the reference group and to the immigrant Canadian Americans. Only one difference was detected at

$p < .05$ for comparisons with risk or protective factors between immigrant Arab Americans and immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans. These patterns of lower prevalence for immigrant Arab Americans compared to the reference group and to immigrant Canadian Americans but not compared to immigrant there Middle Eastern Americans were also generally replicated for age groups and educational achievement (not shown).

Table 1: Prevalence of individual risk and protective factors across demographic groups

	Immigrant Arab Americans	Immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans	Immigrant Canadian Immigrants	U.S.-born White Non-Hispanic Americans
Gender				
Male	60.5%	55.9%	46.0%**	48.6%**
Female	39.5%	44.1%	54.0%**	51.4%**
Age				
12-17	6.8%	6.8%	4.6%**	9.1%**
18-25	11.7%	13.2%	8.0%**	12.0%
26-35	25.4%	19.0%*	12.7%**	14.1%**
36 +	56.1%	61.0%	74.7%**	64.8%**
Education, for those 18 or older				
High school graduation or less	31.7%	21.3%**	32.1%	44.4%**
Some college	23.1%	21.1%	29.2%*	26.1%
College graduate	45.3%	57.6%**	38.7%	29.5%**
Religiosity				
High (strongly agree)	47.5%	30.8%**	26.5%**	32.4%**
Lower (all other responses)	52.5%	69.2%**	73.5%**	67.6%**

* $p < .05$ for comparison between Immigrant Arab Americans and comparison group.

** $p < .01$ for comparison between Immigrant Arab Americans and comparison group.

Religiosity is based on responses to the statement: *Your religious beliefs influence how you make decisions in your life.*

Table 2: Prevalence of lifetime, past year and past month of marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use across demographic groups.

	Immigrant Arab Americans	Immigrant Middle Eastern Americans	Immigrant Canadian Immigrants	U.S.-born White Non-Hispanic Americans
Marijuana				
Lifetime	18.3%	16.1%	45.4%**	45.2%**
Past year	5.4%	4.2%	10.1%**	11.1%**
Past month	3.6%	2.7%	4.9%	6.5%**
Prescription drug				
Lifetime	10.3%	9.4%	19.1%**	23.6%**
Past year	4.6%	3.3%	4.8%	7.0%*
Past month	2.4%	2.0%	1.4%	3.0%

* $p < .05$ for comparison between Immigrant Arab Americans and comparison group.

** $p < .01$ for comparison between Immigrant Arab Americans and comparison group.

Table 3: Lifetime prevalence of marijuana or non-medical prescription drug use by gender and religiosity across demographic groups.

	Immigrant Arab Americans	Immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans	Immigrant Canadian Immigrants	U.S.-born White Non-Hispanic Americans
Marijuana	18.3%	16.1%	45.4%**	45.2%**
Gender				
Male	24.9%	22.0%	50.2%**	49.3%**
Female	8.1%	8.7%	41.3%**	41.2%**
Religiosity				
High (strongly agree)	12.9%	5.1%*	28.6%**	31.6%**
Lower (all other responses)	23.4%	21.2%	51.7%**	51.7%**
Prescription drug	10.3%	9.4%	19.1%**	23.6%**
Gender				
Male	10.6%	11.5%	19.6%**	25.5%**
Female	9.8%	6.7%	18.8%**	21.8%**
Religiosity				
High (strongly agree)	10.3%	6.8%	15.8%	16.7%**
Lower (all other responses)	9.9%	10.5%	20.5%**	27.0%**

*p<.05 for comparison between Immigrant Arab Americans and comparison group.

**p<.01 for comparison between Immigrant Arab Americans and comparison group.

Religiosity is based on responses to the statement: Your religious beliefs influence how you make decisions in your life.

Although the prevalence of lifetime marijuana use by immigrant Arab Americans was less than half (40.5%) of that for the reference group, there was no statistical difference in the prevalence of current marijuana abuse/dependence between immigrant Arab Americans and the three comparison groups (Table 4). Likewise, there was no difference in the prevalence of current prescription drug abuse/dependence between immigrant Arab Americans and the three comparison groups. Controlling for the lower lifetime exposure, 8.2% of immigrant Arab Americans who reported ever trying marijuana currently have symptoms consistent with a diagnosis of abuse or dependence and 5.8% exposed to non-medical prescription drug use currently have symptoms consistent with diagnosis of abuse or dependence. For the reference group, the percentages are 3.5% and 4.2% for marijuana and prescription drug misuse respectively.

Conclusion

In the current study of immigrant Arab Americans, there was lower marijuana and non-medical prescription drug use both over their lifetimes and during time periods (past year or past month) than the reference group of U.S. born White non-Hispanic Americans. Although the lifetime prevalence for immigrants may include time residing in countries with low prevalence of drug use, presumably recent use would capture use in environments with higher drug use [22]. Consistent with our hypothesis that cultural factors influence drug use, the drug use pattern among immigrant Arab Americans was lower than that of immigrant Canadian Americans but not lower than that of immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans. The differences detected both with the reference group and immigrant Canadian Americans were not due to distribution of measured risk and protective factors. These findings support

Table 4: Current prevalence of abuse or dependence by drugs and by demographic groups

	Immigrant Arab Americans	Immigrant Other Middle Eastern Americans	Immigrant Canadian Immigrants	U.S.-born White Non-Hispanic Americans
Marijuana	1.5%	0.8%	0.6%	1.6%
Prescription drug	0.6%	0.1%	0.2%	1.0%

the hypothesis that it is the presence of protective cultural factors as opposed to "healthy immigrant" effect explains the lower drug use pattern among immigrant Arab Americans. One implication of this finding is that tailored drug prevention efforts should leverage protective cultural factors among Arab Americans.

A different picture emerges for abuse/dependence of both marijuana and prescription drugs. For these drugs, there was no difference between any of the estimates for immigrant Arab Americans and those of the comparison groups. The lack of difference detected is most likely due to small sample sizes with abuse/dependence for individual drugs being a rare event. The existence of a real difference that our sample could not detect would be consistent with the finding that U.S. born Latinos and Asian Americans have higher prevalence of substance abuse/dependence than immigrants [9,32]. Nonetheless, the findings suggest that tailored treatment efforts should be prepared for addressing marijuana and prescription drug abuse/dependence among Arab Americans.

We focused on two specific drugs as opposed to all illegal substances to provide drug-specific information for prevention and treatment efforts. In community-based surveys, other illegal drugs are rarely reported and examination of other specific drugs would aggravate the small sample problem. From analysis of treatment admissions, we found similar profiles for drugs of abuse among Arab Americans and other urban ethnicities [24] but increased likelihood of polysubstance abuse among Arab Americans who were born in the U.S./reside here longer and speak English [25]. However, Arab Americans seeking substance abuse treatment reported greater criminal justice involvement than White Americans, consistent with national data on other immigrant minorities [26]. One limitation is that the surveys were conducted in English and Spanish. The exclusion of individuals who are not proficient in English may bias the estimates [27]. The sample also only includes immigrants and thus excludes later generations of Arab Americans further limiting generalizability. All information was based upon self-report and the tendency to deny/exaggerate drug use may differ across demographic groups [28]. The NSDUH takes great care to encourage accurate reporting but there still may remain barriers. The number of immigrants in the sample was small but we combined years to provide greater stability. The inability to conduct multivariate analyses, especially by length of time in the U.S., limits the conclusions. However, this is the only data source of which we know that can provide these drug patterns. Knowledge from this national

database can assist in planning more in-depth regional data collection to supplement these findings.

In conclusion, immigrant Arab Americans use marijuana, but they have lower lifetime and recent use of marijuana than the reference group. Similarly, immigrant Arab Americans reported non-medical use of prescription drugs but less so than the reference group. These patterns appeared to be due to cultural factors as opposed to risk factor distribution or immigration-related factors. In contrast, the prevalence of current abuse/dependence for either marijuana or prescription drugs did not differ between immigrant Arab Americans and the reference group. Use of these data should help tailored prevention and treatment efforts reduce the burden of drug abuse to Arab Americans and society.

Acknowledgement

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Prevalence of hemoglobinopathies and iron deficiency anemia among married couples in Erbil province of Iraq

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Abstract

Thalassemia is the most common genetic disorders Worldwide , widely spread throughout the Mediteranean region, Africa and Far East. The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of β -thalassemia

trait and other haemoglobinopathies among subjects attending marriage screening center in Erbil.

Over a period of one year, 7000 couples were screened for the carrier state of haemoglobinopathies.

Screened subjects were categorized according to the result of complete blood count, serum ferritin and hemoglobin electrophoresis into six groups, namely: normal, β -thalassemia trait, α -thalassemia trait, sickle cell trait, hemoglobin H disease and iron deficiency anemia. Individuals with low Hb and low red cell indices (MCV < 80 fl and MCH < 27 pg) were further investigated by measurement of serum ferritin level and Hb electrophoresis. The prevalence of β -thalassemia trait was 6.94% (972/14000) with nearly equal proportions between males and females (47.6% and 52.3%). HbH disease and sickle cell trait were less common. Iron deficiency anemia was reported in 56 subjects (0.4 %). In countries where hemoglobinopathies are prevalent, premarital screening programs are essential for identification and prevention of high risk marriages. In Erbil, with relatively high prevalence rates of β -thalassemia trait, future complementary control programs including genetic counseling and antenatal diagnosis will be very essential for eliminating the rates of thalassemia disease.

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Introduction

Hemoglobinopathies including Hb variants and thalassemia are groups of inherited disorders of hemoglobin synthesis arising from mutations and/or deletions of one or more

of the globin genes resulting in production of structurally abnormal hemoglobin variants in the former and reduced rate of synthesis of structurally normal globin chains in the latter [1]. Although the carrier states of both conditions may be clinically silent, the homozygous or the doubly heterozygous states manifest clinically as anemia of varying degree of severity [2].

The high incidence of consanguinity among our populations plays a very important role in maintaining the recessive pattern of inheritance and increases the risk of homozygous or doubly heterozygous clinically affected offspring's creating great psychological and financial stresses

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on the families and great burdens on the financial resources of many countries in the region. Many reports on the frequencies of these disorders in the Middle East countries have been published. In Erbil and neighboring provinces, considerable number of researches has been done which studied the molecular pattern of thalassemia [3]. However, no accurate prevalence figures of the different hemoglobinopathies in Erbil province exist.

Methods

Over a period of one year, from February 2010 to February 2011, 7,000 couples underwent routine compulsory premarital testing at Erbil marriage screening center. All of them were included in this study. This center is the only authorized marriage screening center in Erbil. All participants had complete blood count (CBC) (including cell counts, Hb and red cells indices) on the same day of blood sampling using automated blood cell counter (Beckman coulter counter). Individuals with low Hb and/or low red cell indices were further investigated by measurement of serum ferritin level and Hb electrophoresis. Serum ferritin was measured using standardized ELISA technique, Hb electrophoresis was performed using Beckman paragon system which utilizes alkaline electrophoresis (PH 8.6) and aga rose gel as supportive medium.

Results

This study screened 14000 subjects who underwent premarital screening at Erbil marriage screening center.

Their mean age was (25.47±5.54) years ranged between 16 and 45 years. Individuals were considered as:

1. Normal: when they had normal Hb, normal red cell indices and normal Hb electrophoresis pattern.
2. Iron deficiency anemia: when red cell indices and serum ferritin were low (MCV less than 80 fl, MCH less than 27 pg, and serum ferritin less than 15 µg/L) with normal electrophoretic pattern.
3. β-thalassemia trait: when they had low red cell indices, normal or high serum ferritin and increased Hb-A2 on Hb electrophoresis.
4. HbH disease: when they had low red cell indices, normal or high serum ferritin level, HbH band on Hb electrophoresis and a positive HbH inclusion test.
5. Sickle cell trait: when they had low red cell indices, normal serum ferritin level and Hb electrophoresis pattern characteristic of sick cell trait (HbA and HbS bands in about equal proportion).
6. α-thalassemia trait: when they had low red cells indices, erythrocytosis (RBC>5x10¹²/L), normal or high serum ferritin and normal Hb electrophoresis pattern (this diagnosis remained presumptive).

Data was collected and statistically analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

As illustrated in table 1, β-thalassemia trait was found to be the commonest encountered type of hemoglobinopathies. Its prevalence was 6.94% (972/14000) with male to female ratio of 0.9-1.0. Sickle cell trait encountered in 10 subjects and 4 cases found to have Hb- H disease.

Table 1: Summary of screening results.

Category	Male	Female	Total
Normal	6520(46.57%)	6434(45.95%)	12954(92.53%)
β- thalassemia trait	463(3.3%)	509(3.64%)	972(6.94%)
Sickle cell trait	5(0.035%)	5(0.035%)	10(0.07%)
Hb- H disease	0(0%)	4(0.028%)	4(0.028%)
α- thalassemia trait	2(0.014%)	2(0.014%)	4(0.028%)
Iron deficiency anemia	10(0.07%)	46(0.035%)	56(0.39%)
Total	7000(50%)	7000(50%)	14000(100%)

Four cases were empirically labeled as α -thalassemia trait based on normal Hb-electrophoretic pattern, normal serum ferritin, and erythrocytosis in the presence of hypochromic microcytic red blood cells morphology. Iron deficiency anemia was reported in only 56 cases (predominantly in female).

Discussion

β -thalassemia is prevalent in the Mediterranean, Africa and Middle East countries and it forms a real health problem in many of these countries [4] including Kurdistan region of Iraq. According to Hardy Weinberg equilibrium equation for autosomal recessive diseases 1/840 individual has β -thalassemia. It is estimated that about 1500 patients with thalassemia major are currently attending thalassemia centers in the three provinces of Iraqi Kurdistan.

As step aiming at prevention of the disease, in the end of 2009 the department of health in Erbil established its "premarital screening program". The premarital screening center of Erbil was principally designed to control β -thalassemia's. Its main aim is detecting carriers and providing advice to couples about the possibility of having homozygously affected offspring's. Couples may reconsider marriage when both carry the gene or they may be advised about antenatal diagnosis and thus can be given the advantage of therapeutic abortion when the fetus is homozygously affected.

The importance of screening programs lies in the fact that they also provide a platform for increased awareness and education regarding thalassemia among the screened population.

This study intentionally analyzed data of apparently normal subjects who underwent premarital screening as they are considered to be fairly representative of all sections of the population. Besides, they also comprised a population group which could be easily accessible for investigations and counseling. The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence of β -thalassemia trait and other types of hemoglobinopathies in couples undergoing premarital screening in Erbil province and to help to establish more comprehensive preventive procedures such as genetic and prenatal counseling of the couples to improve the health status of the population concerned.

The current study verifies that Kurdistan is among the high prevalent countries for β -thalassemia as 6.94% of the screened subjects (972/14,000) were found to have β -thalassemia trait. There was no significant difference among males and females (male to female ratio was 0.9:1.0). Figures of this study are consistent with the result by Dr. Muhammad who screened university students in Erbil in 2008 and reported prevalence figure of (7.04%) [5]. These two studies indicate that β -thalassemia is significantly higher than figures reported in Duhok (3.7%) (In the extreme North of Iraq) in 2007 [6] and 4.14% reported in Sulaimani (lies also in the north of Iraq) [6] and very approximate figures were reported from the center of Iraq, in Baghdad, and Basra in the extreme south (4.4% and 4.6% respectively) [8, 9]. Compared to regional and neighboring countries the carrier rate in our locality is higher than that reported from Tunisia (3.1%) [10], Padova (Italy) (5.4%) [11], Pakistan (3.4%) [12], Jordan (3.5%) [13], Hong Kong (3.09%) [14], Denizli (Turkey) (2.2%) [15] and Lebanon (2-3%) [16], while the Iranian figures are higher with a prevalence rate of 10% reported in 2002 [17]. In this study, β -thalassemia trait was the commonest type of the encountered hemoglobinopathies 98.1% (972/990). This is similar to results from regional states of Qatar and Bahrain (94.7%) [18] and (93.8%) [19]. Sickle cell trait was detected in only 10 subjects (0.07%) which is similar to that reported in Konya urban area in Turkey (0.05%) [20]; while Hb-H disease was detected in only 4 subjects (0.028%). α -thalassemia was found to be very rare in our locality and this may be due to the fact that Erbil lies in the area where β -thalassemia is commonly encountered hemoglobinopathy and that the prevalence rate of α -thalassemia trait obtained in this study may be underestimated, since its well-known that a proportion α -thalassemia trait would be missed if MCV and/or MCH used as screening tests. Reliable data on the prevalence of α -thalassemia defects in the region will require molecular characterization. The latter is currently not available. In conclusion β -thalassemia trait was the commonest type of all hemoglobinopathies in our locality with prevalence rate of 6.94%. Increasing awareness of the disease by education through medical fraternity and public media and the provision of facilities for antenatal diagnosis which are not currently available are essential to reduce the thalassemia homozygous population.

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Hemophilia in Iraqi Kurdistan: A clinico-pathological study

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Abstract

Hemophilia is a sex linked bleeding disorder. Affected patients suffer spontaneous or post-traumatic bleeding into various sites of the body depending on the level of coagulation factor deficiency. The aim of this study was to assess the relation of severity of hemophilia to age at diagnosis, severity and frequency of bleeding episodes, circumcision associated bleeding, joint deformity, limitation of movement and aPTT level. In this prospective study, a total of 135 hemophilia patients were recruited and studied. Their bleeding history, clinical and laboratory data were recorded thereafter followed up for eight months. Patients were classified according to levels of factor deficiency into mild (5-20% of the normal), moderate (1-5% of the normal) and severe ($\leq 1\%$ of the normal). Majority of patients had Hemophilia A (89%). The mean age of patients was 13 years, 46.5% were ≤ 10 years. About 60% had first time bleeding within first year of life. Patients with severe hemophilia presented earlier, had more bleeding episodes and related complications. At least one bout of hemarthrosis was recorded in 103 patients (76.3%) during the course of their disease with knee joint most frequently involved. Functional disability encountered in about 10% of cases majority had severe hemophilia. With the exception of the aPTT, all other hematological parameters were within normal ranges. The degree of aPTT prolongation related significantly to the severity of disease ($P < 0.05$). In conclusion, there was a significant relation between the severity of hemophilia and earlier age at the diagnosis, severity of bleeding, frequency of bleeding episodes per year, circumcision associated bleeding, joint deformity, limitation of movement, and the level of aPTT.

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Keywords: Iraqi Kurdistan; Hemophilia A; Hemophilia B; APTT

INTRODUCTION

Hemophilia is a sex-linked recessive bleeding disorder mainly affecting male through female carrier. It is caused by low concentrations of specific coagulation factors. Factor VIII deficiency (hemophilia A) is four times more

common than factor IX deficiency (hemophilia B). They are estimated to occur, respectively, in approximately 1 of every 10,000 and 1 of every 30,000 male births worldwide. No community is immune to hemophilia as almost a third of all patients are due to fresh mutations, with negative family history [1, 2]. Hemophilia is clinically classified into mild, moderate and severe according to factor level in the plasma. Mild hemophilia is when factor concentration ranges between 5-20% of the normal; moderate is 1-5%; and severe hemophilia when factor level is $\leq 1\%$ [3]. It is important to differentiate hemophilia from the much more common autosomally transmitted von Willebrand disease (VWD), which affects both sexes and it could affect

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almost 1% of the entire population [4]. Children with hemophilia usually present with bleeding when they start crawling or after circumcision. Abnormal and recurrent bleeding can then occur in various parts of the body but mainly into joints [5]. Less frequently bleedings occur into muscles and mucous membranes. Bleeding into joints is very painful, it accounts for approximately 75-80% percent of bleeding episodes in severely affected patients with hemophilia (6). Recurrent episodes of hemarthrosis in absence of replacement therapy and proper care result in synovitis and joint destruction which in turn cause limitation of motion and functional disability [7].

There has not been any previous study done on hemophilia in Iraqi Kurdistan; therefore, very little data was available about extent of the disease in terms of number of patients and the gap between registered and expected cases in comparison with those of developed world. This study aimed at assessing the relation of severity of hemophilia (level of factor deficiency) to age at diagnosis, severity of bleeding, frequency of bleeding episodes per year, circumcision associated bleeding, joint deformity, limitation of movement (LOM), and the level of aPTT. This will provide correct data for the health authorities for future establishment of comprehensive care centers for hemophilia patients and will support any national program intending to establish a hemophilia national registry.

Methods

This prospective study, reviewed registered hemophilia patients in the three governorates of Iraqi Kurdistan. From November 2008 to June 2009, 135 patients with hemophilia (133 male and 2 female) were recruited from hospitals of Erbil, Dohuk and Suleimaniyah Cities. Patients were contacted and interviewed individually. After written consent by the patients (or their attendants) their history was reviewed, clinically examined, and then followed up during the period of study. Clinical data including personal information, age of diagnosis, family history, type of hemophilia, clinical presentations, sites and frequency of bleeding, complications, daily activities and functional status of the patient were registered in a pre-designed questionnaire. Results of the relevant laboratory tests were also registered.

All patients had relevant hematological tests and radiography done at Nanakaly hospital for blood diseases in Erbil City. Complete blood count using automated counter (Beckman Coulter, USA); bleeding time (BT) was measured using Ivy's method with standard lancet; coagulation tests, prothrombin time (PT) and activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT), were done according to standard manual methods. FVIII and FIX assay were carried out using coagulometer (Stago). Radiography was done for

involved joints. Hemophiliacs were classified into three groups according to their coagulation factor levels; mild 5-20% of the normal, moderate 1-5% of the normal and severe $\leq 1\%$ of the normal [3]. Data was statistically analyzed using Microsoft® Excel, Professional Edition 2003; p-value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

In this series, 120 patients (89%) had Hemophilia A and 15 patients (11%) had Hemophilia B. Their mean age was 13 ± 10.48 years ranged between 9 months to 60 years. Sixty three (46.5%) of them were ≤ 10 years. Only 3 patients were above 40 years of whom one was 60 years female. In this cohort two patients were females. Age distribution is shown in Table 1. More than half of the studied patients, 79 patients (58.5%) presented with first time bleeding within the first year of their life; while 45 patients (33.3%) presented between (1-5) years and only 11 patients (8.2%) presented after 5 years of age. It was found that the mean of factor level was lower among patients who presented earlier; this difference was statistically significant (Table 2). Family history was positive in 99 patients (73.3%); there was no relation between severity of the disease and family history.

Table (1): Age distribution of patients.

Age	0-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	Total
No.	63	48	16	5	1	2	135
%	46.5	35.5	12	4	0.7	1.3	100

Table (2): Age at diagnosis

Age of Diagnosis	Number	%	Mean Factor (%)	P-value
Year 1	79	58.5	4.03	0.017
Year 2	27	20	5.52	
Year 3	10	7.4	7.82	
Year 4	6	4.4	9.8	
Year 5	2	1.48	3.0	
Year 6	6	4.4	6.66	
Year 7	5	3.7	14.25	
Total	135	100		

Patients suffering severe hemophilia constituted 31% (42 patients); those with moderate disease were 46 (34%) and the remaining 47 patients (35%) had mild disease. When patients divided according to severity of bleeding, it appeared that 34 of them (25%) had spontaneous bleeding, 69 (51%) bled after minor trauma and 32 patients (24%) had bleeding only after major trauma. Majority of those who bled spontaneously had severe disease (29 cases - 69%); on the other hand, mild cases bled only after major trauma or surgery. The relation between severity of

bleeding and level of factor deficiency was significant, $p < 0.05$ (Figure 1). When the frequency of bleeding was studied, it was found that 95 patients (70.4%) had 1-10 times bleeding per year, 29 (21.5%) had 11-20 times bleeding and 6 patients (4.4%) bled >20 times per year (Table 3). The mean factor level for those who had 0-10 times bleeding was 6.6% while it was 1.9% for those who had >10 times bleeding per year. The annual frequency of bleeding was significantly higher among hemophiliacs with low factor levels ($p < 0.01$).

Figure (1): Relation between severity of bleeding and factor deficiency.

Table (3): Frequency of bleeding episodes per year

	< 1 episode/ year	1-10 episodes/ year	11-20 episodes/ year	21-48 episodes/ year
Severe H*	0	21	16	5
Moderate H	1	33	11	1
Mild H	4	41	2	0
Total (%)	5 (3.7%)	95 (70.4%)	29 (21.5%)	6 (4.4%)

* H=hemophilia

Circumcision associated bleeding was intently considered in this study as male circumcision is a regular religious practice in our locality. In 133 male hemophiliacs, circumcision was associated with bleeding that required medical interference in 66 patients (49.6%); but was not problematic in 47 others (35.4%). Expectedly, 20 patients (15%) were not circumcised because of family history of circumcision related bleeding in previous children (Table 4). Our study showed that there is significant

relation between severity of the disease and the circumcision associated bleeding ($p < 0.05$).

The current study demonstrated that 32 cases (23.7%) of our hemophiliacs had bleeding only into joints; 71 patients (52.6%) had mixed bleedings into joints, mucous membranes and soft tissues, and 32 others (23.7%) had bleedings only into soft tissues or mucous membranes. Overall, 103 cases (76.3%) had got hemarthrosis during the course of their disease with joints most frequently affected being the main

load or strain bearing articulations. Bleeding into knees was recorded in 42 patients; 38 others had bleedings into knee and other joints. Elbow was affected in 11 patients, ankle in 6, wrist in 4 and shoulder joint in 2 patients. Misalignment and joint deformity was found in 55 patients (40.7%); the remaining 80 patients (59.3%) did not have any deformities. Deformity of knee was recorded in 35 patients, elbow in 6, ankle in 4 and multiple joint deformities found in 10 patients. Table 5 shows that most of severe hemophiliacs had joint deformities and none with mild disease had any deformity. The relation between severity of the disease and presence of deformity in joints was significant with the $p < 0.05$.

The degree of limitation of movement (LOM) among the studied set was variable. Severe LOM in form of joints ankylosis with inability to move without support or walking aids was found in 15 patients (11%). On the other hand, 31 patients (23%) had mild LOM who were able to perform their daily activities with little pain. In between, there were 43 patients (32%) who had moderate LOM. With those there was a nearly normal group of 46 patients

(34%) who had no LOM. There was a significant relation between severity of hemophilia and both incidence and degree of LOM ($P < 0.05$). Most patients with severe or moderate disease had moderate to severe LOM while 10 cases (7.4%) with mild disease had mild degree of limitations. Within the studied group, 13 patients (9.5%) were functionally disabled because of their disease; of which 10 patients had severe hemophilia and 3 had moderate disease.

Almost all hematological parameters were within normal ranges except the aPTT. The means of Hb level and platelet count were 13.0g/dl and $308 \times 10^9/L$ respectively. Bleeding time ranged between 1.5-9 minutes (mean=3.56 min). The mean PT was 13.2 seconds. On the other hand, all patients had prolonged aPTT. The degree of aPTT prolongation was variable among patients with variable severity of factor deficiency. Patients with mild hemophilia had less prolongation of aPTT while those with severe disease had extreme prolongation. It was found that the degree of prolongation of aPTT related significantly to the severity of hemophilia ($p < 0.001$).

Table (4): Circumcision associated bleeding.

	Associated bleeding	No associated bleeding	Not Circumcised	Total
Sever H*	23	7	11	41 (+1 female)
Moderate H	24	18	4	46
Mild H	19	22	5	46 (+1 female)
Total (%)	66 (49.6)	47 (35.4)	20 (15)	133 (100)

Table (5): Relation between severity of the disease and joint deformity.

	Presence of joint deformity	Absence of Joint deformity	Total
Sever H	35	7	42
Moderate H	20	26	46
Mild H	0	47	47
Total (%)	55 (40.7)	80 (59.3)	135 (100)

Discussion

Hemophilia is the second most common inherited coagulation disorder after VWD. In the three governorates of Iraqi Kurdistan 135 hemophilia cases are registered, this corresponds to a prevalence of 3.4/100,000 population. This figure is lower than that reported by other countries in which figures were as high as 20.5, 10-15 and 6.5 per 100,000 in USA, Europe and Japan respectively [8, 9]. In Iran, higher prevalence figure (24 per 100,000) was reported by Farhud et al [10]. This lag between expected and registered numbers may be attributed to difficulties in diagnosis due to lack of proper laboratory facilities for diagnosis of bleeding disorders and factors assay, and lack of specialized hemophilia center leading to the fact that patients are being scattered over many unspecialized hospitals.

In this series, 89% of the patients had hemophilia A and 11% were hemophilia B. This is widely accepted as hemophilia A is the common type and accounts for about 85% of all hemophilias [1]. Among the studied patients only two were females; this distribution is expected as hemophilia is a sex linked disorder. Hemophilia in females is extremely rare, although female offspring from a hemophilic father and a carrier mother have been reported. Hemophilia may occur in females with X chromosome abnormalities such as Turner syndrome, and other X chromosome defects. Rarely extreme lyonization of normal X chromosome may result in symptomatic carriers [11]. Patients aged ≤ 10 years constituted 46.6%; the next commonly affected age group was between 11-20 years (35.5%). This distribution is identical with findings of Al-Murshidi in Baghdad [12]. The relative rarity of older hemophiliacs in Iraq can be explained as many of the mild cases remain undiagnosed, and many die early due to inadequate management. This is unlike the situation in the west where prophylactic replacement therapy turns young hemophiliacs to live almost normal life [13].

More than half of our patients (58.5%) presented with first time bleedings before the age of one year, mostly after circumcision. Bleeding after circumcision appears to be a good indicator of inherited bleeding disorder in societies where circumcision is a regular religious practice like in ours [5]. In Al-Murshidy's report, 84% presented with first time bleedings before the first year and majority were diagnosed after circumcision [12]. Majority of severe hemophiliacs were diagnosed early in life while those with mild disease presented later when major trauma or surgery provoked unusual bleeding. The relation between severity of hemophilia and age of diagnosis was significant ($p < 0.05$). These results are consistent with results of studies from developed countries [5, 14]. In this study, severe hemophiliacs represented less than

one-third of all patients. This is incomparable with the findings of other studies where severe cases constituted the major portion because of frequent attending to hospitals and earlier diagnosis. The explanation for this is early death of severe cases due to inadequate care, and some families with good socioeconomic status seek better management abroad.

In this series, 25% of cases were spontaneous bleeders, 51% had bleeding after minor trauma and the remaining 24% had bleeding only after major trauma. Most of the spontaneous bleeders had severe disease and some had moderate hemophilia; while none with mild disease ever had a spontaneous bleeding episode. There was a significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between severity of bleeding and level of factor deficiency.

Similar results by Al-Murshidy who reported that episodes of spontaneous hemarthrosis were infrequent in moderate and absent in mild hemophilia, and major trauma or surgery being imported for the detection of mild hemophilia [12]. Moreover, our study revealed that there is significant relation between severity of the disease and the circumcision associated bleeding. Expectedly, 20 patients (15%) were not circumcised because of positive family history of bleeding in previous children. This supports what has been stated that bleeding after circumcision is the forerunner of other symptoms in many societies [15]. When the annual frequency of bleeding was assessed, it was found that number bleeding episodes related to the severity of the disease, a finding that has been repeatedly confirmed in literatures. Patients with mild hemophilia usually bleed excessively only after trauma or surgery, those with severe hemophilia have an annual average of 20 to 30 episodes of spontaneous or excessive bleeding after minor trauma, particularly deep seated bleeding into joints and muscles [16].

Bleeding into joints only was recorded in 23.7% of studied patients; more than half had history of mixed type bleedings into joints, soft tissues, mucous membranes and muscles; of them 17 had at least one attack of epistaxis with hemarthrosis. Smaller numbers had soft tissue bleeding (13.3%) or bleeding into mucous membranes (10.4%) only. The overall incidence of hemarthrosis was more than 75%. Knees were most frequently affected either alone or together with other joints, followed by elbows then ankles, wrists and shoulders. The frequency and site distribution of joint bleeding is comparable with those reported by Al-Murshidi and others [12, 17, 18]. Joint deformity and misalignment was recorded in 41% of patients. The frequency and site of deformed joints followed the rate of affection by hemarthrosis.

There was a significant correlation between the severity of the disease and incidence of joint deformities ($p < 0.05$). Out of 55 patients with joint deformities 35 had severe hemophilia, of them 10 had multiple joint deformities. No patient with mild disease had joint deformity. These findings are consistent with results of Gurcay et al who reported that about 50% of severe hemophilia patient develop joint deformities with a high potential for functional disability if prompt treatment is unavailable or inadequate [19]. Deformities of joints from hemarthrosis resulted in variable degree of limitation of movements (LOM) depending on the degree and number of joint affection. In this study 66% of hemophiliacs found to have LOM while the others had no limitation with nearly normal activities. These figures are higher comparing to figures reported from developed countries where better treatment and care is provided. Patients with severe hemophilia mostly suffered a moderate to severe degree of LOM. From the later group 15 were unable to move without support or walking aids. On the other hand, mild hemophiliacs in worse scenarios had mild degree of LOM. This relation between severity of the disease and both incidence and degree of LOM was significant ($p < 0.05$). This is widely accepted because frequent bleedings into joints in the severe forms lead to joint deformities and later on LOM [20]. Limitation of movements eventually will cause functional disability, mainly when bleeding episodes are frequent and multiple joints affected. Disability encountered in 13 patients, of whom 10 had severe and 3 had moderate hemophilia. Ten of those functionally disabled patients were below 15 years and they were not attending school due to their disability, and the other 3 were older and completely dependent.

The basic hematological parameters of the hemophiliacs did not show any considerable difference from normal. The presence or absence of anemia or signs of blood regeneration depend on the severity and frequency of bleeding. In this study, only 5 patients were anemic, the mean Hb value was 13.0g/dl with no significant difference between the three hemophilia groups. Platelet counts and BT were normal in all patients. Likewise the PT was normal; this is the classical pattern in hemophilia [21]. The aPPT was prolonged in all patients; the extent of prolongation was directly related to the severity of factor deficiency ($p < 0.001$). The aPTT increased from 40 seconds in mild group to as much as 108 seconds in patients with severe disease.

In conclusion, there was a significant relation between the severity of hemophilia and earlier age at the diagnosis, severity of bleeding, frequency of bleeding episodes per year, circumcision associated bleeding, joint deformity, limitation of movement

(LOM), and the level of aPTT. Relatively high incidences of joint deformities and movement limitation of varying degree were recorded among our patients. A good proportion of patients suffered severe functional disability. This reflects the inadequate medical services and poor quality of rehabilitation care our hemophiliacs received.

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"Magnifying glass" for difficult radiocephalic arteriovenous fistulas

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Abstract

Background: Some uremic patients suffering from diabetes, atherosclerosis or simply by absent or exhausted peripheral vascular bed require bigger effort in creating arteriovenous fistula. Although it is possible to use prosthetic graft for difficult cases, the use of native vessels falls always in the respect of patient's quality of life. A help for these cases comes from the use of a microsurgical technique for creating vascular access.

Patient and Methods: For this study we evaluated the 72 patients underwent microsurgical radiocephalic fistula comparing them to a homogeneous group of 72 patients underwent traditional surgery. The patients were followed up at 1, 2 months and 1 year.

Results: From comparison between the two groups our findings suggested that microsurgical radiocephalic arteriovenous fistula is more effective than traditional surgery in term of functional patency with appropriate dialysis.

Conclusion: The use of microsurgical technique in our experience provides an improvement for the success of distal radiocephalic arteriovenous fistula in term of primary patency in those cases with a poor prognosis according to quality of distal native vessels.

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Key words: Microsurgery, Vascular access, Arteriovenous fistula, Radiocephalic fistula.

Introduction

The distal radiocephalic arteriovenous fistula (AVF) is the vascular access of choice for chronic hemodialysis [1-3]. This statement is based on the evidence that AVF, upon reaching maturity, gives the best results in terms of patency over-time, associated with lower incidence of complications (thrombotic, infectious, ischemic), compared to other vessels with native vascular access, prosthetic, or central venous catheters. Differently than prosthetic fistula, the main problem of this native vascular access is represented

by early failure, coming up to 30-50%, with an average of 15.3%, according to recent meta-analysis [4-6].

The advanced age, comorbidity factors such as hypertension, obesity or diabetes -factors already known for their negative effect in general surgery- are predictors of early failure of vascular access [6-8]. The diameter of the vessels (radial artery and cephalic vein) seems to be the limiting specific factor according to various works [9-13]. The diameter should not be less than 1.6-2 mm for the radial artery and 1.6-2.5 mm for cephalic vein. However, despite these findings, excellent results were obtained in pediatric populations through the use of microsurgery, which reduces the incidence of immediate failure of the 5-10% [14, 15]. The use of this technique may result useful in that circumstances in which a failure is likely to happen

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such as in presence of a scarce peripheral vascular bed as in woman [16]. Here we describe our experience about the use of microsurgical technique on a group of selected patients with sub-optimal forearm vessels to overcome the problems in making such a difficult vascular access.

Patients and Method

From March 2007 to October 2010, 72 first radiocephalic end-to side AVF with microsurgical technique have been performed. In the same period we continued to perform traditional AVF without microsurgery. The patients with vascular access performed with microsurgical technique were compared to a homogeneous group of 72 patients with traditional surgery randomly selected. All the patients underwent creation of radiocephalic AVF at non-dominant forearm. The patients underwent ultrasonography study in order to evaluate the radial artery diameter at wrist [13]. Demographic data are summarized in Tab 1.

Table 1: Demographic data of the two groups.

	Traditional AVF	Microsurgical AVF	p
Number of patients	72	72	-
Gender M/F	-	-	-
Age (mean $\pm$ SEM)	63.00 $\pm$ 0.62	65.33 $\pm$ 0.63	s
Hypertension (%)	87.11 $\pm$ 0.43	92.17 $\pm$ 0.61	s
Diabetes (%)	85.33 $\pm$ 0.64	75.17 $\pm$ 0.63	s
Obesity (BMI > 30) (%)	33.28 $\pm$ 0.60	26.06 $\pm$ 0.75	s

The choice of microsurgical technique was dependent only on surgical microscope availability and, at last but not at least, the surgeon's opinion. The microsurgical technique required the use of a dedicated stereoscopic surgical microscope that allows an optimal visualization of the anatomical details due to the possibility of magnification of image to over 12 times and focal illumination with cold light. The microsurgical technique allows working with extreme precision on small structures, while respecting their anatomical and functional integrity. The microsurgical technique was demonstrated to provide important advantages in pediatric population needing distal AVF [14]. The anesthesia was performed by means of brachial plexus block with axillary approach. The advantage of the use of this technique beyond the anesthetic effects is the vasodilation, and prolonged postoperative analgesia compared to simple local infiltration [17]. The first surgery stage was carried out with the use of loop magnification at 2.5^xs. The longitudinal skin incision, about 5 cm in length, ran halfway between the vein and artery. To optimize

the view of operative field we used a special retractor [18]. Then, we proceeded to vein isolation for a length sufficient to allow its mobilization at the site of the anastomosis. Subsequently, the vein was terminalized and modeled in a spout of clarinet, by the help of surgical microscope. To avoid drying, the vessel was frequently irrigated with 2% heparinized saline. After the incision of the antebrachial fascia, the anterior wall of radial artery was exposed and a 10 mm longitudinal arteriotomy was performed by means of ophthalmological scalpel completed with microsurgical scissors. The lateral-terminal anastomosis was then made with two continuous monofilament polypropylene sutures of 10/0 according to the side to end technique. Upon completion of the anastomosis, the clamps were removed and the patency of the AVF was confirmed by digital perception of the classic thrill. The success of the procedure was demonstrated by auscultating the continuous murmur with systolic reinforcement in the first section of the vein. The duration of the entire surgical procedure took an average of 85 minutes (60-110). The patients were followed up at 1, 2 month after the surgical procedure and also at 1 year. Maturation was defined as functional patency with appropriate dialysis.

Results

Two thrombosis occurred within the immediate 24 h following surgery in group with microsurgical AVF compared to 7 cases in traditional group (Tab. 2)

Table 2: Thrombosis occurred after intervention and during follow-up into the two groups.

Thrombosis Time	Traditional surgery		Microsurgery	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
After intervention	4	3	0	2
After 1 month	8	4	2	6
After 2 months	0	0	0	0
After 24 months	3	4	1	2

Eight patients out of 72 developed an early failure of AVF at 1 month, compared to the 12 submitted to traditional surgery. All the patients with this complication underwent re-intervention and were therefore excluded from the follow-up. At 2 months, no failure was found for both the two groups. In all cases the patients performed dialysis by the created AVF. One-year follow-up showed a failure of 3 cases for microsurgery group and 7 cases for traditional surgery. The primary patency rate during follow-up in two groups was tested by unpaired t- Student's test for parametric variable and by one-way ANOVA analysis of variance. A p value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant (Tab.3, and Fig.1).

Table 3. Patency rate occurred after intervention and during follow-up into the two groups.

Time	Traditional surgery		Microsurgery	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
After intervention	89.24 ± 0.67	86.24 ± 0.73	94.91 ± 0.48	91.00 ± 0.74
After 1 months	66.76 ± 0.67	59.28 ± 0.67	79.24 ± 0.84	62.00 ± 0.74
After 2 months	39.24 ± 0.67	36.24 ± 0.73	52.03 ± 0.95	48.85 ± 1.12
After 24 months	29.24 ± 0.67	26.28 ± 0.91	43.24 ± 0.84	39.46 ± 0.94

Fig. 1. Column bar graph of the patency rate (%) during follow-up into the two groups (traditional surgery vs. microsurgery).

Discussion

The native distal radiocephalic AVF represents the gold standard for chronic hemodialysis [3], but this statement became true and accepted worldwide only recently [1]. Many factors play a potential harmful role in native fistula maturation such as increasing average age of patients and the incidence of comorbidity factors that represent a risk of immediate failure [4]. This complication, in fact, accounts by 30-50% with an average value calculated in meta-analysis study of 15.3% [19-22]. Several risk factors are being studied in recent years: advanced age, hypertension, diabetes, obesity, vascular diseases and the diameter of the vessels (radial artery and cephalic vein). The age and comorbidity factors are well-recognized risk factors on vascular surgery, with equal access for both native vessels and through the prosthesis, either for proximal and distal ones. In addition, factors such as diabetes and age can

synergistically increase the risk of peripheral ischemia for proximal access. In fact, the distal ischemia is a significant problem for patients who undergo the creation of a vascular access for hemodialysis [23]. From that, the best solution for these patients seems to be the distal anastomosis. Considering in most of cases the prosthetic graft the last resource, many attempts using minimally invasive surgery have been done to realize a distal native vascular access using a venous tract deeper [24] not always of easy realization.

The small caliber of forearm vessels is a factor of specific risk for distal radiocephalic AVF. Some studies have shown an increased risk of immediate failure due to the use of radial artery caliber <1.6 mm [14]. Heart failure high flow rate is another potential complication, with access too much greater risk for proximal than distal [25]. It has been successfully demonstrated that the use of automatic stapler derived from cardiothoracic surgery can help in

creating AVF [26] but in case of severe vascular calcification or atherosclerosis their use is not safe. Some authors [27] reported a successful creation of microsurgical distal forearm radiocephalic fistula using vessels of small caliber in a pediatric population with very small vessels. The microsurgical technique allows working with extreme precision on structures of small size, respecting the anatomical and functional integrity avoiding technical errors capable to influence the outcome of intervention. There must be a distinction between constitutionally small vessels and vessels with severe lesions in their anatomical structure/function. In the first case, except for surgical difficulty due to their small size, they do not have characteristics that prevent the maturation process (expansion and remodeling of the wall). The absence of maturation of fistula by 4-6 weeks will give a patent vascular access but with a flow insufficient to perform hemodialysis. This arises in many cases from a reduced flow in artery or shunted flow in collateral veins. This kind of access in our experience is still susceptible to be rescued. Another case is when the vascular access fails early even in presence of a good flow in artery. In the latter case according to our experience the problem comes from a vascular bed not capable to receive the shunted flow because of a vascular sclerosis.

Conclusions

Microsurgery is effective in enabling the creation of distal radio-cephalic AVF in adult patients with difficult vascular access, such as women where notoriously the superficial vascular bed is not well represented. From the reported data we found that this method can improve the primary patency rate in that case in which the reduced caliber of vessel decreases the possibility of primary success but we want to try to preserve the proximal vasculature.

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Assessment of hemostatic changes in patients with non-promyelocytic acute myeloid leukemia

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Abstract

Background: Many patients with malignancies demonstrate coagulation abnormalities as activated coagulation and activation of fibrinolysis. Chemotherapy used for the treatment of leukemia may influence the coagulation changes.

Objectives: The aim of this study was to assess the haemostatic changes in patients with non-promyelocytic acute myeloid leukemia (AML) before start of induction treatment and following two weeks of ending therapy.

Methods: The study was prospectively conducted, between October 2009 and October 2011, on 58 acute myeloid leukemia patients at the national center of hematology in Baghdad, Iraq. markers of coagulation were measured pre and post induction of chemotherapy

Result: A total of 58 patients with AML were included in this study (32 males and 26 females, aged 15–65 years, with median age of 43 years. There were no significant change in hemostatic parameters before starting therapy in all types, while there were significant changes in some hemostatic parameter after 2 week of therapy especially in Hemoglobin and platelets count.

Conclusions: Results suggest that hemostatic changes can occur in patients with de novo AML, with no significant changes after induction treatment, even though these change are not serious as that of promyelocytic leukemia(AML-M3)

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Key words: hemostasis, Acute myeloid leukemia, induction treatment

Introduction

Malignant hematological disorders may be associated with coagulopathy causing bleeding and thromboembolic complications [1]. Severe infections, chemotherapy, may augment this risk by the action of inflammatory mediators and the release of proteases. Secondary activation of fibrinolysis may partly compensate the activated coagulation, but in metastatic prostate cancer and acute promyelocytic leukemia (APL), the fibrinolysis may prevail [2, 3].

Molecular markers for increased thrombin generation that can detect a pre-thrombotic state include a prothrombin activation fragment, Fragment 1+2 (F1+2), and a complex formed between thrombin and its cognate serpin antithrombin, the thrombin-antithrombin complex (TAT) [4, 5]. The complex formed between activated protein C (APC) and the serpin, protein c inhibitor (PCI), has been shown to be a sensitive indicator of thrombin formation and, thus, of the activation of blood coagulation [6]. However, these methods are not widely used in clinical practice.

Hematological malignancies are often associated with hemostatic disturbances [9, 10] which seem, at least partly, to be associated with Von Willebrand factor (VWF) defects. Both increased activity of the

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coagulation system as well as hyperfibrinolysis have been described. In addition, patients often experience low platelet counts ($<40 \times 10^9/L$) which may cause life-threatening hemorrhages [11]. Other pathophysiological mechanisms that may add to an increased bleeding tendency include a massive proteolytic state, triggered by pro coagulant substances, plasminogen activators and proteinases released into circulation from leukemic cells as well as proteolytical degradation of the VWF [12]. Life threatening bleeding is frequent in acute leukemias, particularly in acute promyelocytic leukemia (APL) (13). An important pathogenetic role is attributed to the leukemic cell properties interfering with haemostatic mechanisms, leukemias present with abnormalities in laboratory tests of blood coagulation, even without clinical manifestations of thromboembolism or hemorrhage, these abnormalities demonstrate different degrees of blood clotting activation and characterize the so called hyper coagulable state [14].

The aim of this study was to evaluate hemostatic changes in patients with non-promyelocytic AML prior to the start of induction treatment and following two weeks of therapy.

Patients and Methods

Study design and subjects

A prospective study conducted at the national center of hematology in Baghdad, Iraq between October 2009 and October, 2011. Inclusion criteria included patients with diagnosis of de novo AML who admitted for induction therapy, with age more than 15 years of age. Exclusion criteria included acute promyelocytic leukemia, age less than 15 and more than 65, and history of bleeding tendency before the diagnosis of AML. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients before starting the study. Intravenous chemotherapy consisted of doxorubicine hydrochloride 30 mg per square meter infusion over $\frac{1}{2}$ hour for three successive days and cytarabine arabinoside 100 mg per square meter infusion over 12 to 18 hours for seven successive days. Blood samples were collected in the morning prior to treatment on day one, and in between and after 2 weeks. Assessment of prior and ongoing bleeding and treatments, e.g. drugs and transfusions, were recorded. The study was approved by the local Ethics Committee of the national center of hematology in Almustansiriya University.

Laboratory assays

Complete blood count was analyzed by Abbotts cell-Dyn auto-analyzer used in the laboratory unit at the national center of hematology. Prothrombin time (PT) represented by international normalization ratio (INR) was determined using Stago Prothrombin complex Assay (Method according to Owren) (16) (SPA; Diagnostica Stago, Asnières, France). Activated partial thrombin time (APTT) was analyzed using stago assay (SPA; Diagnostica Stago, Asnières, France), while plasma fibrinogen was assessed by claus technique using a commercially available kit (Diagnostica Stago /France).

Data were analyzed using SPSS (version 15 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). A t-test for independent samples was used. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Fifty-eight patients met the criteria for entering the study; thirty two were males and twenty six females, their ages ranged from 15 - 65 years with median of 43 years.

According to the French-American-British (FAB) classification of acute leukemia [14], one patient was categorized as M0, 17 patients as M1, 29 patients as M2, 4 patients as M4, 5 patients as M5 and 2 patient as M6. no M7 was recorded. At presentation 22 patients (37.9%) had bleeding manifestations.

Thrombocytopenia was present in 42 patients (72.4%), and 18 patients (31%) had some abnormalities of global coagulation markers.

Results of the hemostatic analyses, shown in table 1 as before chemotherapy (Day 1), and at the end of the observation period (after 2 weeks). Hb was decreased during the study period with the lowest values observed after chemotherapy. Platelets were low prior to the beginning of treatment and declined significantly thereafter. INR was significantly elevated at days 3-5 while APTT was significantly prolonged after 2 weeks, at the other time points the values were well within their respective reference intervals. During the study period, 22 patients had hemorrhagic incidents. Five patients had oozing from the gum. Two patients had epistaxis. Five patients had bleeding per rectum only, three had gastrointestinal bleeding and seven had vaginal bleeding. Fifty patients were transfused with a median (Range) of 6 (3-9) units of packed erythrocyte and 45 patients had 4 (1-15) units platelets.

Table 1: Results of hemostatic analysis

Hemostatic parameter	before treatment median(range)	after treatment(2 weeks) median(range)	P value
Hb, g/dL	9.2 (5.1-15.2)	6.7 (6.1- 8.9)	0.001
Platelet count($\times 10^9/L$)	65 (50- 174)	18 (11-54)	0.001
INR	1.1 (1.0- 1.5)	1.3 (1.0- 2.1)	NS
APTT, s	32 (26-36)	35 (30-45)	NS
FVII, %	90(55-150)	85(60-140)	NS
Fibrinogen g/dL	220(190-450)	200(185-400)	NS

NS= not significant

Discussion

The probability of developing severe hemorrhages varies according to the type of acute leukemia and type of therapy, APL (AML M3 subtype) typically presents with life-threatening hemorrhagic syndrome. The abnormalities of blood clotting system underlying the clinical pictures of coagulopathy in APL include hypofibrinogenemia increased levels of fibrin degradation products (F.D.Ps.), and prolonged prothrombin time and thrombin times(15).

The major determinants for pathogenesis of coagulopathy of acute myeloid leukemia are:

1-Factors associated with leukemia cells including the expression of procoagulant, fibrinolytic & proteolytic properties & the secretion of cytokines

2-cytotoxic therapy.

3-concomitant infectious complications.

In this study there was significant difference in hemoglobin and platelets count between the two period which agree with most of other studies(8,9,15,20); this explained by the effect of chemotherapy on the bone marrow. Regarding median APTT, this study revealed that it was normal at presentation and slightly prolonged at the end of the observation period, PT represented by INR behaved in a similar way. These findings show an initial ongoing increased thrombin generation that occurs before consumption of clotting factors is apparent in global hemostatic tests (e.g. prolonged APTT). In other previous studies, it has been found that APTT to be the global test which best predicts outcome in the intensive care unit regarding bleeding [16, 17]. The presence of hypofibrinogenemia, reflected by low plasma fibrin, showed the same pattern as the markers for bleeding tendency. [15]. This study showed that there was no difference in fibrinogen level before and after therapy in contrast to that found in the majority of APL cases and in some reported cases of AML-M4. (20)We found that concentrations of factor

7 which have the shortest life span among other factors remained at stable level throughout the observation period, contrary to the findings of the same investigators who reported decline after induction therapy (13). Of interest is that despite the low and stable factor 7 levels during the observation period, changes in the INR could be observed after induction chemotherapy. Although the size of the material in the current investigation limits the ability to investigate survival related to APC- PCI complex concentration or other coagulation parameters, the use of hemostatic parameters (as e.g. global hemostatic tests) remain as sensitive for early detection of bleeding diathesis in acute leukemia (20). A sensitive, specific and early marker of activation of the coagulation system would potentially provide the clinician with a tool for making timely decisions in the treatment of coagulation disturbances, thereby perhaps improving the outcome for this patient group. Our data indicate that there were no differences in coagulation tests in patient with AML at presentation and chemotherapy has negligible effect on the coagulation pathway. Despite of that it is recommended that all patients with acute leukemia be investigated for coagulopathy at presentation and be follow-up after completion of chemotherapy so that not to miss unusual presentation in non-promyelocytic leukemia.

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Salivary IgA and alkaline phosphatase level In thalassemia major patients

Fawaz. D. Abdl Razaq*

Abstract

Background: Thalassemias are a group of inherited defects in the synthesis of either α or β polypeptide chains of the globin portion of hemoglobin molecule, and therefore, referred as α and β type subjects.

Subjects materials and method: The study included 15 patients with thalassemia major (8 male and 7 female) and group of 15 healthy control (7male and 8 female). Unstimulated saliva was collected from each subject and alkaline phosphatase and Immunoglobulin A was determined

Result: Asignificant difference relationship of immunoglobulin A and alkaline phosphatase enzyme in patients with thalassemia major compared to healthy control.

Conclusion: This study was the first study that measure salivary alkaline phosphatase and immunogloblin. A in Iraqi thalassemic patient, further investigations are needed to determine the theoretical risk of oral diseases in thalassemia patients.

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Key words: thalassemia. IgA. Alkaline phosphatase.

Introduction

The thalassemia are a family of inherited disorders of hemoglobin. synthesis characterized by a reduced output of one or other of the globin chains of adult hemoglobin [1]. The homozygous type that is known as β -thalassemia major or Cooley's anemia is the most common monogenic disorder in the Mediterranean basin, the Middle East, Asia and South Pacific [2]. The defensive role of saliva is mainly played via immunoglobulins. Periodontal infections are the most common diseases in oral cavity and therefore defensive function of saliva against these infections are important. With regard to the effects of systemic diseases on defensive function of saliva [3].

Therefore, the secretory IgA appears to have prime importance in immune exclusion of pathogenic

microorganisms and maintenance of intestinal homeostasis. Despite this critical role, there may be some compensatory mechanisms that would prevent disease manifestations in some IgA deficient individuals [4].

Alkaline phosphatase (Alp) is an important enzyme mainly derived from the liver, bone and in lesser amounts from intestine, placenta, kidneys and leukocytes, an increase in Alp level in the serum is frequently the associated with a variety of diseases[5], and since no extensive study was conducted in Iraq on the association of IgA and Alp in the saliva of thalassemia major, therefore the proposal of this study was to examine the levels of IgA and Alp in β -thalassemia major patients and to compare them with a matched non thalassemic health control subjects.

Subjects, Materials and Methods

The sample in this study composed of 15 patients with an age ranged (15 - 36) years old (8 male and 7

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females) attending the Al Zahrawi Hospital in Baghdad prior to the study, thalassemic centre agreed to cooperate with as on this study.

Seven to eight ml of unstimulated saliva (resting) collected after asking the individual to rinse his or her mouth with water, the saliva collected into small plastic polyethylene tube the and centrifuged to 1500 RPM for 10 minutes the supernatant later used for biochemical study including Alp by using Biomajhreb kit, and immunological study for salivary

IgA by using (Radial immunodifusion plate IgA RID. REF code number).

Result

The age and sex distribution of the total sample is shown in table (1), figure (1), the mean age of thalassemic patient (19.8 years) and health control (20 years).

Table 1: Age & sex distribution of the total sample.

Sample	Age Groups	Frequency	Percent	C.S. P-value
Study	< 15 yrs.	1	6.7	C.C.=0.077 P=0.996 NS
	15 -19 yrs.	8	53.3	
	20 -24 yrs.	4	26.7	
	25 -29 yrs.	1	6.7	
	30 > yrs.	1	6.7	
Control	< 15 yrs.	1	6.7	
	15 -19 yrs.	7	46.7	
	20 -24 yrs.	5	33.3	
	25 -29 yrs.	1	6.7	
	30 > yrs.	1	6.7	

Figure (1): Age & sex distribution of total sample.

IgA analysis

In order to studying and analyzing the observation of the studied parameter (IgA – Indicator) and creating a new standard limitation for the study group of thalassemia disease, according to inferential whole restricted cases in stability of, stem leaf plotting/ or explorer method had been used, the procedure of this method depending on the order statistic of the actual observation ascending form with determining the (1st & 3rd) Quartiles. The form I pointed the lower and upper sides or data limitation which included the ordered observation of that having less than two degree of deviation by their mean value (2 STd Dev) and the two edges belong to the first and third quartiles and the median value between them (figure 2).

Figure (2): Stem-Leaf Plots (Explorer) for the studied parameter (IgA -Indicator) by applying the smoothing of the suggested technique.

For summarization to the process of creating a standardized limitation (table 2). We can conclude that all readings of the study group had been accepted including that contaminated diagnosed in the downstairs/ or upstairs, while at the control group the contaminated points should be excluded in one side until the final iteration which were achieved, and the chose's side depending on which direction of abnormal/ or defected region would be. This suggested technique is working as a smoothing tool and the finally when a non-contaminated value (s) presented lower/ (or upper) side of control group. In this study the lower base line (downstairs) of control group would be the critical base line (upstairs) of the study group.

Table 2: Standardized limitation for the studied parameter (IgA) by applying the smoothing of the suggested technique.

IgA –Indicator for "Thalassemia"	139.1 ≤
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Again, there was a statistically difference between the mean of IgA of thalassemia patients (135.22 ± 45.25) and those of the parallel group of healthy group (177.49 ± 19.24) (table 3). Figure (3) shows the IgA according to sex distribution, a significant correlation was exist when compared the IgA in male, while non-significant relation as compared the IgA in female (table 4).

Table3: Summary statistics for IgA & ALP indicators of studying thalassemia disease in the study and control groups.

Parameters	Groups	N	Mean	Std. D.	Std. E.
IgA µg/ mL	Study	15	135.22	45.25	11.68
	Control	15	177.49	19.24	4.97
ALP IU/ L	Study	15	5.27	0.27	0.07
	Control	15	4.59	0.45	0.12

Figure (3): Cylinder bar chart for means values of IgA indicator of studying thalassemia disease in the study and control Groups in male and female.

Table 4: Comparison significant for IgA & ALP indicators of studying thalassemia disease among different groups in male and female.

Parameters	Equality of variances test Levene's test		Equality of means test ANOVA test		C.S. P-value
	Statistic	P-value	Statistic	P-value	
IgA in (Male)	10.450	0.006	-2.384	0.040	S
ALP in (Male)	3.213	0.095	3.302	0.005	HS
IgA in (Female)	21.141	0.001	-2.227	0.056	NS
ALP in (Female)	4.278	0.061	3.654	0.003	HS

Biochemical (Alkaline phosphatase)

As shown in table (3, 4) the descriptive statistics of Alp in both thalassemic patients and control group, the mean of Alp in the study group and its standard deviation (5.27 ± 0.27) which was higher than its level in healthy control (4.59 ± 0.45). Chi. Square (C. S). Test was applied to test significance the result was a highly significant difference ($P < 0.01$) (table 5).

Figure (5) shows the Alp according to the sex distribution, by applying C. S. test, a highly significant correlation was established between male and female (table 4). Finally age group recorded non-significant differences at $p > 0.05$ in the samples (study, control) according to the IgA, Alp parameters (table 6).

Table 5: Comparison Significant for IgA & ALP indicators of studying thalassemia disease among different groups.

Parameters	Equality of variances test Levene's test		Equality of means test ANOVA test		C.S. P-value
	Statistic	P-value	Statistic	P-value	
IgA	24.564	0.000	18.901	0.004	HS
ALP	7.789	0.009	22.777	0.000	HS

Figure (5): Cylinder bar chart for means values of ALP indicator of studying thalassemia disease in the study and control groups in male and female.

Table 6: Comparison Significant by ANOVA test for IgA & ALP indicators of studying thalassemia disease among different groups in different age groups.

ANOVA-test							
Sample	Parameters	S.O.V.	Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Study	IgA	Between Groups	6,469.84	4	1,617.46	0.73	0.592
		Within Groups	22,194.22	10	2,219.42		
		Total	28,664.05	14			
	ALP	Between Groups	0.07	4	0.02	0.19	0.939
		Within Groups	0.93	10	0.09		
		Total	1.00	14			
Control	IgA	Between Groups	1,728.79	4	432.20	1.25	0.351
		Within Groups	3,452.91	10	345.29		
		Total	5,181.70	14			
	ALP	Between Groups	0.97	4	0.24	1.30	0.335
		Within Groups	1.87	10	0.19		
		Total	2.84	14			

Discussion

A number of clinical studies have analyzed the status of the oral cavities in thalassemic patients considering both dental, periodontal condition and orofacial complication [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. The concentration of the biochemical components in saliva play an important in the oral diseases, but few studies examine this in connection with thalassemic.

A lower IgA level in saliva of thalassemics has been reported in thalassemic patients, this had similarities with other researches [11, 12, 13, 14, 15], which may be contributing to T-cell independent mechanism production of IgA [16,17], also the abnormalities in the cytokine net such as lack of IL-21, Interleukin have also been proposed to play a role in IgA deficiency[18,19,20], while[16] stated that there was no significant difference between the rate of IgA in thalassemic and normal patients.

This variation may also arise from the fact that the definition of selective IgA deficiency may differ in each study registry.

An elevated level of Alp was observed more frequently in patients with thalassemia as compared to healthy control, this study is in agreement with the study carried out by [21, 22], this may be attributed to a variety of non specific diseases as extra hepatic bile obstruction, intra hepatic

cholestasis, hepatitis due to blood transfusion or because of the accelerated de novo, synthesis of the enzyme and subsequent regurgitation in to the serum [7,8].

Conclusion

The exact cellular and molecular mechanism as involved in biochemical and immunological changes in thalassemia patient need to be further elucidated.

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The effect of transversus abdominis block on decreasing pain following inguinal hernia repair

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Abstract

Objective: to evaluate the transversus abdominis block for treating pain after inguinal hernia repair operations.

Methods: this study included 60 patients who were allocated in to 2 groups in a random manner r: Group B (Transversus abdominal block, 30 patients received transversus abdominis in addition to an intravenous single-injection of morphine 5 mg). Group M (control group, 30 patients received morphine 5mg intravenously). The patient degree of pain was evaluated postoperatively.

Results: There were 60 patients, 30 in each group. Postoperatively, pain scores were significantly less in group b than group m

Conclusion: transversus abdominis block given before operation improves postoperative pain after inguinal hernia.

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Key words: Postoperative pain, transversus abdominis block, inguinal hernia.

Introduction

Postoperative pain control has been managed in many ways. With different therapeutic versus side effect profile for each. Non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs devoid of sedation and respiratory depression, however, it is associated with potentially serious side effect such as gastrointestinal bleeding and renal

impairment [1]. Opioids have been commonly used for postoperative pain management but they are associated with respiratory depression and sedation [2].

Regional or local anesthesia can be used for postoperative pain control and could avoid common systemic side effect side effect associated with other drugs [3].

Several studies show that preoperative transverses abdominis plane block improves postoperative pain significantly after abdominal surgery [4].

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of preoperative transverses abdominis plane block in decreasing postoperative pain after inguinal hernia repair operations.

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Methods

Sixty patients of ASA I-III, undergoing unilateral inguinal hernia repair were enrolled in the study. After applying suitable monitoring and inserting an intravenous cannula, Anesthesia was induced in the usual manner using Fentanyl, Propofol and atracurium. Larangal mask airway was inserted. Patients were randomized to receive either TAP block in addition to morphine 5 mg intravenously (group b, n=30) or morphine 5 mg intravenously (group m, n=30).

After induction of anesthesia and while the patient is sleeping tap block was performed at the site of the operation by using the following technique:

The triangle of petit which is considered the main landmark of the operation is identified firstly by palpating the iliac crest inferiorly, latissimus dorsi posteriorly and the external oblique anteriorly. After identifying this land marks, 22 G 50 mm needle was used to enter this triangle in a right angle until the first resistance was encountered which indicates that the needle was entering the fascia of the external oblique muscle. The needle then advanced further in the same direction to encounter the second resistance which indicates the entrance into the transverses abdominis facial plan.

The local anesthetic agent then injected carefully (0.5 ml/kg bupivacaine 0.25%). The selected dose of morphine 0.1 mg/kg has been given to all patients intravenously.

Patients were asked to rate their pain according to Visual analogue pain scale (VAS; 0 mm=no pain, 100 mm=worst pain imaginable), VAS was recorded for both groups every 2 hourly for the first 4 hours. If patient recorded pain more than 30 mm, additional IV boluses of morphine 2 mg were administered by nurse. The amount of morphine given was recorded for both groups. Data were analyzed using student's t-test.

Results

Sixty patients were included in this study, 30 in each group. Patient's data were comparable for both groups as shown in table 1. pain scores during the first 4 hours postoperatively are shown in table 2, they are significantly less in group b than group m over the 4 hours $p < 0.05$.

Table 1: Patient characteristic, in both groups. Data are mean (range), mean (SD).

	TAP Group (b) n=30	Control Group (m) n=30
Sex (m/f)	28/2	27/3
Age (yr.)	43(17-80)	41(17-78)
Weight (kg)	65(9)	21/6/3
ASA class (I/II/III)	20/8/2	67(12)

Table 2: Mean (SD) pain scores for 2 groups.

	GT	GM	P value
0h	21 (1.2)	33 (1.5)	< 0.05
2h	18 (1.1)	31 (1.2)	< 0.05
4h	13 (1.2)	22 (1.3)	< 0.05
12h	6 (1.1)	13 (1.3)	< 0.05
24h	5 (1.2)	14 (1.1)	< 0.05

Discussion

Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most commonly performed surgical procedures worldwide. Postoperative analgesia is very important for patient satisfaction and preventing respiratory and cardiovascular complications [5]. Other known advantages of effective regional analgesic techniques include reduced pain intensity, decrease incidence of side effects from analgesics, and improved patient comfort [6].

The success of the tap block depends on the applied anatomy, the innervations of the anterior abdominal layers is by the lower six thoracic nerves and the first lumbar nerve [7].

The anterior primary rami of these nerves pierce the abdominal wall musculature course through a facial plane between the internal oblique and transversus abdominal muscle [7]. So the local anesthetic given is deposited on the transversus abdominis plane. And provide sensory and muscle blockade.

This study indicates that TAP blockade decreased the pain after hernia repair operations during the first 24 hours. Similar finding for inguinal hernia or other type of operations have been confirmed by other authors [8, 9].

In this study we found the effect of this block on pain extended to 24 hrs. Postoperatively the pharmacological effect of bupivacaine cannot be

expected to cover this time finding may be explained. The reasons for the prolonged duration of analgesic may relate to the fact that the TAP is relatively poorly vascularized, and therefore drug clearance may be slowed, by a pre-emptive effect of the block (reducing the nociceptive input to the central nervous system in the first hour after surgery may have attenuated central sensitization, thereby leading to less postoperative pain, but we think that this is very debatable issue).

A variety of local and regional anesthetic procedures for Pain control after have been described after laparoscopic cholecystectomy with the goals of providing optimal pain control and avoiding complications has the important after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. in this study we have not reported any clinically significant complications.

Ultrasound-guided sensory block of the anterior abdominal wall has been used recently in many studies and it has been associated with better results because of better identification [10, 11].

Conclusion

Transversus abdominis block decreases pain significantly after inguinal hernia repair.

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Findings of flexible laryngoscope in patients with hoarseness

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Abstract

Background: With increasing stress due to day life, rising level of pollution and changing habit and life styles hoarseness and voice disorders are becoming more and more prevalent.

Aims:

- 1 -To emphasize the role of flexible laryngoscope in diagnosis of hoarseness.
- 2 -To determine the incidence of different causes of hoarseness.

Patients and Methods: During the period of one year, (100) patients aged between 3-70 years presented with hoarseness were seen in ENT department in Al-Kadhymia Teaching Hospital in Baghdad. Flexible laryngoscope was done for all them in whom indirect laryngoscope was unsatisfactory. Only (37) patients required subsequent direct laryngoscope under general anesthesia.

Results :Out of total number of patients (100), the data were collected and analyzed according to sex , age, duration of hoarseness, association symptoms and clinical finding on flexible laryngoscope (54) male , (46) female , (25%) had squamous cell carcinoma (S.cc) of larynx, (20%) vocal cord palsy , (16%) vocal cord polyp , (12%) vocal cord nodule, (5%) Renkie's oedema, (10%) chronic non-specific laryngitis, (4%) acute laryngitis, (6%) function dysphonic, (1%) laryngeal papillomatosis and (1%) vocal cord webs.

Conclusions:

- 1 -The use of flexible laryngoscope had great value in diagnosis of hoarseness and examination of larynx.
- 2 -Squamous cell carcinoma of larynx constitute the major cause of hoarseness in elderly patients.
- 3 -Gastro- esophageal reflux disease GERD is an important predisposing factor. In chronic nonspecific laryngitis, vocal cord polyp, nodule and functional dysphonia.

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Keywords: Hoarseness, Flexible Laryngoscope.

Introduction

Hoarseness: defined as vocal roughness resulting from random variation in the periodicity and/or intensity of consecutive waves [1], by other words, hoarseness is perceived cough, harsh or breathy quality to voice [2].

Flexible fiberoptic laryngoscope: Is a device in which a bundle of fiberoptic strands are collected

into flexible instrument which has the ability to manipulated (round corners), the illumination runs through some fibers threads and the operator receives a picture from the distal ends of endoscope. The fiberoptic laryngoscope has been designed into numbers of diameters and length [3].

Patients & Method

During the period from January 2009 to January 2010, 100 patients aged between 3-70 years presented with hoarseness were seen in E.N.T department, Al-Kadhymia Teaching Hospital at Al-Nahrain University. After a thorough history and full ENT examination, Flexible fiberoptic laryngoscope under local anesthesia had been done for all of them by the following procedure:

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calculated for the results as follow; significant when the $P \leq 0.001$ non-significant when the $P \geq 0.001$.

The nose is inspected and the wider side chosen, if there is significant difference. This is sprayed up to 1cc of 10% xylocaine solution along the oropharynx and back of tongue 5-6 sprays of xylocaine (50-60mg). Adequate time (5-10 minutes) should be allowed to obtain adequate anesthesia. Trans-nasal examination of the postnasal space; the pharynx and larynx performed with short and thin endoscopy have diameter ≤ 5 mm and length of approximation 300mm.

Statistical analysis: The chi-square(χ^2) test was used to evaluate the association between categorical variables; to determine whether association was significant the P value was

Results

1 - Age: In the present study, the age ranged from 3-70 years. The most common age group seen was the fourth and fifth decade with a mean age value 45 years.

After analysis of history, examination and available investigations the causes of hoarseness distributed according to age group shown in Table (1).

2 - Sex: (Table-2) in our study, there were 54 male and 46 female. Male to female ratio was 1.14.

3 - Duration of hoarseness at presentation: (Table-3).Varies from few weeks to several months

Table (1): Causes of hoarseness according to etiology and age group 100 patients.

Causes of hoarseness	Age Group (years)							Total	%
	1-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70		
1- Malignant (squamous cell carcinoma)	-	-	-	-	-	7	18	25	25%
2- Benign lesion									
- V.C. polyp	-	-	2	4	6	2	-	16	16%
- V.C. nodule	-	2	7	3	-	-	-	12	12%
- Renkie's edema	-	-	-	-	-	2	3	5	5%
Total								33	33%
3- Neurological causes (Vocal cord paralysis)	-	2	2	5	8	3	-	20	20%
4- Inflammatory causes									
- Chronic laryngitis (non-specific)	-	-	2	2	-	-	-	4	4%
- Acute laryngitis	-	-	2	2	-	-	-	4	4%
Total								8	8%
5- Functional (muscle tension dysphonia)	-	3	2	1	-	-	-	6	6%
6- Congenital									
- Vocal cord web	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1%
- Juvenile respiratory papillomatosis	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1%

Table (2): Causes of hoarseness distributed according to sex.

Cause of hoarseness	No. of patients	Male	Female	Male/ female ratio %
1- Benign lesion				
- Vocal cord polyps	16	10	6	1.66
- Vocal cord nodule	12	4	8	0.5
- Renkie's edema	5	2	3	0.66
2- Malignant lesion				
- Squamous cell CA.	25	23	2	11.5
3- Neurological cause vocal cord paralysis				
4- Inflammatory				
- Acute laryngitis	4	2	2	1
- Chronic non-specific laryngitis	10	3	7	0.4
5- Functional				
6- Congenital				
- Vocal cord web		1	-	1
- Juvenile respiratory papillomatosis		1	-	1

$\chi^2=20.31$ $P=0.00001$ (significant).

Table (3): Duration of hoarseness at presentation.

Causes of hoarseness	No. of patients	Duration of hoarseness
1- Benign lesion		
- Vocal cord polyps	16	2-4 months
- Vocal cord nodule	12	2-3 months
- Renkie's edema	5	3-6 months
2- Squamous cell CA of larynx		
	25	3-9 months
3- Neurological cause vocal cord paralysis		
	20	2 wks - 3 months
4- Inflammatory		
- Acute laryngitis	4	2 wks
- Chronic non-specific laryngitis	10	2-6 months
5- Functional		
	6	1 wk - 2 months
6- Congenital		
- Vocal cord web	1	4-6 months
- Juvenile respiratory papillomatosis	1	5-9 months

4 - Finding of flexible laryngoscope; the findings were variable as shown in Table (4):

- (25) Patients had glottic and/or supraglottic mass, proved by direct laryngoscope with histopathology to be squamous cell carcinoma of larynx. All were smokers and (4) patients had positive history of GERD.

- (20) Patients had immobile vocal cords, (9) of them were smokers, (4) had history of GERD and (2) had history of voice abuse.

- (1) Patients had left vocal cord paralysis. (8) of them had previous thyroid surgery. (4) had history of neck trauma (blast injury). (2) had no cause (idiopathic).

- (4) Patients had right vocal cord paralysis. (2) had history of neck trauma (blast injury). (1) had previous thyroid surgery.

- (2) Patients had bilateral vocal cord paralysis :(1) had previous thyroid surgery and the other had no cause (idiopathic).

- (16) Patients had vocal cord polyp, (12) had history of voice abuse, (8) were smokers and (6) patients had history of GERD.

- (12) Patients had bilateral vocal cord nodule. (8) patients had history of voice abuse, (4) had history of GERD and (2) were smokers.

- (4) Patients had acute laryngitis :(2) patients had history of voice abuse and (2) had GERD and only one was smoker.

- (6) Patients had functional dysphonia. (4) patients had history of voice abuse (3) had GERD and (2) were smokers.

- (5) Patients had Reinke's edema. (4) patients were smoker, (2) had history of voice abuse and (3) patients had GERD.

Table (4): Finding of flexible laryngoscope.

flexible laryngoscope finding	No. of patients	%	Requiring D.L
1- Glottic and/or supraglottic mass	25	25	25
2- Immobile vocal cord paralysis			
- Left	14	14	
- Right paralysis	4	4	
- Bilateral	2	2	
3- Vocal cord polyp	16	16	8
4-non-specific laryngitis			
- Chronic	10	10	2
- Acute laryngitis	4	4	---
5- Vocal cord nodule	12	12	---
6- Reinke's edemas	5	5	2
7- No abnormality (functional dysphonia)	6	6	---
8- Vocal cord web	1	1	---
9- Juvenile respiratory papillomatosis	1	1	---
	100	100	37

Discussion

In our study, flexible fiberoptic laryngoscope was done for (100) patients presented with hoarseness in whom indirect laryngoscope was unsatisfactory. Only (37) patients required direct laryngoscope.

William GT et al., (1975) examined (72) patient with flexible in the Royal infirmary of Edinburgh over three months duration, the patient were not a selected group. The study showed that flexible laryngoscope allow unhurried laryngeal visualization in patient in whom with flexible laryngoscope, the larynx can be observed in natural action of swallowing, breathing, coughing and speaking [4].

Welch AR, (1982) performed flexible laryngoscope on (60) patients with hoarseness referred to ENT department of Leicester Royal infirmary over a 2-year period in whom indirect laryngoscope was unsatisfactory. Only (23) patients of the sixty examined required direct laryngoscope [5]. Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C. Sagar (2004) performed flexible laryngoscope on (100) patients presented with hoarseness referred to ENT department at Safdarjung Hospital (New Delhi) Only (18) patient required direct laryngoscope [6].

Malignant Lesion:

- In this study (25%) squamous cell carcinoma of larynx (S.C.C.) which is the largest group.
- William GT et al., (1975) found that (5.5%) had (S.C.C) [4].
- Welch AR (1982) found that (5%) had (S.C.C.). [5].

- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani, P.C Sagar (2004) found that (18%) had S.C.C. [6].

Neurological Cause:

- Vocal cord paralysis is the most common cause.
- In my study (20%) had vocal cord paralysis (V.C.P.).
- Welch AR study (1982) found that (6.6%) had (V.C.P.) [5].
- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C. Sagar (2004) found that only (9%) had V.C.P. [6].
- Benninger et al (1994) found 8.8% had V.C.P. [7].

Vocal Cord Polyp:

- Our study (16%) had vocal cord polyp.
- William GT et al., (1975) (2.7%) had V. cord polyp [4].
- Welch AR (1982) (3%) had vocal cord polyp [5].
- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C. Sagar (2004) (13.8%) [6].

Vocal Cord Nodule:

- Our study (12%) had vocal cord nodule.
- William GT et al., (1975) (8.3%) [4].
- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C. Sagar (2004) (19.6%) [6].
- Bouchyer et al 1988 showed 24% [8].

Reinke's Oedema:

- Our study (5%) had Reinke's oedema
- William GT, et al., (1975) (5.5%) [4].
- Welch AR (1982) no one has Reinke's edema (0%) [5].
- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C. Sagar (2004) (1%) [6].
- Kauffmann I. (1992) 33% [9].

Inflammatory:

- Our study (14%) had laryngitis.
- (10%) had chronic non-specific laryngitis.
- (4%) had acute laryngitis following upper respiratory tract infection.
- William G.T et al., (1975) (33.2%) had chronic laryngitis [4].
- Welch, AR (1982) (16.6%) had chronic laryngitis [5].
- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C Sagar (2004) showed that: (8%) had chronic laryngitis, (7%) had tubercular laryngitis and (7%) had post-irradiation laryngitis [6].
- Sasaki (1991) 12 patients with T.B larynx who complain of hoarseness 10 of them had got cavities in CXR, all of them the sputum smear were positive [10].

Functional:

- In t study (6%) of patients had function dysphonic the diagnosis is by exclusion other causes.
 - (4) patients were female and history of anxiety and depression.
 - (2) Patients were boys and had puberophonia.
- William G.T et al., (1975) (4.1%) had functional voice change:
 - One had hysterical aphonia.
 - One had functional dysphonia.
 - One had functional spastic dysphonia [4].
- Welch AR study (1982) showed that (51.6%) had functional dysphonia [5].
- Kadambari Batra, Gulmotwani and P.C sugar (2004) showed that functional voice disorder was the largest group (51%).
- They had found a new concept that lesion such as vocal cord polyp, nodular and granuloma, were secondary to vocal abuse , misuse syndrome, that they should included in functional voice disorders [6].
- Bridger et al (1983) recorded 109 patients presented with functional voice disorder during 4 years and the female to male ratio was 2:1 [11].

Gastro-esophageal reflux disease

In this study (GERD) is an important predisposing factor for acute laryngitis (2 out of 4 patients), vocal cord polyp(6 out of 16), vocal cord nodule(4 out of 12) , Reinke's oedema(3out 5) and functional dysphonia(3out of 6).

Baris Naiboglu et al 2011(in Turkey), GERD was determined by esophagogastroduedonoscopy and biopsy in 127 patients responsible for laryngopharyngeal symptoms and signs and Empiric antireflux treatment has a significant improving effect on laryngopharyngeal symptoms and signs [12].

Congenital:

- In our study, two children were identified, both were boys. One was (2) years old had laryngeal web in anterior commissure and the other (4) years old with juvenile respiratory papillomatosis (J.R.P.).
- In William GL et al., (1975) -only (2.7%) had juvenile respiratory papillomatosis [4].

Conclusions

1. In approaching the problem of hoarseness, the application of flexible system laryngoscope has an important role to play in the examination of the larynx.
2. Much unnecessary hospital admission for direct laryngoscope may be avoided by using flexible laryngoscope which is simple, safe, reliable and economical

procedure when indirect laryngoscope has been unsatisfactory.

3. Gastro-esophageal reflux disease (GERD) is an important predisposing factor in laryngitis, vocal cord polyp, vocal cord nodule and functional dysphonia.
4. Hoarseness in a child must not be dismissed as being the result of vocal abuse since respiratory papillomatosis with its potential risk could be the cause.
5. Functional dysphonia associated with stress, anxiety and depression.

Recommendation

Perform flexible laryngoscope for all patients with hoarseness of voice.

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Tramadol: subcutaneous wound infiltration versus intravenous administration after inguinal hernia operations

Muhammed Niazy Ghany *, Tayeb S. Kareem **

Abstract

Background and Objectives: Some studies have shown that opioids have a local analgesic effect with minimal side effects. The aim of the study is to compare the therapeutic effects and possible side effects of intravenous versus local wound infiltration of tramadol following open inguinal hernia operations.

Patients & Methods: A comparative prospective study of 50 adult male patients who underwent inguinal hernia repair during the period from September 2009 to March 2010 in the surgical units of both Erbil Teaching Hospital and Rizgari Teaching Hospital in Erbil. Patients were divided randomly into two groups:

Subcutaneous group (SC) (n=25): received tramadol subcutaneously at the wound prior to skin closure.

Intravenous group (IV) (n=25): received tramadol intravenously within 15 minutes prior to skin closure.

Postoperative pain and complications such as nausea and vomiting were recorded at time of receiving the patients in the ward, after 30 minutes, hourly for six hours then at 12 hour and 24 hour postoperatively.

Results: The VAS score was reported to be higher in the IV group throughout the study. Nausea and vomiting occurred less frequently in the SC group. This was statistically highly significant. Only 1(4.0%) case in SC group required diclofenac while 4(16%) cases in IV group required this drug.

Conclusion: Subcutaneous wound infiltration with tramadol after open inguinal hernia operations reduces postoperative analgesic consumption and produces less nausea and vomiting than does intravenous administration.

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Key words: Tramadol; hernia; pain; subcutaneous infiltration.

Introduction

Inguinal hernias are very common and their repair is one of the most frequently performed surgical operations [1]. It is frequently associated with persistent postoperative discomfort and distress for

the patient and late discharge from the hospital with a loss of the cost-saving benefit [2].

It is well known that undertreated acute pain has harmful effects on all systems of the body [3]. Postoperative pain resulted from the fact that the physical processes of incision, traction, and cutting of tissues stimulate free nerve endings and specific nociceptors [4]. The surgical stress response (SSR) peaks in the postoperative period and has major effects on the cardiac, coagulation, and immune systems of the body [5]. Brodner et al. have highlighted that blocking the SSR results in earlier

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extubation and ambulation, thus augmenting recovery and decreasing cost [6]. Post-herniorrhaphy pain is usually treated by either Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs or opioids that are administered either alone or in combination with acetaminophen [7]. Opioids provide effective analgesia but side-effects, especially respiratory depression, emesis and sedation, reduce the advantages of these medications in outpatient surgery [8].

The aim of the study is to compare the therapeutic effects and possible complications of intravenous versus local wound infiltration of tramadol following open inguinal hernia operations.

Patients & Methods

A comparative prospective study was carried out in the surgical units of both Erbil Teaching Hospital and Rizgari Teaching Hospital in Erbil. All adult male patients of the ASA physical status I-II, who underwent inguinal hernia repair under general anesthesia, during the period from September 2009 to March 2010, were enrolled in the study. Exclusion criteria were patients with definite liver disease, renal impairment, history of opium addiction, allergy to tramadol, history of seizure disorder, or administration of monoamine oxidase inhibitors, naloxone, cimetidine, carbamazepine, and ondansetron. Patients refusing general anesthesia were also excluded from the study. The operations done by more than one surgeon and the type of the operations selected according to the surgeons preference. Patients were allocated randomly into one of two groups:

Subcutaneous group (SC): (n=27) received subcutaneous wound infiltration contained tramadol 2 mg/kg titrated with NaCl 0.9% for a total of 20 ml. The infiltration started from the external oblique aponeurosis up to the skin prior to skin closure.

Intravenous group (IV): (n=28) tramadol 2 mg/kg plus NaCl 0.9% to a volume of 50 ml was infused slowly within 15 minutes prior to skin closure.

We used Tramadol Hexal AG (Bach No. 8M1031) in both groups. Intravenous administration performed by the anesthetist while subcutaneous wound infiltration with tramadol done by the surgeon.

Postoperative assessment of the intensity of pain as measured by a 10- mm visual analog scale (VAS), and complications such as nausea and vomiting were recorded at time of receiving the patients in the ward (Regarded as zero time), after 30 minutes, hourly for six hours then at 12 hour and 24 hour postoperatively. Diclofenac 75 mg/dose was administered intramuscularly when pain intensity was greater than 4 and intravenous metoclopramide 10 mg/dose was prescribed when nausea and vomiting were present.

Informed consent obtained from all patients. The study approved by local Research Ethics Committee. The statistical analysis done by SPSS version 17 and Epi Info version 6. Parametric tests (T-test, Chi square and Fisher exact test) were used for comparison between the results of the two groups. P value less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Two patients in SC group & 3 patients in IV group initially assigned were excluded due to incomplete data collection. The remained (25 in SC group and 25 in IV group) were included in the study. The age of the patients in SC group ranged between 18-71 (mean 35.96) years and their weight ranged 42-104 (mean 68.48) Kg. while in IV group the age ranged between 18-69 (mean 39.67) years and the weight ranged between 48-90 (mean 65.32) Kg. The VAS score was reported to be higher in the IV group throughout the study. These scores were found to be highly significant at 3hr & up ward till 24hr (p = 0.00) (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparison of the changes in the VAS scores during the study.

Parameter	SC±SD	IV±SD	P value	Mean difference	95% C.I
VAS at zero time	0.28 ± 0.61	0.6 ± 0.5	0.04	-0.32	-0.63 to -0.00
VAS at 30 mint	0.8 ± 0.70	1.12 ± 0.52	0.07	-0.32	-0.67 to 0.03
VAS at 1hr	1.20 ± 0.81	1.20 ± 0.91	1.0	0.00	-0.49 to 0.49
VAS at 2hr	0.96 ± 0.88	1.12 ± 0.66	0.47	-0.16	0.60 to 0.28
VAS at 3hr	0.96 ± 0.53	1.36 ± 0.48	0.00	-0.40	-0.69 to -0.10
VAS at 4hr	1.04 ± 0.35	1.36 ± 0.56	0.02	-0.32	-0.58 to -0.05
VAS at 5hr	1.12 ± 0.33	1.56 ± 0.50	0.00	-0.44	-0.68 to -0.19
VAS at 6hr	1.20 ± 0.40	1.68 ± 0.55	0.00	-0.48	-0.75 to -0.20
VAS at 12hr	1.28 ± 0.45	1.68 ± 0.55	0.00	-0.40	-0.68 to -0.11
VAS at 24hr	1.28 ± 0.45	1.68 ± 0.55	0.00	-0.40	-0.68 to -0.11

Only 1(4%) case in the SC group required diclofenac while 4 (16%) cases in the IV group required this drug in the first 16 hr postoperatively (Table 2). It was not significant statistically ($p= 0.35$).

Nausea and vomiting occurred in 2% of cases in SC group and in 8% of cases in IV group. This was highly significant statically ($p= 0.008$) (Table 3).

Table 2: diclofenac requirement in both groups.

Route of giving tramadol	Time of given Diclofenac		Total
	1-7hr	8-16hr	
SC	1 4.0%	0 0.00%	1 4.00%
IV	1 4.0%	3 12.0%	4 16.00%

Table 3: shows the incidence of nausea & vomiting in both groups

Time	subcutaneous	intravenous	P value
at 0 time	0(0%)	1(4%)	0.31
30mint	0(0%)	1(4%)	0.31
1hr	0(0%)	4(16%)	0.03
2hr	0(0%)	1(4%)	0.31
3hr	0(4%)	1(4%)	0.31
4hr	1(4%)	1(4%)	1.0
5hr	0(0%)	1(4%)	0.31
6hr	1(4%)	0(0%)	0.31
12hr	0(0%)	0(0%)	
24hr	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Total	2(8%)	10(40%)	0.008

Discussion

Physicians, nurses, and patients alike fear opioids, even though they remain the mainstay of acute pain treatment [9]. However, the high rates of adverse effects provide an impetus to investigate alternatives. Recent studies have shown that localized use of these drugs can overcome the associated problems [10, 11]. Clinical studies have shown that tramadol has a local anesthetic effect [10] with minimal sedation and cardiovascular compromise [11-13].

In this study, we demonstrated that subcutaneous wound infiltration with tramadol following inguinal hernia operations is associated with decreased VAS scores, lower incidence of nausea and vomiting and reduced need for analgesia. Several studies have noted that use of analgesic agents such as tramadol during surgery lowers patient's postoperative need for analgesia. Unlugenc et al. [14] found a considerable decrease in morphine consumption following tramadol administration after major abdominal surgery. Altunkaya *et al* propose that tramadol can be used as an alternative drug to lidocaine for minor surgeries because of its ability to decrease the demand for postoperative analgesia [15]. khajavi *et al* found that following subcutaneous wound infiltration with tramadol, postoperative analgesia was prolonged and the need for more opioid was reduced considerably [16]. In this study regarding the demand for postoperative analgesia; there is no significant difference between the two groups statistically ($p=0.35$) in spite of an obvious difference between the percentage of the cases who required diclofenac (table 2). This can be explained that small number of cases has been taken.

Conclusion

Subcutaneous wound infiltration with tramadol after open inguinal hernia operations reduces postoperative analgesic consumption and produces less nausea and vomiting than does intravenous administration.

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The application of advanced trauma life support (ATLS) in casualty department in Al-Kindy Teaching Hospital, does it change rate of mortality?

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Abstract

Background: Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) was developed in the United States in the 1970s to provide a standardized method for the initial assessment and treatment of severely injured victims by physicians working in Emergency Departments (EDs). The concept, based on the principles "treat first what kills first" and "do no further harm," was initially meant for doctors who are not already experienced with care of major trauma victims.

Objectives: The aim of this study is to demonstrate any difference in mortality among trauma patients in Al-Kindy Teaching Hospital (KTH) before (pre-ATLS) & after (post-ATLS) application of ATLS principles.

Patients & Methods: This study involves (12997) trauma patients admitted to Casualty Department (CD) in KTH during the year 2008 (pre-ATLS period) & of (8298) trauma patients admitted to same CD during the year 2010 (post-ATLS period). The data was collected retrospectively and analyzed to see if the results are statistically significant by applying p-value (if P-value < 0.05 it is considered statistically significant).

Results: In year 2008 (pre-ATLS period), total number of patients was (12997). There were 6563 males (50.5%), 5251 females (40.4%) & 1183 children (9.1%) [Child is defined as less than 5 years of age]. Average age (excluding children) was (31 years) with range of (13-75 years). Total number of deaths was 198 (1.5%), number of male deaths was 100(50.5%), number of female deaths was 80 (40.4%) & number of child deaths was 18(9.1%). In year 2010 (post-ATLS period), total number of patients was (8298). There were 6299 males (75.9%), 1738 females (20.9%) & 261 children (3.15%). Average age (excluding children) was (28 years) with range of (11-70 years). Number of total deaths was 191 (2.3%), number of male deaths was 145(75.916%), number of female deaths was 40(20.942%) & number of child deaths was 6(3.141%).

Conclusion: Our study demonstrates that introduction of the ATLS program significantly improved the outcome and decrease mortality in trauma patient admitted to CDs in Iraqi hospitals. It also improves the performance of doctors working in CDs who provide care and primary resuscitation.

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Keywords: Advanced Trauma Life Support, Trauma, Casualty, Trauma Mortality.

Introduction

Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) was developed in the United States in the 1970s to provide a standardized method for the initial assessment and treatment of severely injured victims by physicians working in Emergency

Departments (EDs). The concept, based on the principles "treat first what kills first" and "do no further harm," was initially meant for doctors who are not already experienced with care of major trauma victims [1,2].

ATLS courses sponsored by the American College of Surgeons Committee on Trauma (ACSCOT) were held in Al-Kindy Teaching Hospital, a big general hospital in Baghdad, Iraq. These courses were presented (both lectures & skill stations) by well trained doctors (trainers of trainee, TOT). Each

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course was attended (for a period of 2 weeks) by specialist and junior doctors of different specialties. The medical and paramedical staff of Al-Kindy Teaching Hospital (KTH) also attended the courses. After finishing the course, each attendant was given a certificate of attendance. The aim of the courses is to increase the competence & the ability of the attendant doctor to deal with emergency cases & to decrease morbidity & mortality by applying principles of ATLS, i.e. primary survey, secondary survey & definitive management.

Patients & Methods

This is a retrospective study of (12997) trauma patients admitted to CD in KTH during the year 2008 (pre-ATLS period) & of (8298) trauma patients admitted to same CD during the year 2010 (post-ATLS period). The patients were distributed over 4 seasons of the year as shown in table 1 & table 2.

Table 1: Trauma patients admitted to CD in KTH in the year 2008 (pre-ATLS) distributed over seasons of the year (n= 12997).

Season	No. of patients	No. of deaths	% of deaths
First season	4426	53	1.197
Second season	2632	46	1.748
Third season	3257	54	1.658
Fourth season	2682	45	1.523
Total	12997	198	1.523

Table 2: Trauma patients admitted to CD in KTH in the year 2010 (post-ATLS) distributed over seasons of the year (n= 8298).

Season	No. of patients	No. of deaths	% of deaths
First season	1630	42	2.577
Second season	2276	56	2.460
Third season	2438	48	1.969
Fourth season	1954	45	2.303
Total	8298	191	2.302

In year 2008 (pre-ATLS period), total number of patients was (12997). There were 6563 males (50.5%), 5251 females (40.4%) & 1183 children (9.1%) [Child is defined as less than 5 years of age]. Average age (excluding children) was (31 years) with range of (13-75 years). Total number of deaths was 198 (1.5%), number of male deaths was

100 (50.5%), number of female deaths was 80 (40.4%) & number of child deaths was 18 (9.1%). See table-3.

Table 3: summary of the statistical values according to age & sex in year 2008 (pre-ATLS) in KTH. (No. of patients=12997).

Total no. of Patients	12997
No. of males (%)	6563 (52.5%)
No. of females (%)	5251 (40.4%)
No. of children (%)	1183 (9.1%)
Total no. of deaths (%)	198 (1.523%)
No. of male deaths (%)	100 (50.5%)
of female deaths (%)	80 (40.4%)
No. of child deaths (%)	18 (9.1%)

In year 2010 (post-ATLS period), total number of patients was (8298). There were 6299 males (75.9%), 1738 females (20.9%) & 261 children (3.15%). Average age (excluding children) was (28 years) with range of (11-70 years). Number of total deaths was 191 (2.3%), number of male deaths was 145 (75.916%), number of female deaths was 40 (20.942%) & number of child deaths was 6 (3.141%). See table-4.

Table-4 summary of the statistical values according to age & sex in year 2010 (post-ATLS) in KTH. (No. of patients=8298).

Total no. of Patients	8298
No. of males (%)	6299 (75.9%)
No. of females (%)	1738 (20.9%)
No. of children (%)	261 (3.15%)
Total no. of deaths (%)	191 (2.30%)
No. of male deaths (%)	145 (75.92%)
of female deaths (%)	40 (20.94%)
No. of child deaths (%)	6 (3.14%)

Table 5 summarizes & compares mortality in KTH in year 2008 (pre-ATLS) & year 2010 (post-ATLS) according to age & sex, and shows p-value (p-value is significant if <0.05).

Table-5: Mortality & p-value in KTH in year 2008 (pre-ATLS) & year 2010 (post-ATLS) according to age & sex.

	Year 2008	Year 2010	P-Value
Total no. of Patients	12997	8298	
Total no. of deaths (%)	198 (1.523%)	191 (2.30%)	0.722
No. of male deaths (%)	100 (50.5%)	145 (75.92%)	0.004
No. of female deaths (%)	80 (40.4%)	40 (20.94%)	0.0002
No. of child deaths (%)	18 (9.1%)	6 (3.14%)	0.014

RESULTS

There were no statistically significant differences in total death rate between pre-ATLS period (year 2008) and post-ATLS period (year 2010) [total death no. in year 2008 was 198 (1.52% from total no. of patients), while total death no. in year 2010 was 191 (2.3% from total no. of patients), p-value=0.722]. But we found statistically significant differences in death rates between the two years in regard to age & sex. No. of male deaths was 100 (50.5% from total death no.) in year 2008 and 145 (75.9% from total death no.) in year 2010; p-value=0.004. No. of female deaths was 80 (40.4% from total no. of deaths) in year 2008 and 40 (20.94% from total no. of deaths) in year 2010; p-value= 0.0002. No. of child death was 18 (9.1% from total no. of deaths) in year 2008 and 6 (3.14% from total no. of deaths) in year 2010; p-value=0.014. (P-value is considered significant if < 0.05). See table-5.

DISCUSSION

The ATLS course emphasizes the primary management of the injured patient, starting at the time of injury and continuing through the initial assessment, life-saving interventions, reevaluation and stabilization and, when needed, transfer to a trauma center¹. Courses were held in KTH & intended to help all doctors who will be involved in acute trauma care. This study is trying to answer the question "whether ATLS training affects the fate of the trauma patient, decrease mortality and can help doctors performing their primary care in CDs effectively". The data were collected retrospectively from a big general hospital in Iraq, KTH (where data were collected in pre- and post-ATLS periods). Comparison between pre- and post-ATLS periods in KTH was performed, using p-value to predict the statistical significance of applying ATLS principles for primary care in CDs (when p-value is less than 0.05 it is considered significant), and the impact on mortality rate of trauma patients. There are few studies in world literature to evaluate the impact of ATLS in management of trauma patient in CDs. Most of these studies involve small no. of patient [1, 3-5]. In Iraqi literature no studies were

done for such evaluation, at time of preparing this study and we can claim that this is the 1st study in Iraq evaluating the impact of ATLS application. In KTH when we compare total no. of deaths in pre-ATLS period and post-ATLS period we didn't find a statistically significant difference (p-value=0.722). This may be due to larger no. of trauma patients seen in CD in year 2008 (n=12997) compared to no. of patients seen in year 2010 (n=8298). But when we compare death rates according to age & sex there is a statistically significant difference (if p-value< 0.05). Male deaths in pre-ATLS period was 100 (50.5%), while it was 145 (75.9%) in post-ATLS period (p-value=0.004). The larger no. of male deaths in year 2010 may be due to more males seen in this year (n=6299=75.9% of total number). No. of female death in pre-ATLS period was 80 (40.4%) while it was 40 (20.94%) in post-ATLS period (p-value=0.0002). Child death in pre-ATLS period was 18 (9.1%) and 6 (3.14%) in post-ATLS period (p-value=0.014). So total death in pre-ATLS period (year 2008) was 198 (1.52% from total no. 12997), compared to total death of 191 (2.3% from total no. 8298) in post-ATLS period (year 2010).

These results are not similar to the results in some other studies [1, 3, 4, 5]. Ger D.J. Van Olden et al in 2003 found no statistical significance in his study between pre- and post-ATLS periods, and this may be due to small no. of patients studied (63 patients were studied) [1]. Vestrup et al in 1987 studied 50 patients in pre-ATLS & 71 patients in post-ATLS periods and they found no difference in mortality after ATLS training [3]. Similar to our study results were found by Ali et al (1993) in a retrospective study over a 9-year period. Ali et al. demonstrated that the ATLS program significantly improved trauma outcome in a developing country. Post-ATLS, trauma mortality decreased from 68% to 34% [5]. More studies are needed to evaluate the impact of applying ATLS principles. These studies should consider other parameters, such as causes of trauma, causes and time of mortality, mortality in 1st hour after trauma (the golden hour) and the people who provide the immediate care and resuscitation in CDs.

CONCLUSION

Our study demonstrates that introduction of the ATLS program significantly improved the outcome and decrease mortality in trauma patient admitted to CDs in Iraqi hospitals. It also improves the performance of doctors working in CDs who provide care and primary resuscitation. But our study didn't consider all parameters affecting patient's outcome. Although further studies on larger no. of patients & multicentre studies are needed to evaluate the benefits of ATLS program application, we recommend that ATLS programs should be applied as part of casualty training for doctors who care for trauma patients.

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Comparative study of surgical wound cultures and drug resistance in Duhok city, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: Data from the several years showed that the wound infections have been found to pose a major problem in the field of surgery for a long time along with an increasing bacterial resistance for drugs that were considered as the first line of treatment for post-operative wound infections.

Objectives: The objective of this study was undertaken to determine the frequency of bacteriological profile causing surgical wound infections and to evaluate their antimicrobial susceptibility patterns among outpatients visiting out-clinic at Azadi teaching hospital in Duhok city, Iraq.

Methods: A total of 263 wound swabs collected from surgical wound infections were analysed by screened on Blood agar, MacConkey agar and Nutrient agar, followed by the identification of the isolates based on their cultural characteristics and their reactions in standard biochemical tests. All the isolates were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility by the disk diffusion technique according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines on Muller Hinton Agar.

Results: Of the 263 surgical wound swabs cultured, 180 (69.6%) had a positive bacterial culture, of them *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (27.8%) was the most frequent pathogen followed sequentially by *Staphylococcus aureus* (22.2%). Other gram-negative bacteria also have been isolated such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (16.2%), *Escherichia coli* (14.4%), *Proteus mirabilis* (7.2%) and *Enterobacter cloacae* (2.8%). with exception to amikacin, imipenem and ciprofloxacin, a majority of isolated pathogens exhibited high resistance rates to most other used antibiotics. A total of 4 distinct antibiotype patterns were obtained with multi-drug resistant isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; predominant antibiotypes were 2 and 3.

Conclusion: This study shows increased rate of surgical wound infection in study area. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were found to be the most frequent causative agent and showed multi-drug resistance with different antibiotype patterns.

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Key words: Bacteriological profile, Wound infections, Antibiotics, Antibiotype.

Introduction

Wound infection is regarded as the most common nosocomial infection in surgical patients. It has been associated with increased trauma care, prolonged hospitals stay and treatment. However, despite an improved understanding of the pathophysiology and improved methods of prevention and prophylaxis, surgical wound

Infections remain the most common cause of post operative morbidity and mortality [1]. The probability of wound infections largely depends on the patients' systemic host defenses, local wound conditions and microbial burden. A surgical wound may get infected by the exogenous bacterial flora which may be present in the environmental air of the operation theatre or by the endogenous flora. Micro-organisms which are responsible for wound infections depend on the surgical site, the study population and antimicrobial use within the hospital [2]. There is a need to reduce the cost which is potentially associated with antibiotic misuse versus use of high-end antibiotics, multiple antibiotics and the prolonged duration of

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treatment. Updating the antibiogram periodically will further reduce the rate of postoperative wound infections to a considerable extent [3, 4]. Therefore; the present study was aimed to find out the frequency of bacteriological profile responsible for surgical wound infections and determining the antibiotic susceptibility pattern of the micro-organisms as well as set up the antibiotyping patterns for the most common bacterial isolates.

Material and Methods

Study Population: A total of 263 samples were obtained from those outpatients who showed an evidence of surgical wound infections in Azadi teaching hospital in Duhok city; Iraq, between March 2008 to November 2010.

Sample Collection: pus samples / wound swabs were collected with aseptic precautions from clinically suspected postoperative wound infections and were transported to the laboratory without delay. The specimens have been routinely processed by the public health central laboratory in Duhok city.

Bacterial Identification: Several media and tests were used for the isolation, identification and testing the susceptibility of the isolates for common used antibiotics. The media used are: Blood agar (with 5-7% defibrinated blood), MacConkey agar, Nutrient agar, Mannitol salt agar, Simmons citrate agar, kligler Iron Agar (KIA), Mueller-Hinton agar, Sulfide formation indole production, Motility Test (SIM), Nutrient agar, Methyl Red-Voges-Proskauer broth, Coagulase, Catalase, Urease, Oxidase tests were used for the identification. All of the above media and reagents were obtained from (Difco, USA). The media were prepared according to manufacturer's instructions in 500 mL bottle and sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 20 min. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hrs in an incubator. The plates were read the following day but extended to 48 hrs if there was no bacterial growth within 24 hrs. Isolated colonies were subjected to Gram staining technique and biochemical tests for identification [5].

Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing: Antibiotic susceptibility tests were carried out on isolated and identified colonies of bacterial isolates using commercially prepared antibiotic sensitivity disc (Oxoid, England) using modified Kirby-Bauer method according to CLSI guidelines, using Mueller-Hinton agar standard media. The

inhibition zone standards for antimicrobial susceptibility were considered from tables for interpretative zone diameters of Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) [6]. In this study resist typing patterns were done just for *Escherichia coli* isolates since was commonest bacterial recovered.

Results

Of the 263 surgical wound swabs cultured, 180 (69.6%) had a positive bacterial culture. all specimens were directly transferred to the microbiology laboratory and cultured to the appropriate media (as described in methods).

Table 1 shows the most bacterial etiology causing wound infections were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 50 isolates (27.8 %), followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* 40 isolates (22.2 %). The lowest causative agents were *Streptococcus pyogenes* 6 isolates (3.3%), and *Enterobacter cloacae* 5 isolates (2.8%).

Table 1: Frequency of various pathogens causing wound infections.

Bacteriological profile	No. of Organisms (%)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	50 (27.8)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	40 (22.2)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	29 (16.2)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	26 (14.4)
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	13 (7.2)
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	11 (6.1)
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	6 (3.3)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	5 (2.8)
Total	180 (100%)

Table 2 shows the susceptibility rates of various bacterial isolates responsible to wound infections. A majority of the isolates showed high susceptibility rate to amikacin, imipenem and ciprofloxacin sequentially. On other hand, most other used antibiotics were ineffective.

Table 3 shows the antibiotyping patterns of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates to commonly used antibiotics. It was found that all of the isolates were multiple resistant, i.e. resistant to more than one antibiotic. The obtained results of antibiotyping patterns revealed out of 50 isolates, 10 isolates with multiple-drug resistant were belonged to 4 distinct antibiotyping patterns; common antibiotypes were 2 and 3.

Table 2: Antimicrobial susceptibility test of various pathogens causing wound infections.

Bacteriological profile	Antibiotics										
	AMC * %	CL %	CN %	CIP %	CRO %	IPM %	DO %	F %	E %	AK %	** %
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	16	6	14	50	4	36	22	6	2	54	80
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	28	48	25	55	8	45	30	13	35	68	90
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	7	7	41	45	3	27	10	0	10	55	90
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	19	4	42	62	0	62	23	27	0	77	70
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	0	7	23	46	23	38	0	23	0	84	90
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	64	18	18	64	0	64	36	27	0	27	70
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	50	83	50	83	50	83	67	0	67	50	10
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	0	0	40	40	0	83	0	20	0	100	80

* %: Susceptibility rate

** : percentage of resistance collectively to all antibiotics used.

AMC: amoxiclav (10µg), CL: cephalexin (30µg), CN: gentamicin (10µg), CIP: ciprofloxacin (100µg), CRO: Cefuroxime (30µg), IPM: imepenum (30µg), DO: doxycyclin (10µg), F: nitrofurantoin (10µg), E: erythromycin (5µg), AK: amikacin (10).

Table 3: Antibiotyping patterns of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates.

Antibiotyping patterns	Resistance spectrum phenotypic	No. of isolates (%)
Antibiotype 1	E, CRO, AK, DO, CL, CN, AMC, F, CIP	2 (20)
Antibiotype 2	E, CRO, AK, CL, CN, AMC, F, CIP	3 (30)
Antibiotype 3	E, CRO, CL, CN, AMC, F	3 (30)
Antibiotype 4	E, CRO, AK, DO, CL, CN, AMC, F	2 (20)
Total		10 (100)

Discussion

The knowledge of the bacteriology of an infection and the laboratory susceptibility testing of micro-organism implicated could make drug selection in antimicrobial chemotherapy more rational. Furthermore, this would reduce or eliminate errors in empirical selection of both ineffective and expensive drugs, and higher mortality. The result of present study showed that the overall infection rate of surgical wound infections was (69.6%). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* which accounted for 27.8% prevalence was the predominant isolates followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* (22.2%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (16.2%), *Escherichia coli* (14.4%), *Proteus mirabilis* (7.2%), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (6.1%), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (3.3%) and *Enterobacter cloacae* (2.8%). Other study clarified that infection rate of surgical wound infections was 7.5%. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the commonest in (44%), *Bacteroides fragilis* (11%), *Escherichia coli* (11%), *Proteus spp.* (11%), *Pseudomonas spp* and *Klebsiella spp* (8.3 % of each) [7]. other work found *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates was the highest (51.6%) followed by *Klebsiella spp.* (22.6%),

Pseudomonas aeruginosa and *Proteus spp.* (9.7% each) and *E. coli* (6.45%) [8]. the similar finding was reported in Bosnia [9]. The picture was however different at Jos where Oguachuba found *Proteus spp* to be the most common surgical wound infections isolate with a rate of 41.9% followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* with 25.6% [10]. Also, other study conducted in Ghana reported that the *Proteus spp* represented highest wound isolates [11]. The overall infection rate of surgical wounds was 8.29% in study in Iran. The commonest isolates were *Staphylococcus aureus* (21%) and *E.coli* (21%), followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (17%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (15%) [12]. It must be noted that anaerobic organisms require very stringent conditions for isolation, therefore, there are difficulties associated with anaerobic cultures in this country; this may have been responsible for the non-mention of anaerobes in our study.

The result of the antibiogram of the pathogenic isolates shows that the amikacin exhibited considerable activity against most leading organisms, except with *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, as follows:

Klebsiella pneumoniae (54%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (68%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (56%), *Escherichia coli* (77%), *Proteus mirabilis* (84%), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (27%), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (50%) and *Enterobacter cloacae* (100%). This is already reported in other studies [13, 14, 15]. Thus; this drug is still effective and could be considered as alternative options in the empirical treatment of surgical wound infections in our area. In contrast, other study conducted in Pakistan, found that the amoxiclav and imipenem were the most effective drugs against wound isolates [16]. Among overall recovered pathogens in our study, only three of the organisms: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (45%) *Proteus mirabilis* (46%) and *Enterobacter cloacae* (40%) were less or moderate susceptible to ciprofloxacin. Similar data was noted by [17]. Based on obtained results, a majority of the isolated organisms exhibited high resistance rates to antibiotics tested namely: erythromycin, amoxiclav, cephalixin and cefuroxime. However, this showed that these categories of the isolates were collectively multi-resistant strains. Similar data were reported by [7, 8, 14].

The later observation evolves great importance and implies that these antibiotics are no longer be effectively used as empirical therapy for surgical wound infections particularly in the study area. Thus updating the antibiogram periodically will further reduce the rate of postoperative wound infections to a considerable extent.

Antibiotyping is a phenotypic method that consists of testing bacterial strains against a set of arbitrarily chosen antibiotics, whereby, a resistance pattern that is characteristic of a strain is generated and, is believed to describe the isolates for epidemiological purposes. In the present study we investigated the possible value of antibiotyping patterns of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates.

As previously mentioned, we have determined the susceptibility test of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* to selected antibiotics and collectively, most of the isolates were multiple resistant. Obtained results of this study revealed that the out of 50 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, 10 isolates of multi-drug resistant (with the same antibiotic sensitivity pattern) occurred twice or more were belonged to 4 distinct antibiotype patterns. Antibiotype 2 and 3 were predominant has much higher frequency rate comprising (30% of each) of the isolates. Moreover, those isolates, from various outpatients, were

identical on the basis of disk susceptibility patterns, indicating relatedness among them. In general, this simple typing system provide discriminatory between strains and able to determine relatedness among isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in order to tracing the source of infections in our environment.

The overall result of this study clearly emphasizes that the magnitude of surgical wound infection problem may be increasing because many of the causative organisms have probably started to develop some form of drug resistance to the currently used antibiotics. The overall infection rate of surgical wound was 69.6%; this is relatively high based on the generally acceptable surgical wound infection. Therefore, undoubtedly, efforts on continual monitoring in the form of wound surveillance can then allow each institute in our setting to identify and immediately correct specific problem areas. In addition, this study is therefore a step towards the generation of national data on the prevalence of antimicrobial resistant pathogens responsible for surgical wound infections in Duhok city.

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Detection of hepatitis B viral markers and DNA in sera of chronic carriers in Duhok

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Abstract

Background: Hepatitis B virus infection is among the most devastating health problems in the world, including Iraq. The aim of this study was to evaluate the relationship of the serological, biochemical markers with molecular markers in order to assess the infectivity of virus in chronic hepatitis B virus carriers.

Patients & Methods: A total of 55 chronic hepatitis B virus carriers (51 were males and 4 females, their ages were between (19-62 years mean 40.5 $\pm$ SD =9.89) were analyzed by serological, biochemical and molecular assays.

Results: Out of 55 chronic HBsAg positive carriers, 10 (18.18%) carriers were HBeAg positive, 45 (81.82%) were HBeAg negative, HBV DNA was detected by polymerase chain reaction assay (PCR) in 31 (56.36%) of carrier cases, among them 10 (32.26%) were HBeAg positive, and 21 (67.74%) were HBeAg negative. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) was above 2 $\times$ ULN (upper limit of normal) in (60%) of HBsAg carrier cases with detectable HBV DNA and positive HBeAg, and in (14.3%) of carriers with detectable HBV DNA, negative HBeAg, while in (25%) of carriers had non-detectable HBV DNA and negative HBeAg.

Conclusions: the detection of HBV DNA by PCR is the best predictor of the course of infection and is more reliable than the other markers.

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Keywords: PCR, HBsAg, HBeAg, Chronic carrier.

Introduction

Hepatitis B viruses (HBV) continue to cause viral hepatitis in developing and under developing countries, currently over two billion people have evidence of previous HBV infection and 350 million become chronic carriers of the virus [1]. The spectrum of clinical manifestations of HBV infection varies in both acute and chronic disease. During the acute phase, manifestations range from subclinical hepatitis to anicteric hepatitis, icteric hepatitis, and fulminant hepatitis. During the

chronic phase, manifestations range from an asymptomatic carrier state to chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma. The clinical outcome of HBV infection depends upon the age at infection, the level of HBV replication, the genotype of the virus, and the immune status of the host [2].

Nearly all infants and most adults who progress to chronic infection have no symptoms during the acute phase. So, diagnosis largely depends on laboratory investigations. Routine hepatitis B serology includes tests for the detection of HBsAg, HBeAg, their corresponding antibodies anti-HBs, anti-HBe and anti-HBc (total) and anti-HBc IgM. Following infection with HBV, classically HBsAg becomes detectable in serum during the

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incubation period of 3-5 weeks before appearance of clinical symptoms and persists for 2-4 weeks after elevation of transaminase level. It disappears in 2-6 months as the patient recovers and protective anti-HBs antibody appears, persistence of HBsAg beyond six months after acute infection is accepted as evidence of chronic infection [3].

In chronic hepatitis B virus infection, HBeAg may remain detectable for many months and usually for years. In typical cases of acute hepatitis, detection of HBeAg has little value. HBeAg usually becomes detectable in the serum when HBsAg first appears but disappears within several weeks as acute hepatitis resolves. However in chronic infection, HBeAg is an important marker of viral replication, infectivity and ongoing liver injury. Antibody to HBeAg is detectable as HBeAg disappears from the serum and the presence of anti-HBe is associated with likelihood of spontaneous resolution of acute infection. In chronic hepatitis B virus infection the loss of HBeAg and acquisition of anti-HBe tends to be associated with biochemical and histological improvement [4].

During acute phase of infection, anti-HBc of IgM class predominates. As the infection evolves, anti-HBc IgM levels gradually decline and often become undetectable within six months. If anti-HBc IgM is negative, the probability of acute infection in HBsAg-positive cases is nil [5].

The diagnosis of HBV is not only imperative but also complex because of different viral antigen which bring about varying serological profiles in different stages of the disease, Patients positive for HBeAg or having replicative HBV disease tend to have more severe liver disease and are more infectious than these with antiHBe antibodies [6]. In HBeAg negative samples the incidence of HBV-DNA positively determined by PCR has been reported by several groups to be range from (64-100%) [7]. So the presence of HBV-DNA in serum is a reliable marker of viral replication and infectivity, PCR becoming the preferred method for its detection, PCR is an extremely sensitive technique which can detect as few as 10 HBV genomes per milliliter. The presence of serum HBV-DNA in chronic hepatitis patients is indicative of active viral replication, the molecular technique like PCR assay is a very sensitive marker for detection of HBV-DNA in certain sera which are HBsAg positive even in the absence of HBeAg, comparison of different serological markers with molecular diagnostic test is

necessary for predicting the course of chronic liver disease [8].

Patients and Methods

Blood samples from 55 known chronic HBsAg carriers were collected, 51 of them males and 4 females, their age ranges between 19 to 62 years (mean 40.5 year $\pm$ SD =9.89). Tests were carried out at Central Laboratory in Duhok City, Kurdistan Region, Iraq from October 2009 to March 2010, the study conform to the ethical requirements of the health authority in Duhok. In this study, HBsAg-positive, anti-HBc IgM negative and anti-HBc (total) positive cases were considered as chronic HBsAg carriers. All the patients were tested for serological markers, biochemical parameter (ALT level) and molecular marker (HBV DNA). HBeAg, HBV DNA and ALT level were detected to assess the infectivity of HBV. Initially, a sample of blood consisting of (5) milliliters was obtained from antecubital vein by a sterile disposable syringe from each case. About 3ml blood sample was poured into a clean plane tube without anticoagulant and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 – 10 minutes. The serum was separated and stored in multiple marked clean tubes at (2-8 °C) for both ELISA and biochemical test, and remaining 2ml of whole blood was poured into EDTA tubes and stored at (- 20 °C) for longer storage for PCR assay.

All the serological tests were done by APSON LX automated immunoassay analyzer using ELISA test kits from MTPC company (Germany) which include (HBsAg, anti-HBc (total), anti-HBc IgM and HBeAg) ELISA kits. Biochemical tests from Biomerieux company (France). HBV DNA tests were carried out using HBV-DNA detection kit from Cinnagen Company (Iran) to detect HBV DNA level in blood samples of all HBsAg-positive patients. The HBV DNA was compared with HBeAg status and the level of liver enzyme ALT.

All the selected HBsAg positive serum samples that are anti-HBc (total) positive were retested for anti-HBc IgM marker, then all anti-HBc (total) positive and anti-HBc(IgM) negative serum samples were retested for both HBeAg and ALT levels. Thereafter, the whole blood samples for all HBeAg negative and positive cases were tested for PCR assay.

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) and Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) co infections were excluded through appropriate serological tests (ELISA).

Results

Out of 55 chronic HBsAg carriers, 10 were HBeAg-positive, remaining 45 were HBeAg-negative (Table 1). Out of 55 HBsAg chronic carriers, 31(56.36%) had detectable HBV DNA by polymerase chain reaction assay, the remaining 24 (43.64%) HBsAg chronic cases did not have detectable HBV DNA (Figure 1). Out of 31 patients who had detectable HBV DNA, 10 cases of them were HBeAg positive (32.26%), The remaining 21 (67.74%) cases were HBeAg negative (Table 2). The carrier cases involved in the study (55 cases) were categorized according to the detected immunological/molecular markers of HBV infection and according to ALT levels, as a marker of liver damage (Table 3).

The first category consisted of 6 out of 10 (60%) of carriers had detectable HBV DNA with positive HBeAg and raised ALT levels, furthermore, in this group 4 out of 10 (40%) of carriers had detectable HBV DNA with positive HBeAg and normal ALT levels. The second category consisted of 3 out of 21 (14.3%) of carriers had detectable HBV DNA, negative HBeAg and raised ALT levels, while 18 out of 21 (85.7%) of carriers had detectable HBV DNA, negative HBeAg and normal ALT levels. The third category consisted of 6 out of 24 (25%) of carriers had non-detectable HBV DNA, negative HBeAg and raised ALT levels, while 18 out of 24 (75%) of carriers had non-detectable HBV DNA, negative HBeAg and normal ALT levels.

Table 1: Immunological markers of HBV detected among HBsAg positive studied individuals

Studied HBsAg positive cases No. (55)	Anti-HBc (total) No. (%)	Anti-HBc IgM No. (%)	HBeAg No. (%)
HBsAg positive	55 (100)	0 (0)	10 (18.18)

Table 2: molecular/Immunological markers of HBV detected among HBsAg positive studied individuals.

Studied HBsAg positive cases No. (55)	HBeAg positive No (%)	HBeAg negative No (%)	Total
Detectable HBV DNA	10(32.26)	21 (67.74)	31(56.36%)
Non-detectable HBV DNA	0(0)	24 (100)	24 (43.63%)

Figure 1: 2% Agarose gel electrophoresis of HBV-DNA PCR amplification; Lane L: represent ladder marker with known molecular weight. Lane 1, 2, 3 represents positive samples. Lane 4, 5, 6 represents Negative samples (No Bands appear). Lane 7 represents negative Control (No bands appear). Lane 8 represents positive control with DNA Band of 353 bp.

Table3: Diagnostic categorization of studied HBsAg carrier cases.

Categorization of the studied 55 Cases (No.)	Immunological/molecular Marker (S)	Biochemical marker † (No. %)
Active Chronic hepatitis -B (10)	Detectable HBV DNA HBeAg positive	Raised ALT levels 6 (60)
		Normal ALT levels 4 (40)
Active Chronic hepatitis -B (21)	Detectable HBV DNA HBeAg negative	Raised ALT levels 3 (14.3)
		Normal ALT levels 18 (85.7)
Inactive HBsAg carriers (24)	Non-detectable HBVDNA HBeAg negative	Raised ALT levels 6 (25)
		Normal ALT levels 18 (75)

† > 2 ULN (Upper limit of normal), normal range is 0-40 IU/L in male, 0-30 IU/L in female

Discussion

The presence of HBeAg is regarded as a marker of active viral replication. This study revealed that HBeAg positive cases were 10 (18.18%) among the (55) chronic HBsAg positive carriers. The measurement of HBeAg by different methods like those detected by rapid methods or by using ELISA technique with different sensitivity may play role in giving various results among different studies. The low rate of this marker in this study could be attributed to the rate of mutation in HBV-precore/core region which yield (HBeAg negative mutant) associated with CHB [9].

Measurement or detection of serum HBV-DNA in Hepatitis B patients facilitates prediction of active viral replication and hepatic inflammatory activity, especially with HBeAg negative patients. In the present study, HBV DNA was detected in 31 (56.36%) of 55 HBsAg positive patients, 10 (32.26%) were HBeAg positive while 21 (67.74%) cases were HBeAg negative.

Data from this study detected the presence of HBV DNA in 100% of HBeAg-positive carriers and in 46.7% of HBeAg negative cases, this is very close to the results obtained by (Loriot et al., 1992; Ljunggren et al., 1993) [10, 11], who reported a percentage of 80-100% and 26-64% respectively and this later group (HBV DNA detectable, HBeAg negative) is usually infected with precore mutant strain which is common in Asia and Mediterranean area [12, 13]. Thus, our present data indicate that the HBeAg status does not necessarily reflect the HBV-DNA level in the serum and cannot be a reliable marker to predict the clinical outcome of CHB carriers, which is in agreement with other studies [14, 15].

The results of the first category (Table 3) revealed that 6 out of 10 (60%) of carriers had HBV DNA by PCR with positive HBeAg and raised ALT level, which indicates active chronic hepatitis [16]. The results of the other group (Table III) included in this study was 4 out of 10 (40%) of carriers with HBV DNA, positive HBeAg and normal ALT. We considered that this group included active chronic carriers in spite of normal ALT [9, 17]. This group of people are in the "immune tolerant" stage of hepatitis B, their HBV DNA levels can reach billions of copies because their immune systems have not recognized or begun to fight the infection [18]. The mechanisms of tolerance may be due to ineffective Ag processing and presentation on MHC class I molecules [19], anergy of T cell response [20] and distribution of NK cells, CD4+

cells and CD8+ cells resembles that seen in normal liver [21]. HBeAg-positive patients with or without raised ALT level (64%, 36%) respectively were found with active HBV virus replication (detectable HBV DNA) [9]. In HBeAg negative chronic hepatitis B, ALT levels can flare with an intervening period of normal

Values can continue to increase without flare, or demonstrate intermittent flares superimposed on a continuous elevation [18].

This study showed that 3 out of 21 (14.3%) of carriers in second category (Table III) had positive HBV DNA, negative HBeAg and raised ALT level, while 18 out of 21 (85.7%) of carriers had HBV DNA positive, negative HBeAg and normal ALT. Chen et al 2011 found that regular monitoring of levels of HBV DNA and ALT is important in clinical management of chronic carriers of HBV and considered as independent predictors for hepatocellular carcinoma. Thus our results revealed that 21 out of 31 HBV DNA positive carriers had no HBeAg, HBeAg negative CHB was not an uncommon or benign entity and chronic liver disease develops in a significant proportion of such patients [19]. The presence or absence of HBeAg may not necessarily reflect the serum HBV-DNA concentration, particularly in persistent infection and thus absence of HBeAg and presence of anti-HBe poorly correlated with complete loss of HBV DNA from the serum [20].

The results of the third category (Table III) revealed that 6 out of 24 (25%) of carriers with non-detectable HBV DNA and negative HBeAg had raised ALT level. While 18 out of 24 (75%) of carriers also with non-detectable HBV DNA and negative HBeAg had normal ALT level. In a study found that in patients with non-replicative HBV infection and normal ALT level, HBV DNA was not detected. Normal ALT level, absence of HBeAg and absence of HBV DNA were suggestive of the non-replicative state in those patients [6].

Conclusion

This study indicates that detection of HBV DNA by PCR is the best predictor of the course of infection and is more reliable than the other markers, mainly in CHB patients with negative HBeAg. Normal ALT level should not indicate that further

investigations is unnecessary and should not be considered as a reliable predictor of the course of infection.

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Tooth discoloration in patients seen at university teaching hospital

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Abstract

Background: Discolouration of teeth is common and can affect the aesthetic sensibilities of a person. It can be extrinsic or intrinsic in nature. This study evaluates the distribution and causes of tooth discolouration by age, gender and ethnicity.

Patients and Methods: Collection of data was performed by using questionnaires and clinical examinations to determine the cause and type of tooth discolouration. Standardized clinical pictures of tooth discolouration were used as a guide in the selection and classification. Independent sample t-test and analysis of variance were used for comparison of age between genders and ethnic groups.

Results: The prevalence of extrinsic tooth discolouration (52.9%) was slightly higher than intrinsic tooth discolouration. The causes of extrinsic tooth discolouration were mostly contributed by staining due to tobacco, coffee and tea consumption. Fluorosis was the most common type of intrinsic tooth discolouration observed. Generally there was no significant difference in age and types of tooth discoloration between males and females and among ethnic groups.

Conclusion: Tooth discolouration occurs in all age, gender and ethnic groups. Awareness of the causes of tooth discolouration may help to minimize its occurrence.

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Key words: Tooth discoloration, aesthetic, causes, awareness.

Introduction

Cosmetic dentistry is usually most popular especially among female patients who wish to improve their appearance of discoloured teeth [1]. More patients nowadays are willing to spend money and time to have whiter teeth [2]. Dentists have been preoccupied with aesthetic procedures since the late 1800s [3]. The science of colour is important in dentistry with regard to color perception and description, and can be improved with training [4]. The thickness or morphology of

enamel, translucency, external or internal stains; recession and dentine exposure are usually the factors that affect tooth colour. Tooth discoloration may be caused by natural (acquired) or iatrogenic (inflicted) factors [5]. The aetiology of tooth discoloration is complex but can be broadly classified into two groups which are extrinsic and intrinsic tooth discoloration [6, 7] as shown in figure 1. External or extrinsic staining can be divided into two main categories; direct and indirect extrinsic discoloration. Direct extrinsic staining occurs when compounds such as coffee and tea are incorporated into the pellicle layer producing chromogens. Deposition of tannin found in coffee and tea contributes to brown stains on the outer (buccal, labial) and inner (lingual, palatal) surfaces of the teeth. Enamel defects, salivary dysfunction, and poor oral hygiene may also contribute to extrinsic stains [8].

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Figure 1: Intrinsic discoloration of tooth No.11 due to caries and extrinsic discoloration of lower anterior teeth due to tobacco staining.

Indirect staining occurs when there is chemical interaction with another compound which produces cationic antiseptics and metal salts [2]. The inability to remove stain-producing materials, the use of dentifrices with inadequate cleaning and accumulation of dental plaque, calculus and food particles will cause brown or black staining over time. Intrinsic discoloration occurs following a change to the structural composition and thickness of dentinal tissue during tooth development [2]. It is caused by incorporation of chromatogenic material into dentine and enamel during tooth development or after tooth eruption [9] as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Intrinsic discoloration due to dental fluorosis.

Several methods can be used to manage tooth discoloration. These include the removal of surface stain by bleaching or tooth whitening, and application of operative techniques such as veneers and crowns [10]. Tooth whitening changes the shade and appearance of teeth without using restorative materials [11]. Bleaching is considered a conservative technique. The materials available for dental bleaching include carbamide peroxide, hydrogen peroxide gels and solutions, sodium perborate or a combination of these materials [12]. The bleaching technique is divided into two groups: vital bleaching and non-vital bleaching [13].

Although bleaching has its advantages in the treatment of discoloured teeth, several side effects may occur post-treatment. These include hypersensitivity, reversible gingival irritation, cervical resorption and risk of developing cancer [14]. Thus, the correct diagnosis of aetiology of tooth discoloration based on a complete assessment of the individual patient may allow the dental practitioner to manage the condition accordingly [15].

The present study aimed to assess distribution of patients with tooth discoloration in relation to age, gender and ethnicity in Faculty of Dentistry, UKM, and to assess the risk factors for tooth discoloration.

Patients & Methods

The study was approved by the Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia Dental Faculty Ethics Committee. An in-house questionnaire on tooth discoloration was constructed. It was divided into three parts: Part A, on demographic data; part B, on oral health habits; and Part C, on awareness and knowledge of tooth discoloration among patients.

One hundred and two patients comprising mainly Malays, Chinese and Indians, participated in the questionnaire session. The patients ranged in age from 12-45 years old. All questions were required to be answered.

Clinical examinations were then performed on the patients to determine the causes and types of tooth discoloration. Standardized clinical pictures of tooth discoloration were used as a guideline in the selection and classification of types of tooth discoloration. The data from the questionnaire and clinical examination was analyzed by using

SPSS version 17.0 (2009). Comparison of age between males and female was done using independent samples t-test.

Results

Demographic pattern of respondents:

The questionnaire was distributed to 102 respondents who showed apparent tooth discoloration. The study population consisted of 55 (53.9%) males and 47 (46.1%) females. Out of the 102 respondents, 68 people (66.7%) were Malays, 19 (18.6%) were Chinese and 14 (13.7%) were Indians. One other respondent came from the Melanau ethnic group (1%). Thus, majority of respondents presenting with tooth discoloration consisted of Malays, followed by Chinese and Indians to a lesser extent.

The mean age of respondents was 28.8 ± 8.8 years old. The mean age for male was 27.1 ± 8.6 and the mean age for female was 30.8 ± 8.6 years old. Majority of patients were in the age range of 21-25 years old (32.4%). The least number of patients fell in the age range of 11-15 years old, consisting of 3 respondents (2.9%). Majority of respondents (54.9%) were not aware about tooth discoloration. Thus it appeared that awareness and knowledge of respondents regarding tooth discoloration is poor.

Majority of respondents (52.9%) showed extrinsic tooth discoloration, whereas the remaining 47.1% had intrinsic tooth discoloration. Respondents showing extrinsic tooth discoloration were exposed to direct staining from tobacco, tea and coffee (49.1%). Chromogenic bacteria were the second largest cause of extrinsic staining (30.9%). Only 20% of respondents showing extrinsic tooth discoloration had indirect staining from chlorhexidine mouthwash. Majority of respondents showing intrinsic tooth discoloration had fluorosis (70.2%) as shown in figure 3, followed by tetracycline staining and non-vital tooth discoloration (both types tying in at 8.5%, respectively). It was interesting to note that 33% of respondents swallowed toothpaste during childhood brushing. Only 23.5% of respondents used mouthwash routinely. Majority of respondents (91.2%) had a habit of drinking coffee or tea. Majority of respondents (66.7%) were non-smokers. However, among the smokers, 22% of the total numbers of respondents were considered heavy smokers who consumed 5 to 30 cigarettes per day.

Figure 3: Pie chart showing types of intrinsic tooth discoloration in the study population.

Discussion

In the present study, the incidence of tooth discoloration was higher in males than females. This suggests that males are more susceptible to extrinsic tooth discoloration caused by coffee, tea and cigarettes [4]. The lower incidence of tooth discoloration in the females suggests that they are generally more conscious about their appearance than males [3], leading to more meticulous oral care and seeking earlier treatment for their tooth discoloration.

The highest incidence of tooth discoloration was found among Malay respondents followed by the Chinese and Indian respondents. This may be due to the fact that Malays form the largest ethnic group in West Malaysia followed by Chinese and Indians, respectively. Thus, majority of patients who would visit the UKM Polyclinic would be expected to consist more of Malays, followed by Chinese and Indian patients to a lesser extent.

The mean age of male respondents who showed tooth discoloration were younger than in the females, but it was not statistically significant (independent samples t-test, $p > 0.05$). The highest frequencies of incidence of tooth discoloration were in the age range of 21-25 years old followed by those aged 26-30 years old. The lowest frequency fell in the age range of 11-15 years old. People in the age range of 21-30 years old are young adults who were more likely to be exposed to agents of extrinsic tooth discoloration such as cigarettes, coffee, tea and bicarbonate drinks during social gatherings. Tooth discoloration

rarely occurred among 11- to 15-year-old individuals because being children; they were less exposed to the social factor and were usually under parental supervision and care.

The present study showed that there were fewer patients who were aware and knew about tooth discoloration than those who were aware. This concurred with findings from another study by [16]. The dearth of information about tooth discoloration either in dental practice or public information via media may be the reason for the lack of awareness among Malaysians. Tooth discoloration was not considered a problem that had to be solved as it was perceived to not affect the quality of life seriously. In addition, the poor to moderate socioeconomic background of some Malaysians may result in the careless attitude where tooth discoloration is concerned.

In the present study, extrinsic tooth discoloration was more common than intrinsic discoloration. This was seen in the higher number of respondents who consumed coffee and tea, and the number of moderate to heavy smokers. A similar observation was reported by [17]. Extrinsic tooth discoloration occurred more easily as extrinsic agents such as coffee, tea and cigarettes stained the teeth easily compared to agents of intrinsic tooth discoloration. Three factors contributing to extrinsic tooth discoloration are firstly, direct staining from tobacco, tea and coffee [3]; secondly, staining by chromogenic bacteria; and thirdly by the indirect staining of chlorhexidine mouthwash. The highest incidence was associated with direct staining due to consumption of coffee, tea and cigarettes as these are widely available in the market and had thus become a lifestyle to most of the Malaysians.

In addition, extrinsic tooth discoloration may also be caused by poor oral hygiene and lack of proper tooth cleaning knowledge [18]. Although all respondents brushed their teeth at least once daily, the method of brushing teeth may not have removed the plaque and staining effectively. The highest cases recorded for intrinsic tooth discoloration in this study was due to fluorosis. This was probably associated with the use of fluoridated water in Malaysia and the habit of some children who swallowed toothpaste containing high fluoride levels when brushing their teeth [19]. Indeed, one third of respondents swallowed toothpaste during childhood tooth-brushing. Other causes of intrinsic tooth discoloration such as amelogenesis imperfecta,

non-vital tooth bleaching and enamel hypoplasia were not very common compared to fluorosis.

Majority of respondents in this study agreed that tooth discoloration affected their appearance. This suggests that more patients were concerned about the incidence of tooth discoloration but the levels of concern were different. There were also many other factors that influenced patients in obtaining more information about tooth discoloration and how to treat it. Half of the study population knew about the treatment options such as bleaching, microabrasion, veneer or crown. However, they agreed that many people were still in the dark as to how to get sufficient information on tooth discoloration and its management.

Conclusion

Tooth discoloration can occur in anyone regardless of gender, age, and ethnicity. The awareness of patients about tooth discoloration was considered to be at a moderate level. There were many factors that influenced this level of awareness. It is suggested that the public and private sectors can help to heighten the awareness and knowledge of tooth discoloration among the Malaysian public by campaigns and distribution of pamphlets during dental road shows. Such dissemination on awareness of tooth discoloration can help in its effective management.

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Direct Trocar Entry as an Alternative to Veress Needle Even For Obese Patients in Laparoscopic Surgery

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Abstract

Background: Commonly we utilize veress needle in laparoscopic surgery as usual to start with the introduction of pneumoperitoneum in the abdomen (classic pneumoperitoneum), but there are many alternatives to it for better and fast work even in obese patients.

Objectives: The purpose of this study is to compare direct trocar (DT) to Veress needle (VN) entry for the creation of pneumoperitoneum during laparoscopy with regard to the duration of the procedure (trocar and Veress placement time), volume of gas used, ease of performance, and frequency of complications through a randomized clinical study in Alkarkh hospital.

Patients and Methods: 60 patients scheduled to undergo diagnostic and therapeutic laparoscopy (general surgery and gynecology cases), 45 cases divided into DT (group A = 25) and VN (group B = 20), the other 15 cases were obese patients BMI>30, subdivided into two subgroups (1, 2) submitted for the study, they were randomly allocated to either DT or VN entry for pneumoperitoneum. The laparoscopic procedures performed by the same surgeon.

Results: The trocar and Veress placement time, volume of gas consumption, ease of performance and frequency of complications were analyzed. The mean trocar and Veress placement time was significantly shorter in group A and subgroup 1 than in group B and subgroup 2. The mean gas consumption was significantly less in group A (2-3liters) and subgroup 1 than in group B and subgroup 2 (4-6 liters). No major complications (bowel, vessels injury) in both groups were encountered. Minor complications (failure pneumoperitoneum) were significantly less in group A and subgroup 1 than in group B and subgroup 2.

Conclusions: DT entry is a safe alternative to the VN entry technique for the creation of pneumoperitoneum. This approach has further advantages with less cost and instrumentation along with rapid creation of pneumoperitoneum even in obese patients.

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Key words: Veress needle (classical size and long size), Trocar, pneumoperitoneum, and Laparoscope.

Introduction

Creation of pneumoperitoneum is an important first step procedure in laparoscopic surgery, since it allows better traction on internal abdominal structures and better entrance of the other ports under direct vision through laparoscopes. The use of Veress needle was introduced since 1938 which is a

significant development in laparoscopic technology occurred in when Hungarian surgeon, Janos Veress described a spring loaded needle with an inner stylet that automatically converted the sharp cutting edge to a rounded end by incorporating a side hole for creation of pneumoperitoneum [1, 2, 3]. Veress needle utilized till now to be pushed through abdominal wall (supraumbilical or infraumbilical incisions of abdominal wall) to achieve the classic pneumoperitoneum, for obese patients same needle utilized but with longer shaft are utilized, since obesity is one of the main challenges in our study

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which creates difficulty in insertion of needle and trocar due to thick abdominal wall, and failure pneumoperitoneum were a common problem encountered, the trocar part of laparoscope passes toward the abdomen for further port entry and complete laparoscopic procedure [4,5,6,7,8,9,10].

Our purpose is to substitute the use Veress needle as first step and utilize the trocar directly with some precautions to be followed and done safely without causing any harmful effects to internal structures of the abdomen (bowel or vessels).

Patients and Methods

60 cases (20 males, 40 females) were submitted to either DT or VN during the period from April 2010 to Aug. 2011.

15 cases were obese (all were females with B.M.I=30-32kg/m²).

Five of the above cases had previous history of laparotomy (four of them previous surgery for duodenal ulcer-upper midline old scar, one of them had appendicectomy old scar). The mean age of patients is 40 years (range 20-60), divided into two groups:

- 25 patients had DT, Group A.
- Other 20 patients had: VN, Group B
- Obese patients(15 cases) were subdivided into two subgroups:
 1. Seven cases had DT
 2. Eight cases had VN

All patients had full history and were examined clinically, biochemically and radiologically (ultrasound, CT-scan) to exclude any contraindication for laparoscopic surgery (aortic aneurism, distended loops of bowel due to intestinal obstruction, tumors, and coagulopathy), They were undergoing different laparoscopic surgery accordingly (General surgery; laparoscopic cholecystectomy, diagnostic etc., Gynecology; cases for infertility, ovarian cyst etc...).

In our study we depend on the trocar and Veress placement time defined as the time to place the trocar or veress needle into the peritoneal cavity, volume of gas consumption, and frequency of complications (failed pneumoperitoneum, preperitoneal insufflations, and omental injury) were analyzed using instruments available for laparoscopic surgery in Alkarkh hospital.

In classic pneumoperitoneum; The patient is placed in a supine position without any tilt Veress needle utilized to be pushed through abdominal wall (supra-umbilical or infraumbilical incisions which is 10mm in length in abdominal wall) as a first procedure for achieving pneumoperitoneum with a pressure of about 7-8mmHg of Co₂, usually identified through insufflators within laparoscopic trolley instrument, after that we introduce first

trocar through same incisions to complete the stage of pneumoperitoneum with a pressure of about 10-12mmHg inside the abdomen. For obese patients long type of veress needle used. Sometimes catheterization of urinary bladder done to avoid bladder injury especially in gynecological cases [11, 12, 13, 14].

Direct trocar entry in our study depends on penetrating the trocar through specific sites within the abdominal wall, which are the safe sites, and they are avascular areas in addition to supraumbilical and infra umbilical areas. The landmarks are identified as shown in figure1. The anterior iliac spines, lateral borders of the rectus muscles and subcostal margin along with epigastric vessels [15, 16, 17, 21, 22, 23].

Figure 1: Safe sites for trocar placement.

The two lateral triangles are between the lateral border of the rectus sheath and the iliac spines. This is the site for the lateral ports. The third triangle is in the suprapubic region between the two umbilical arteries and the base of the bladder. The epigastric vessels (superior and inferior) are shown in figure1 remain medial to the lateral triangles), the other two triangles are between subcostal margin and edge of rectus muscle.

The first trocar is placed at 90 degrees to the abdominal wall through either infraumbilical or supraumbilical incision (for patients with previous laparotomies we were utilized area no.1 (right hypochondrial region) for first trocar entry.

Assistant and the surgeon elevate the abdominal wall but do not lift up the skin completely. Now the surgeon drives the trocar firmly towards the rectus sheath. Once the rectus sheath is reached, the abdominal skin is lifted up so that a flap is formed that is 90 degrees to the abdominal wall. By keeping the trocar fixed on the rectus sheath, the trocar is now driven through the rectus sheath in a slow and firm twisting motion. The trocar's orientation is at 90 degrees to the flap of skin, which will be in the direction of the pelvis, once you feel the resistance of the rectus sheath giving way do not accelerate but continue with the same speed until you feel entry of the peritoneum. The Trocar needs to go in only by about 3cm to enter the peritoneal cavity. The position of the scope must be checked first before starting insufflations (we were utilizing laparoscopes in DT after introduction of port into the abdomen before insufflations to look for possible wrong entrance through continuous elevation of the abdominal wall) when insufflations started you obtain good view very quickly.

Results

The mean trocar and veress placement time was significantly shorter in group A (1-2min) than in group B (6-8min), and it indicate the time consumed to achieve complete pneumoperitoneum enough to do laparoscopic surgery. The mean gas consumption was significantly less in group A (2-3 liters) than in group B (4-5liters) as seen in table 1.

Complications happened include failed pneumoperitoneum, preperitoneal insufflations, and omental injury occur in group B (table1) and in obese patients (subgroup 2/ table: 2) than group A or subgroup 1 (obese patients / DT) where no complication encountered. Direct entry technique is associated with a significantly reduced major injury (vascular, bowel) incidence when compared to Veress entry, as shown below .

Table: 1 Changes happened according to special parameters listed below.

Groups	Trocar and veress placement time	1 st A Complications	Amount of gas
group a	1-2 min.	nil	2-3l
group b	6-8min.	3 cases: failure (preperitonealinsuf.)	4-5l

For obese patients undergoing different laparoscopic surgery (general and gynecology

surgery), in such cases long type of Veress needle used DT entry safer than VN entry as shown in table 2.

Table2: Reveal changes happen in obese patients

Subgroup	Trocar and veress placement time	1 st a Complication	Amount of gas
Subgroup 1	2-3 min.	nil	3-4l
Subgroup 2	8-10min.	5cases: failure 4case:preperit-oneal, one omental inj.	5-6l

Conclusion

DT entry is a safe alternative to the VN entry technique for the creation of pneumoperitoneum. Such an approach has further advantages as less cost and less instrumentation with rapid creation of pneumoperitoneum in low risk and obese patients. Although this way of entry is not popular, our study show that there were no differences in terms of safety for a way of entry (i.e., Veress needle, direct entry) when compared to another. However no clear evidence as to obtain the optimal form of laparoscopic entry in the low-risk and obese patient. Direct entry may remain an under-utilized and safe alternative to the Veress needle [18, 19, 20, 24].

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Evaluation of Surgery Versus Medical Approach and The Role of Guide Lines in The Management of Gastroesophageal Reflux in Pediatrics

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Abstract

Background: Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is one of the most prevalent gastrointestinal problems that occur in children. The majority of infants can be successfully treated conservatively while awaiting improvement as spontaneous maturation of the physiological antireflux mechanisms occurs. The goals of an antireflux operation are to relieve reflux symptoms, decrease GERD-related complications and hospitalizations, and halt the use of antireflux medications.

Objective: This study presented alternatives for managing the acute and chronic symptoms of uncomplicated GERD in patients who may require long-term treatment. It summarizes the role of guide lines and available evidence comparing the efficacy and safety of medical and surgical interventions in the treatment of GERD, particularly after long-term follow up.

Materials and Methods: From January 2005 to January 2010, 26 children have been treated for GER, 14 with medical approach (primarily involves prokinetic agents and acid suppression therapy) and 12 with antireflux surgery (6 with Thal's operation and 6 Nissen fundoplication) at the Maternity and Children Teaching Hospital in Al-Qadisiya, Iraq. A review of the hospital records of these patients was performed. Twenty three of these children have been followed for an average of 12 months; the remaining 3 have been lost to follow-up. Questions addressed in this report are: What is the evidence of the comparative effectiveness of medical and surgical treatments for improving objective and subjective outcomes in patients with chronic GERD.

Results: The number of patients requiring antireflux medications decreased from 12 patients (46.1%) before antireflux surgery to 4 (15.3%) after antireflux surgery, 3 were restarted on antireflux medications within 1 year after surgery. Vomiting was the most common presenting symptom of recurrent reflux, which occurred an average of 3-8 months following the initial antireflux or fundoplication. Recurrent reflux occurred in 3 children and was documented with upper gastrointestinal radiography.

Conclusion: Failure of therapy could mean patients require surgical intervention. Antireflux surgery and fundoplication is well established as the surgical treatment for medically refractory GERD occurring in childhood. High technical standards and rigorous report of the results are required for keeping a relevant place of pediatric surgery in the treatment of this disease.

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Introduction

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is a common disease of infancy, with a prevalence of as high as 18% in healthy children, and a frequent reason for visits to primary health care providers [1]. Approximately

50% of all healthy infants will vomit more than twice per day [2]. A variety of approaches have been used in the treatment of GERD, including pharmacological and nonpharmacological therapies. As many of the pharmacological therapies for reflux, e.g. metoclopramide hydrochloride (Plasil, Meclodin or Reglan) and cisapride (Propulsid), are falling into disfavor or are withdrawn from use, practitioners may rely more on conservative measures as first-line

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therapy for GERD [3]. Normal infants often regurgitate recently ingested gastric contents during the first hour after feeding [4]. Treatment of GERD is directed at the various identified pathophysiological components. The majority of infants can be successfully treated conservatively while awaiting improvement as spontaneous maturation of the physiological antireflux mechanisms occurs. It remains difficult to delineate the boundary between physiological reflux, causing uncomplicated positing, and pathological reflux (gastro-esophageal reflux disease - GORD), requiring active therapy to prevent morbidity and mortality. Physicians are often called upon to decide on the need for appropriate investigations and management in these children. Because of the great propensity for physiological reflux to resolve spontaneously within the first 10 - 12 months of life, physicians have customarily been cautious in evaluating and treating such infants in the absence of complications [5]. As most infants with modest gastroesophageal reflux will not need an operation, indications for anti reflux in infants are considered carefully. These indications mostly involve patients in imminent danger from their disease such as infants exhibiting weight loss/growth failure, aspiration pneumonias, and/or presentation with an apparent life threatening event (ALTE) [6]. The most common indication for antireflux for infants in our unit is an ALTE episode. Given the life-threatening nature of the event, we proceed to antireflux rather than attempt medical management. The goals of an antireflux operation are to relieve reflux symptoms, decrease GERD-related complications and hospitalizations, and halt the use of antireflux medications. The North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition (NASPGHAN) published the first clinical practice guidelines on pediatric gastroesophageal reflux (GER) and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) in 2001 [7]. Consensus-based guidelines on several aspects of GER and GERD were developed in Europe at about the same time but were not officially endorsed by the European Society of Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition (ESPGHAN) [8, 9]. In 2007, the Councils of ESPGHAN and NASPGHAN established a joint committee to review, update, and unify these guidelines as a means of improving uniformity of practice and quality of patient care [10, 11]. The Committee used the 2001 NASPGHAN guidelines as an outline, adding new sections on certain pediatric populations at high

risk for GERD. The purpose of these guidelines is to provide pediatricians and pediatric subspecialists with a common resource for the evaluation and management of patients with gastroesophageal reflux (GER) and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). These guidelines are not intended as a substitute for clinical judgment or as a protocol for the management of all pediatric patients with GER and GERD.

We therefore undertook a systematic review to summarize the current state of the evidence. To maximize clarity and clinical usefulness, we present the results of that review as distinct evidence summaries detailing the potential benefits and harms of each intervention. In our study we represented the alternatives for managing the acute and chronic symptoms of uncomplicated GERD in patients who may require long-term treatment. It summarizes the role of guide lines and available evidence comparing the efficacy and safety of medical and surgical interventions in the treatment of GERD, particularly after long-term follow up.

Materials and Methods

This study was an open-labeled, uncontrolled, prospective, single centre study. From January 2005 to January 2010 , 26 children have been treated for GER , 14 with medical approach (primarily involves prokinetic agents and acid suppression therapy) and 12 with antireflux surgery (6 with Thal's operation and 6 Nissen fundoplication) at the Maternity and Children Teaching Hospital in Al-Qadisiya , Iraq. A review of the hospital records of these patients was performed. Twenty three of these children have been followed for an average of 12 months; the remaining 3 have been lost to follow-up. Questions addressed in this report are: What is the evidence of the comparative effectiveness of medical and surgical treatments for improving objective and subjective outcomes in patients with chronic GERD? Is there evidence that effectiveness of medical, and surgical treatments varies for specific patient subgroups? What are the short- and long-term adverse effects associated with specific medical and surgical therapies for GERD. During this period we reviewed patients treated medically and surgically for GERD. The nature of our unit's referral involved, in most cases, pediatrician filters that put refined diagnostic procedures and optimal non-operative therapy before the surgical consultation. Gastroesophageal reflux was therefore diagnosed on the basis of

clinical history and invariably documented by barium meal and in few cases by endoscopy, no facilities to use extended pH metering and no attempts for mucosal biopsy. With a few exceptions that will be addressed later, surgery was never indicated as a first-line therapy. All patients were treated with posture, prokinetics particularly metoclopramide hydrochloride (Plasil, Meclodin), and antacid medications that evolved from ranitidine (Zantac) to proton pump inhibitors PPI (Omeprazol and Lansoprazol) in more recent times. This treatment was applied during a minimum of 6 to 12 months (often several years). The patients were treated with lansoprazole (prevacid) at a dose of 15 mg (body weight below 30 kg) or 30 mg (body weight over 30 kg) once daily. After 8 weeks of treatment, the symptoms were evaluated. Those patients that refused to take the medicine for more than 2 weeks because of improved symptoms were re-evaluated for the clinical signs and categorized for no more treatment. After 8 weeks of treatment, the patients were divided into three subgroups: 'symptoms-resolved', 'symptoms-attenuated' and 'symptoms-persistent' according to their response to the treatment. The treatment was discontinued in the 'symptoms-resolved' group. The patients in the 'symptoms-attenuated' group were treated with 'on-demand' therapy. The patients that showed persistent symptoms were maintained with PPI treatment without dose reduction for an additional 16 weeks. At 16 and 24 weeks, changes in symptoms were reassessed, and surgery was only proposed after the persistence of the symptoms under medication was consistently demonstrated. Our preferred surgical approaches were standard open floppy Nissen fundoplication over a very large orogastric tube and open Thal, s operation. No resources for the laparoscopic approach in our unit. Gastrostomy was used in neurologically impaired patients who had swallowing difficulties and in babies with associated conditions in which this addition facilitated management like esophageal atresia with anastomotic stenosis, diaphragmatic hernia, or abdominal wall defects (in our study only one case). Feeding per oral was resumed on the fourth postoperative day, a bland diet was advised for the first 3 weeks, and unrestricted feedings were allowed since then. At 6 months, the position of the wrap was verified by barium meal, and all patients with recurrent symptoms of GER were subjected to clinical and radiological re-evaluation and in 1 patient re-endoscopy was done. Whenever the wrap was disrupted or ascended,

we advised reoperation except in patients wherein the symptoms were mild. Follow up included at least four outpatient clinic visit per year, and outcome were reviewed for each child in this series. Log-rank tests were used to examine the persistence of the antireflux function of the wrap and the differences among groups by this respect. Comparison between groups of patients was made with contingency tables, as well as nonparametric or parametric tests as indicated with a level of significance of 5%. Estimates were considered statistically significant if the 95% confidence interval did not overlap 1.00 and if P less than .05.

Results

From January 2005 to January 2010, a total of 26 infants and children underwent medical and surgical approach for the treatment of GERD disease at the pediatric surgery unit. The mean (SD) age at the time of diagnosis was 1.6 (2.8) years (median age, 1 year; age range, 0-13 years). The mean follow-up was 1 year. There were 16 (61.5%) boys and 10 (38.4%) girls. Among this population, a subgroup of 14 children were identified in whom medical approach was the first and absolute line of management, all done well with appropriate weight gain for age and reasonable control of reflux symptoms. Many patients had significant co-morbidity. Seven children (26.9%) had chronic pulmonary disease, 2 (7.6%) had seizure disorder, one patient (3.8%) had significant neurologic impairment, and 1 child had a prior repair of esophageal atresia and tracheoesophageal fistula (3.8%). The most common presenting symptoms were emesis 19 (73%) patients, failure to thrive 16 (61.5%) [Table 1]. Diagnostic evaluation showed the presence of GER in the majority of children underwent contrast barium swallow as their initial diagnostic evaluation (21/26, 80.7%), hiatal hernia was found in 4 (15.3%) children. Other findings included esophageal dysmotility 1(3.8%) and distal esophageal stricture 1(3.8%), esophagogastroduodenoscopy (7/10, 70%), resources for pH probe, esophageal manometry and technetium 99m gastric scintigraphy lacked in our unit. As an indication of the severity of reflux and its concurrent conditions in our material, it should be pointed out that of 26 patients, 15 (57.6%) were below percentile 3 for weight, 3 had esophageal stenoses (1 of which were anastomotic after esophageal atresia repair), 2 had intrathoracic stomach, 1 had Sandier syndromes,

1 had bronchopulmonary dysplasia and 1 had Barrett esophagus. All patients were administered antireflux medication prior to antireflux surgery and 7 out of 12 patients were administered antireflux medication after surgery (odds ratio=0.58; 95% confidence interval, 0.45-0.75; $P=0.002$). Of the 7 patients, 5 (71.4%) were restarted on antireflux medications within 1 year after surgery. Medical therapy was initiated and routinely consisted of a combination of dietary manipulation, positional changes, prokinetic metoclopramide hydrochloride (Plasil) agents with H2 blockers ranitidine (Zantac) in 18 patient at a dose of 5-10mg/kg/day in 2 daily doses or with proton pump inhibitors lansoprazole (prevacid) at a dose of 15 mg (body weight below 30 kg) or 30 mg (body weight over 30 kg) once daily, and antacids in 8 patients, magnesium- or aluminum-containing antacids (Maalox) at a dose of 1 ml/kg/d in 4 divided doses may be useful in neutralizing gastric acid. Side-effects from overdose may rarely occur, especially in low-birth-weight infants. Symptoms-resolved and symptoms-attenuated subgroups well announced in 14 patients, 9 patients under symptoms resolved responded completely to the antireflux medication and the treatment was discontinued and other 5 patients under symptoms attenuated candidate for further course of antireflux medications [Table 2].

Failed medical management or patients who showed life-threatening reflux episodes, 'symptoms-persistent' (surgical indication was only proposed after failure of optimal medical treatment had been documented, the only exceptions were major hiatal hernia) underwent Nissen fundoplication (360 o) complete wrap at an average age of 38.5 months (range, 8 months - 11.5 years), in our study fundoplication was created in 6 out of 12 treated surgically post medication [Table 3]. The operative procedure was evaluated for uniformity of technique, which usually involved a short (2-3 cm) floppy Nissen procedure performed over the largest dilator that would comfortably fit in the esophagus. The wrap was secured with three or four 2-0 or 3-0 interrupted silk sutures. In approximately half the recurrent cases, the short gastric vessels required division, and in all the patients a crural repair was performed. Concomitant gastrostomy was placed in 1 child. Postoperative complications after the initial procedure included pneumonia (2), wound infection (2), tight wrap (1), ventral hernia (1) and dumping syndrome (1). The average time to recurrence of reflux symptoms was 3 months

(range, 1 week-2.5 years). The symptoms suggestive of recurrence (in 3 out of 6 patients) included emesis, hematemesis and coughing-choking-gagging in 1 patient, aspiration pneumonia, failure to thrive, dysphagia, apneic episodes and dyspnea in 2. Patients with recurrence initially were treated conservatively using medical therapy consisting of prokinetic agents, H2 blockers, antacids, and/or omeprazole. Failure to resolve the recurrent symptoms led to reoperation at an average 18 months after the initial Nissen fundoplication. Five patients had a successful outcome (2 after their second procedure, intraoperative findings confirmed complete wrap breakdown in 1 child and the herniation of the fundic wrap in the other).

Six patients under 'symptoms - persistent' (patients, and asphyxia-suffocation - apnea grouped as apparent life-threatening events (ALTE), in these cases, with persistent symptoms of documented GER surgery was indicated primarily without prolonged courses of medical therapy), those underwent Thal procedure (180o) partial anterior wrap, 2 children experiencing either minor or major complication, wound infection (2), pneumonia (2) and tight wrap was identified and one child had a stricture confirmed. Long-term follow-up showed good-to-excellent outcome in 4 patients.

Table 1: Most common presenting symptoms and the significant co morbidity.

	Presenting symptom	No. & %
1	Emesis	19 (73%)
2	Failure to thrive	16 (61.5%)
3	Aspiration pneumonia	11 (42.3%)
4	Apneic episodes	5 (19.2%)
5	Coughing-choking-gagging	2 (7.6%)
6	Upper gastrointestinal bleed	1 (3.8%)
7	Dysphagia	1 (3.8%)
8	Chronic pulmonary disease	7 (26.9%)
9	Seizure disorder	2 (7.6%)
10	Neurologic impairment	1 (3.8%)

Table 2: The patient's subgroups according to their response to the medical treatment

Age in year	Symptom resolved		Symptom attenuated		Symptom persistent	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
0 - >1	1	2	1	1	1	1
1 - >2	-	2	2	-	1	-
2 - >5	3	1	-	-	5	3
5 - 13	-	-	1	-	1	-
Total	4	5	4	1	8	4

Table 3: Main indication for antireflux surgery, approach, and age at operation in 12 children.

	Nissen fundoplication	Thal procedure	All	Age at operation range (median) in months
asphyxia-suffocation-apnea	2	1	3	16.1
Neurologic impairment	1	-	1	22.2
Esophageal stenoses after atresia repair	1	-	1	18.6
Gastrointestinal symptoms	-	3	4	44.5
Congenital diaphragmatic hernia (hiatal hernia)	2	2	3	24.6
Total	6	6	12	26.2

Discussion

Gastroesophageal reflux occurs as a result of transient LES relaxation to a zero gradient between gastric and esophageal lumens or of an "LES pressure drift" during which the pressure differential between the LES and the lower esophagus gradually decreases to zero and can remain atonic for minutes to an hour or more [12]. Transient LES relaxations are not associated with swallowing and are likely modulated by the filling volume of the fundus or body of the stomach, and by the central nervous system [13]. The concept of a weak esophageal sphincter is no longer tenable. Why do infants appear to have excessive GER while older children and adults appear not to have it. Three reasons are evident: the volume of ingested food per kilogram of body weight is five to eight times greater in infants than adults [14] (greater gastric filling), an infant's esophageal capacity is 5 to 10 mL while an adult's is about 180 mL (less reservoir), and an infant's intra-abdominal esophagus is extremely short while an adult's is about 3 cm [9, 15, 16] (less flap valve action in the abdomen). Before 6 months of age, GER occurs much more frequently while infants

are sitting or propped up. Neurologically handicapped children are at great risk of GERD and primary swallowing disorders [17]. Investigation of potential GERD in such infants and children should, therefore, be early and aggressive. Damage to tissues (at microscopic or macroscopic levels) resulting from GER indicates disease. In clinical practice, both esophageal discomfort and pulmonary symptoms are common reasons for concern and consultation [18]. The diagnostic work-up for an infant or child with suspected GERD depends on the age of the patient and the presenting signs and symptoms [7].

A history and physical examination are sufficient for the diagnosis of gastroesophageal reflux. The North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition recently developed evidence-based clinical practice guidelines with algorithms for the evaluation and treatment of gastroesophageal reflux in infants and children [19]. It is difficult for

parents to believe that such a common medical problem doesn't have a more precise definition. This groundbreaking document is the best attempt so far to gather all the knowledge about reflux into a single place and to give doctors suggested courses of action to follow with their patients. The committee of doctors who wrote the Guidelines defined GERD this way: "Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) occurs when gastric contents reflux into the esophagus or oropharynx [mouth / throat/nose] and produce symptoms" [20]. In infants and toddlers, there is no symptom or group of symptoms that can reliably diagnose GERD or predict treatment response with quality of evidence B (Consistent Retrospective Cohort, Exploratory Cohort, Ecological Study, Outcomes Research, case-control study; or extrapolations from level A studies) [21], in our study the emesis was the leading and significant sign alarming the family for consult the clinic and it was the first clue in our diagnosis. In older children and adolescents a history and physical examination are generally sufficient to reliably diagnose GERD and initiate management with quality of evidence C (Case-series study or extrapolations from level B studies) [21]. Upper GI barium fluoroscopy is an important diagnostic tool in evaluating a child for reflux. Although not a sensitive test in diagnosing GERD, it is useful in eliminating other pathologic processes that can cause regurgitation in an infant, including gastrointestinal obstruction, malrotation, intermittent volvulus, and numerous other possible congenital causes for emesis. A contrast study of the upper GI tract also can be useful in ruling out the presence of a large hiatal hernia [Figure 1, 2]; in this study 4 cases were evaluated and arranged for surgery. Barium esophagography has variable sensitivity secondary to brief monitoring time and poor specificity owing to the presence of physiologic reflux in healthy individuals [22]. Also, a barium swallow is not helpful in terms of evaluating gastric emptying [23]. With variable indications this approach categorized under quality of evidence B [21]. However, as a study to define the presence or absence of pathologic reflux, a barium swallow is not an adequate examination for the overall

Figure 1: Central hiatal hernia and sever GERD in an 11 month old male.

Figure 2: Grade IV GERD with pronounced central hernia in a 3 years old male.

accuracy is no better than 50% [24, 25]. The degree of reflux can be graded according to the highest level the refluxate ascends in the esophagus. The sensitivity of contrast studies is only 40% but the specificity is 85% [26], this

study also allows assessment of the adequacy of esophageal clearance mechanisms and treatment [7]. However, esophageal pH monitoring does not detect reflux that is nonacidic (e.g., postprandial reflux in infants), measure the volume of refluxed fluid or fluid shifts in the esophagus, or detect GERD complications (e.g., respiratory problems) that develop despite normal acid reflux. The usefulness of esophageal pH monitoring in infants with apnea or ALTEs has not been demonstrated [7]. While the future application of this technology seems apparent, its utility is currently limited until normal values are established in the pediatric population [27, 28]. In our study we mentioned that all the resources of esophageal pH monitoring are lacked and made sort of limitations in diagnostic approach and we must agree in these pitfalls in our study and we think we lost a very strong evidence for GERD diagnosis. Endoscopy and biopsy of the esophageal mucosa can be used to verify the presence or absence of reflux esophagitis, Barrett's esophagus, esophageal strictures, eosinophilic esophagitis (a form that appears to have an allergic component that may explain the failure of acid-suppressant therapy), and esophagitis from other causes (e.g., Crohn's disease, infection) [7]. The resources of pediatric endoscopy is present just in our capital, this made other limitations in follow up our patients regarding early picking up the diagnosis or post medical or surgical interventions. Reflux-induced esophageal damage is defined endoscopically as visible breaks of the distal esophageal mucosa, quality of evidence C [21]. Biopsy typically is performed during endoscopy in pediatric patients regardless of whether the mucosa appears visibly abnormal to the endoscopist, because histopathologic changes to the mucosa often are subtle in pediatric patients. Endoscopic biopsy cannot determine whether esophagitis, if present, is due to reflux, quality of evidence B [21]. Absence of histological changes does not rule out reflux disease, quality of evidence B [21]. Manifestation of disease in pediatric patients is subtle. The oropharynx and upper pharynx should be examined during endoscopy because of the possibility of involvement of these areas (e.g., vocal cord

inflammation) in patients with GERD [19]. When endoscopy is performed, esophageal biopsies are recommended for diagnosis of Barrett's esophagus and causes of esophagitis other than GER quality of evidence C [21]. Two randomized controlled trials investigated the effect of formula composition on GERD; with equivocal results [1]. There is no evidence to support this intervention [1]. Tolia et al [29] randomized 28 infants to receive casein predominant, soy-based, and whey-predominant formulas in random order. The infants were given 1 serving of each formula on 3 consecutive days and then underwent measuring for gastric emptying time and reflux by means of scintigraphy. No difference was seen in spitting and vomiting between the formulas. Thickening of formula results in decreased visible reflux (regurgitation), quality of evidence A (Consistent Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial, cohort study, all or none, clinical decision rule validated in different populations) [21]. Prone and lateral positioning is associated with a higher rate of sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS). In infants from birth to 12 months of age, the risk of SIDS outweighs the potential benefits of prone sleeping. Therefore, supine positioning during sleep is generally recommended, quality of evidence A [21]. Acid suppressants act to decrease esophageal acid exposure by reducing the quantity of gastric acid. The antisecretory agents, histamine-2 receptor antagonists (H2RAs) and proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), reduce the secretion of gastric acid, whereas antacids neutralize gastric acid. Because of their superior efficacy and convenience, antisecretory agents have largely superceded antacids and surface agents in the treatment of GERD. There is no evidence to support an empiric trial of pharmacologic treatment in infants and young children with symptoms suggestive of GERD quality of evidence B [21]. In older children and adolescents with heartburn and chest pain, a time-limited trial of acid-suppressive treatment may be useful to determine whether GER is causing the symptoms quality of evidence C [21]. Histamine-2 Receptor Antagonists (H2RAs) act to decrease acid secretion by inhibiting the histamine-2 receptor on the gastric parietal cell. In one study

in infants ranitidine treatment, 2 mg per kg per dose BID, reduced by 44% the duration that gastric pH was <4, and with TID dosing the reduction was 90% [30]. Ranitidine 5 mg/kg per dose orally has been shown to increase gastric pH for 9 to 10 hours in infants [31]. In our study 16 out of 26 patients received H2RA (n=16, 61.5%). Tolerance to intravenous ranitidine and escape from its acid inhibitory effect within six weeks has been observed [32]. H2RAs produce relief of symptoms and mucosal healing, quality of evidence A [21]. To date, there are no large randomized controlled trials of PPIs in children. There have been multiple case series, in many instances of patients who were refractory to H2RA treatment [7, 33-36]. In these reports, children receiving PPIs have shown symptomatic and endoscopic improvement of severe esophagitis. The drug most frequently reported has been omeprazole, at dosages of 0.5 to 3.3 mg/kg/day. In several case series, omeprazole doses as low as 0.5 to 0.6 mg/kg/day were effective. More recently, case series with lansoprazole have been described [37-39]. The NASPGHAN survey indicated that despite limited pediatric data, PPIs are widely prescribed by pediatric gastroenterologists. Survey respondents estimated that in the previous year, they had treated 32,000 pediatric patients with a PPI. Most of the children treated were school-aged (67% were 6 to 17 years old), whereas infants accounted for 13% of prescriptions. Typically (in 52% of cases), the treatment duration was 3 months or less. Approximately 25% of patients were treated for 4 to 6 months, and 14% for 7 to 12 months. Of patients who were 1 year of age or older, about 10% to 15% were treated for longer than 12 months [40]. PPIs are superior to H2RAs in relieving symptoms and healing esophagitis, quality of evidence A [21]. For the treatment of chronic heartburn in older children or adolescents, lifestyle changes with a 4-week PPI trial are recommended, quality of evidence A [21]. If symptoms resolve, continue PPIs for 3 months. If chronic heartburn persists or recurs after treatment, it is recommended that the patient be referred to a pediatric gastroenterologist quality of evidence D [Expert opinion without explicit

critical appraisal, or based on physiology, bench research or first principles] [21]. In the infant or child with reflux esophagitis, initial treatment consists of lifestyle changes and PPI therapy. In most cases, efficacy of therapy can be monitored by the degree of symptom relief quality of evidence A [21]. In the infant with feeding refusal, acid suppression without earlier diagnostic evaluation is not recommended, quality of evidence D [21] [Table 4 summarized our medical versus surgical results with other studies]. Potential side effects of each currently available prokinetic agent outweigh the potential benefits. There is insufficient support to justify the routine use of metoclopramide, erythromycin, bethanechol, or domperidone for GERD quality of evidence C [21]. Because more effective alternatives (H2RAs and PPIs) are available, chronic therapy with buffering agents, alginates, and sucralfate is not recommended for GERD quality of evidence A [21]. In the child with dysphagia or odynophagia, a barium esophagram is recommended, generally followed by an upper endoscopy. Acid suppression without earlier diagnostic evaluation is not recommended quality of evidence D [21]. Surgical intervention has long been considered the definitive therapy for unrelenting GER disease refractory to medical management. In the pediatric population, the Nissen fundoplication has been the most widely used method of surgical repair. Recently, controversy has developed regarding the need for surgical intervention due to the availability of proton pump inhibitors (omeprazole) and prokinetic agents, allowing optimal medical treatment [41]. In addition, controversy also exists regarding the best management plan for those children in whom recurrent GER develops after an antireflux procedure. Two RCTs and two non-randomized studies provided information on lower esophageal sphincter (LES) pressure [42-45] Spechler RCT reported a significant increase in LES pressure in the open fundoplication group compared with the medical group 1 year after surgery (*P* value, not stated) [43]. Mahon RCT reported an increase in LES pressure in the laparoscopic surgery group compared with the PPI group 3 months after surgery (*P*<0.001

between groups] [42]. One retrospective study reported that patients who developed Barrett's esophagus at follow-up had more defective LES pressure and more impaired esophageal peristalsis before treatment ($P<0.05$) [46]. Johansson and Tibbling – the open label comparison of ranitidine with open fundoplication – reported that the LES pressure had a significant increase in the open fundoplication group compared to baseline ($P<0.05$) [44]. Antireflux surgery should be considered only in children with GERD and failure of optimized medical therapy, or long-term dependence on medical therapy where compliance or patient preference preclude ongoing use, or life-threatening complications quality of evidence C [21]. We have found excellent efficacy in preventing recurrent ALTE with fundoplication. Some authors have advocated alternative antireflux procedures such as the Thal procedure. Ramachandran et al [47] described use of the Thal procedure in 141 neurologically impaired children, with recurrence of reflux in 14%, and almost half of the children being converted to a Nissen fundoplication. Tuggle et al [48] documented a higher failure rate after the Thal operation in the neurologically impaired (16% recurrence rate compared to 3% in neurologically normal children), which suggests the Nissen procedure may be more efficacious in this subset of patients. Wheatley et al [49] observed that 34 (45%) of 80 children with repaired esophageal atresia had subsequent GER develop. Twenty-one of the 34 children underwent an antireflux procedure, with recurrence of GER noted in 33%, as compared to a 10% recurrence rate in children treated by an antireflux operation without esophageal atresia. They suggested that the Nissen fundoplication may not be the most suitable antireflux procedure in these patients with esophageal dysmotility. Similar findings were reported by Curci and Dibbins [50], in which 5 (36%) of 14 children with repaired esophageal atresia who underwent Nissen fundoplication had difficulty related to prolonged dysphagia. Caniano et al [51] documented recurrence of GER in 28% of their children with repaired esophageal atresia after Nissen fundoplication. Snyder et al [52] used the

Thal partial fundoplication in 59 children with esophageal atresia and noted a failure rate of 15%. This was a significantly higher failure rate than nonesophageal atresia patients experienced (4.3%) after a Thal procedure. Although Snyder et al. imply that the Thal operation provides less resistance to esophageal emptying, their study was neither prospective in nature nor randomized, but simply compared their results to those obtained in previously published studies concerning the Nissen fundoplication.

Early failure of the antireflux procedure has been seen in neurologically impaired and very malnourished children, with paraoesophageal herniation of the fundus occurring in approximately 10% of cases, usually as a late phenomenon. When this does occur, it causes dysphagia, is often associated with recurrence of GER and requires revision surgery. Discharge from hospital after these operations should be possible within 72 - 96 hours. Although these operations are highly effective in preventing GER, the underlying respiratory problem in patients with asthma-like syndrome might persist because of primary pulmonary disease, prior damage from aspiration or ongoing aspiration due to cricopharyngeal incoordination. Reoperation may be required in up to 10% of cases, mainly because of wrap breakdown and/or hiatal hernia formation [4].

Conclusion

Infants with typical uncomplicated symptoms of reflux should be treated without prior investigations. Therapy is available, but no drug will stop reflux. However, persistent symptoms in any child require a contrast swallow and meal to exclude anatomical abnormalities in the upper gastro-intestinal tract. Some children suffer intractable GERD with secondary complications GERD despite medical treatment. Failure of therapy could mean patients require surgical intervention. Antireflux surgery and fundoplication is well established as the surgical treatment for medically refractory GERD occurring in childhood. However, with life-threatening reflux disease, or with well-defined indications, a surgical antireflux procedure offers a safe treatment option with satisfactory long-term outcome. More studies are needed to clarify how patients with GERD should be managed based upon patient characteristics or response to previous therapy.

Table 4: Medical vs. surgical treatments of GERD, quality of evidence with study design.

Study Intervention Design	N enrolled N with follow-up data	Follow-up / duration	Quality	Results
In this study 2011 open-labeled, uncontrolled, prospective, single centre study MED vs. ONF and TAHL	MED n=26 SUR n=12	1 yr	C	Off PPI MED(n=8)30.7% ,ONF(n=2)7.6% , Thal antireflux (n=1)3.8% P=0.002 Off H2RA (n=18) 69.2%, ONF (n=4)15.3% ,Thal antireflux (n=5)19.2% P=0.002
Randomized controlled trials				
Spechler [43], 2001, 1992 MED vs. ONF	247 127	10 yr	B	Off PPI: MED (n=89) 36% ONF (n=37) 68% P=0.002 Off any antireflux meds: MED (n=90) 8% ONF (n=37) 38% P<0.001
Non-randomized studies				
Holzman, 2001 [53] MED vs. ARS Retrospective matched cohort from Tennessee Medicaid research database	MED n=250 ARS n=135	1 yr	C	Use of GERD drugs first year after ARS: MED 339 days ARS 123 days P<0.001
Khaitan, 2003 [46] MED vs. ARS Follow up of Holzman [53], 2001 study	MED n=200 ARS n=111	4 yr	C	Proportion of pts using GERD drugs was less in ARS than MED for each year of follow-up; In year 4: MED 90% ARS 74% P<0.001
Isolaauri, 1997 [54] MED vs. ONF Retrospective Cohort	120 105	10.9 yr	C	MED: 14/68 (21%) on omeprazole or H2RA regularly; 22/68 (33%) occasionally ONF: 2/37 (5%) on H2RA occasionally

MED: medical treatments; ONF: open Nissen fundoplication; SUR: surgery; PPI: proton pump inhibitor; ARS: antireflux surgery; H2RA: H2 receptor antagonists.

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Consolidation in a child from tuberculosis endemic area - thinking apart from tuberculosis

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Abstract

Tuberculosis is a common problem in the South East Asian region, affecting all age groups. Aply described as the great clinical masquerade, it may cause disease of virtually any organ, and, may present with vague symptoms. Hence it is not uncommon to over diagnose tuberculosis in many patients of this region especially in resource limited settings. Here, we present a case of pulmonary sequestration, presenting as recurrent hemoptysis, and was managed as a case of smear negative pulmonary tuberculosis. For creating awareness on the topic, we are also adding a brief literature on pulmonary sequestration.

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Key words: Tuberculosis, awareness.

Introduction

A 10 year old male child presented to our outpatient department with complaints of recurrent dry cough and streaking of blood for the past 3 months. He had received multiple courses of antibiotics, along with symptomatic management. A tuberculin test done with 5 TU measured an induration of 12 mm. The child was started on anti tuberculosis treatment under the revised national tuberculosis control program, according to weight band. But as his symptoms persisted even after 2 months of anti tubercular treatment, he was referred to our department.

The child was apprehensive and crying. He was afebrile, having a weight of 17.3 kg and BMI of 17. His respiratory system examination was normal other than occasional crackles, varying with cough, on his left infra scapular region. Other general and systemic examination was normal. His chest X-ray showed a dense shadow adjacent to the left heart border (Fig 1), which significantly cleared after antibiotics and anti-tubercular treatment (Fig 2). Lateral chest x ray showed a persistence of the shadow and loss of contour of the left diaphragm. (Fig 3). Hence a contrast enhanced CT scan of the chest was done, which revealed a dense area of consolidation in the paravertebral region, with areas

of break down and small cystic spaces (Fig 4). A Doppler study of the chest showed areas of increased vascularity, though the feeding and draining vessels could not be traced. Based on the clinico - radiological pattern, a differential diagnosis of sequestration lung or congenital cystic adenoid malformation type III was made. The child was referred to the department of cardiothoracic surgery, where an exploratory thoracotomy was done.

Thoracotomy revealed a greyish white sequestered segment of lung in the posterior aspect, adjacent to vertebral border. Careful dissection was made between the chest wall and diaphragm, which revealed a feeding artery from the thoracic aorta. A pulmonary ligament containing the veins draining into pulmonary vein was also identified, and doubly ligated and divided.

The cause of hemoptysis was actively searched but could not be found. A left lower lobectomy was then performed, after searching for other aberrant vessels, which were lacking in this case. Post operative period was uneventful and the thoracic drain was removed on day 5. The child was discharged on antibiotics and analgesics. Histopathology of the specimen revealed no evidence of tuberculosis and hence anti tubercular treatment was withheld. For the past 1 year, the child is under regular follow up, and is asymptomatic with no radiologic signs of disease.

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Figure 1: A dense consolidation along left heart border.

Figure 3 showing loss of contour of left diaphragm.

Figure 2: Near complete resolution of the consolidation.

Figure 4a: Multiple thin cavities in the lower lobe of left lung which were not communicating with the airway.

Figure 4b: A non-homogenous mass with varying lucency and cysts in the posterior part and the thin rim of draining vessel.

Discussion

Pulmonary sequestration refers to an aberrant non-functioning mass of lung tissue, having its own vascular supply from the systemic circulation and lacking communication with the tracheobronchial tree [1]. First described by Huber in 1877 [2], it was termed sequestration by Pryce in 1946[3]. It is a rare congenital abnormality with an incidence reported of only 0.15 – 1.8% in tertiary care centres [4].

Sequestration lung is thought to arise from a developmental anomaly – formation of an accessory lung bud on the ventral aspect of primitive foregut which later on course of time derives its own blood supply and develop separately. If occurring early in the course of embryogenesis, the accessory bud develops into intralobular sequestered lung segment; otherwise it becomes sequestered outside the lung parenchyma. An acquired theory for sequestration – secondary to obliteration of bronchi after a necrotising infection or foreign body has also been proposed [5].

Based on the presence or absence of a visceral pleural covering of its own, pulmonary sequestration is further classified into two – Extra lobar sequestration and intra lobar sequestration. Intralobar sequestration is by far more common than extra lobar sequestration, with same sex prevalence. It is usually asymptomatic, and

discovered only in childhood or early adulthood. The differences between extra lobar and intra lobar sequestration are summarized in table 1.

Table1: differences between extra lobar and intra lobar sequestration.

Feature	Extra lobar	Intra lobar
Incidence	Less common	Commoner (75%)
Sex prevalence	80% in males	Equal
Pleural covering	Invested by its own pleural layer	Surrounded by lung, no pleural layer of its own
Arterial supply	Abdominal aorta (> 70%)[4]	Thoracic aorta
Venous drainage	Systemic veins (>80%)[4]	Pulmonary veins
Skiagram chest	Well differentiated opacity usually in costo – phrenic angle	Homogenous/ cystic shadow in left posterior basal segments
Associated congenital anomalies	Multiple, commonly associated with ipsilateral diaphragmatic paralysis in 60% cases and ipsilateral diaphragmatic hernia in 30% cases[3]	Usually rare.
Time of Diagnosis	Noticed early in life due to associated other congenital abnormalities	Detected later in life, often in childhood or early adulthood due to recurrent pneumonia or hemoptysis [6]

Pulmonary sequestration has been described in all ages, from infancy to as old as 65 years [7, 8]. The main presenting complaints in this condition are, cough, associated fever and hemoptysis, due to recurrent infection of the sequestered lung segment. The chest x ray findings are not well defined, and hence it is common to mistake this entity for many other conditions, such as Bronchogenic cyst, lung cancer, pneumonia, bronchiectasis, pulmonary tuberculosis, A-V fistula, etc. On CT scan, they manifest as mass shadows, cystic – solid shadows, cystic shadows, and intrapulmonary flake shadows [9]. Digital subtraction angiography, CT angiography, Magnetic Resonance Angiography may show the supplying vessels, thus helping in making an easy diagnosis. Earlier, the investigation of choice – DSA – is now being replaced by CT angiography and MRA [10, 11].

Complications

Recurrent infections due to pooled secretions, colonisation by aspergillus, hemoptysis, are the

main complications that have been described with this condition. Congestive heart failure due to high volume left – left shunts in ILS, and right to left shunts in ELS has also been described [1].

Investigations

Ultrasonography is relatively safe and cost effective investigation and can detect pulmonary sequestrations early in the gestational period itself [12]. Laurin and Hagerstrand et al [13] reported chest x ray abnormalities, even before the patient became symptomatic in 7 cases. The definitive diagnosis was earlier made by an aortogram, but now days it has been replaced by CTA and MRA which shows a systemic supply to the sequestered segment [14]. A systemic supply to lungs may also be seen in arterio – venous malformations, aplasia of pulmonary artery, long standing pulmonary infections, or post operative lung. These rare conditions should also be kept in mind before making a diagnosis of sequestration, solely based on angiography reports [14].

Management

Management of this case is usually surgical [8]. In case of ELS, removal of the abnormal tissue is all that is required. But in case of ILS, a lobectomy must be done. Careful ligation of the feeding vessels must be done, because it's not often that the sequestered lung is supplied by multiple systemic branches. Severe haemorrhage has been reported in case a feeding vessel is missed. Now a day, video assisted thoracoscopic surgery is also being done with increased enthusiasm for pulmonary sequestration [8].

Conclusion

Even in regions endemic for tuberculosis like South East Asia, a differential diagnosis of congenital anomalies, which may mimic the clinical presentation of tuberculosis, must be kept before starting anti tubercular therapy in smear negative patients. Careful evaluation of such patients, especially of paediatric group may help to clinch the correct diagnosis and prevent further complications.

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Abiotrophia defectiva endocarditis in a child

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Abstract

Abiotrophia defectiva is a gram-positive coccobacilli that specifically grown in chocolate blood agar and Brucella agar. Infectious diseases caused by *A. defectiva* are extremely rare, and identification of this pathogen is important, as its bacterial characteristics require proper attention. An 8-year-old Chinese girl who is a known case of small perimembranous ventricular septal defect (PMVSD) presented with recurrent high grade fever, cough and poor oral intake for a week. The organism isolated from blood specimens from the patient was identified as *A. defectiva*. Her echocardiogram showed there was large vegetation at pulmonary valve extending on to the main pulmonary artery and right ventricular cavity. Due to detection of vegetations during her follow-up, she was readmitted for further management. Her conditions improved after antibiotics therapy, and she was on routine follow-up every 2 weeks. Clinically it is important to diagnose early so that the treatment can be started as soon as possible and improved the patient's condition.

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Keywords: Abiotrophia, defectiva, endocarditis

Introduction

Nutritionally variant streptococci (NVS), was first described in 1961 by Frenkel and Hirsch [1]. NVS is classified on the basis of growth characteristics such as nutrient requirements (pyridoxal) and presence of satellitism. In 1989, based on DNA-DNA hybridisation, Bouvet et al. showed that NVS could be divided into 2 groups, *Streptococcus defectivus* and *Streptococcus adjacens* [2]. Later, the name was assigned to a new genus *Abiotrophia*. This is based on the genetic and phylogenetic analysis of the 16S rRNA sequences that was proposed by Kawamura et al. in 1995 [3].

Abiotrophia defectiva colonize the oral cavity,

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the intestinal and genitourinary tracts as normal flora [4]. This bacterium has been associated with various serious infections including bacteraemia, endocarditis, brain abscess, septic arthritis and total knee arthroplasty infections. Endocarditis due to *Abiotrophia* sp. is rare, and accounts for less than 4.3% of all cases of streptococcal endocarditis [5]. It is often associated with negative blood cultures. We here by described a case of infective endocarditis who presented with fever and was diagnosed to have *A. defectiva* infection. Early diagnosis and treatment of *A. defectiva* infection is helpful in clinical practice.

Case report

An 8-year-old Chinese girl presented with recurrent high grade fever, cough and poor oral intake for a week. She is a known case of small perimembranous ventricular septal defect (PMVSD) and her last echocardiogram performed in 2009 revealed small VSD (5.73 mm) with good left ventricular (LV) contraction.

She denied any chills, rigors, rashes, eye discharges, vomiting or diarrhea.

She had a body temperature of 37.5°C, heart rate of 126 beats per minute, blood pressure of 96/53 mmHg and respiratory rate of 22 per minute. Her throat slightly inflamed. Apart from being febrile, systemic examinations revealed systolic murmur all over pericardium, with was best heard at upper left sternal edge, grade 4/6. Mild hepatomegaly was noted.

Her total white cell count was $13.9 \times 10^9/l$ with neutrophil predominance, suggestive of bacterial infection and her C-reactive protein (CRP) was raised. The haemoglobin level was 7.1 g/dL and further investigations diagnosed that she has iron deficiency anaemia. Her blood culture grew gram positive cocci that were sent for further molecular identification. She was discharged well after completed 1 week course of intravenous (IV) C-penicillin 960000 unit 6-hourly (QID). She was given outpatient follow up for echocardiography in 3 weeks time.

During her follow up, echocardiography was done. Her VSD was noted. However, there were large vegetation seen at pulmonary valve extending to main pulmonary artery and right ventricular cavity. She was readmitted to the ward for further management of infective endocarditis (IE).

Following discharged, she complaint of intermittent mild-high grade fever at home. No chills or rigors were noted. Examination revealed temperature of 38.0°C with non-radiating systolic murmur at left sternal edge.

Blood culture was sent during second admission, and revealed same morphological organism. Based on molecular studies of the 16S ribosomal RNA (rRNA), the organism was identified as *A. defectiva*. She was treated with several antibiotics such as IV C-penicillin 1 mega Unit 6-hourly for 5 weeks, IV vancomycin 400mg 12-hourly and IV gentamicin 3mg/kg daily. She was discharged after 6 weeks stay in the ward and was prescribed oral ciprofloxacin 250mg BD for 2 weeks while waiting for her next follow up.

While in the ward, repeated echocardiography was done (1 week after first echocardiogram) revealed similar findings. No new vegetation noted. Her third echocardiography was done on the day of discharged noted tiny VSD with smaller vegetation seen on pulmonary valve. She was planned for surgical closure of VSD in Institute Jantung Negara during her next follow up.

Discussion

Infective endocarditis (IE) is an infection of the endocardial surface of the heart and it implies

presence of microorganisms in the lesion [6]. According to European Society of Cardiology (ESC) guidelines, IE should be regarded as a set of clinical situations and they classified IE into few categories; according to the site of infection (right-sided or left-sided), presence or absence of intracardiac foreign material (native valve or prosthetic valve), and also the mode of acquisition (community acquired, health care-associated or intravenous drug abusers) [7].

In this patient, the identification of the organism was quite difficult. Initially, the organism was identified as *Arcanobacterium haemolyticum* (*A. haemolyticum*) based on identification using API@Coryne (Biomérieux, France), a 24-hour identification system of *Corynebacteria* and coryne-like organisms. This was because, based on the initial gram stain, the organism appeared to be pleomorphic gram-positive to gram-variable rod that does not form spores. Earlier researcher suggested that confirmation of *A. haemolyticum* was based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing; therefore, the colony was sent for further identification using 16S rRNA gene sequencing [8]. Unfortunately, the result came back as *A. defectiva* and this result correspond to gram stain on the second sample that showed pleomorphic gram-positive cocci/coccobacilli in chains.

A. defectiva and all NVS require pyridoxal or cysteine for growth and produce leucine aminopeptidase and arylamidase. Identification of the species can be done based on their patterns of carbohydrate fermentation, production of α - and β -galactosidases and β -glucuronidase, and hydrolysis of hippurate or arginine. *A. defectiva* can grow on blood agar. However, for subculture; solid media must be supplemented with 0.001% pyridoxal or 0.01% L-cystein to sustain growth. Alternatively, the subculture plate can be cross-streaked with *Staphylococcus aureus* to provide these factors and permit growth as satellite colonies. Because of difficulty in diagnosing the organism, specific rRNA PCR assays have been developed to aid in the identification of NVS, and have led to the microbiologic diagnosis in cases of culture-negative endocarditis. In this patient, only 2 blood cultures were positive while the remaining sets were negative.

In one case report by Al-Jasser et al., identification of *A. defectiva* with >95% confidence was successful using API@20 Strep (Biomérieux, France) after 24 hours incubation [9]. In this case report, the antimicrobial susceptibility was determined by the E-test for penicillin and the disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar with 5% sheep blood for the other antibiotics. Their results were

interpreted according to the Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) criteria for α -haemolytic streptococci other than *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The organism was found to be susceptible to penicillin, cefuroxime, ceftriaxone, erythromycin, imipenem, vancomycin, chloramphenicol and rifampicin, but resistant to gentamicin.

In our patient, using the first positive colony, the antimicrobial susceptibility was done using E-test for penicillin, and the organism appeared to be sensitive. Nevertheless, no reading was successful using the second colony as the organism was difficult to grow on Mueller-Hinton agar. Meanwhile, in vitro antimicrobial susceptibility testing of NVS is beyond the scope of many routine clinical laboratories. The results of in vitro susceptibility tests do not correlate well with clinical outcome in patients treated for endocarditis [10]. Furthermore, NVS are less susceptible in vitro to penicillin than other streptococci. Approximately 33% to 67% of strains are relatively resistant, and some isolates are highly resistant to penicillin [11]. This is consistent with another study done by Johnson et al. in 2000, which reported that 2 isolates of *A. defectiva* and 6 of 15 isolates of *Abiotrophia adjacens* had reduced susceptibility to penicillin.

All strains of NVS are susceptible to vancomycin, and susceptibility rates to fluoroquinolones have remained high. Decreasing susceptibility to other agents, including the third-generation cephalosporins, azithromycin and clindamycin, has been reported. A combination of penicillin and aminoglycoside is the recommended treatment regimen, and this proved to be successful and safe in one patient of IE in Slovenia as he received penicillin and gentamicin [12, 13]. Other alternatives consist of rifampicin and amoxicillin. Because of the difficulties of in performing susceptibility tests and correlating the results with clinical outcome, it is recommended that all patients with NVS endocarditis be treated with long term combination therapy. For our patient, she received various antibiotics in 6 weeks duration including penicillin, vancomycin, gentamicin and ciprofloxacin based on our suggestions. She was quite well and her vegetation also reduced in size. However, there is no guarantee that relapses may not occur even in cases of endocarditis with strains highly susceptible to penicillin.

In this patient, the risk for her in getting the IE is due to her congenital heart disease (she is having PMVSD). Furthermore, IE caused by NVS carries greater morbidity and mortality than IE caused by other streptococci.¹⁰ A comparison

study by Roberts in 1992, noted that between 49 patients with NVS endocarditis and 130 patients with infection caused by other oral species revealed a higher mortality rate (14% vs. 5%), more frequent complications of embolization (33% vs. 11%) and congestive heart failure (33% vs. 18%), and an increased rate of surgical intervention (33% vs. 18%). As what happened to her while in the ward, she developed septic embolization to her lung [14]. She was quite grateful as the diagnosis was made very fast and no obvious embolus seen within the main pulmonary arteries. As being stated earlier, surgical intervention may be needed in her case to prevent relapses.

Conclusion

Abiotrophia defectiva is a recognized cause of IE. Clinicians and microbiologist should be aware of this organism and its pathogenic potential. Proper identification of this pathogen is important to achieve a better outcome.

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Ocular loiasis in a Nigerian male adult

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Abstract

A 48-year-old male Nigerian farmer with a history of worm exiting through the conjunctiva of the left eye presented in our clinic. The worm, which was eventually removed, was later identified as adult worm of *Loa loa*. The patient was placed on conservative management after the removal of the worm and the chemosis at the point of exit of the worm resolved completely. The vision of the patient was however unaffected.

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Key words: Chemosis, Farmer, *Loa loa*, Sub-conjunctival.

Introduction

Loa loa filariasis (also known as African eye worm, Loiasis, Loaina, *Filaria loa*, *Filaria lacrimalis*, *Filaria subconjunctivalis*, Calabar Swellings, Fugitive Swellings, *Microfilaria diurnal* and Tropical Swellings [1]) is a skin and eye disease caused by the nematode worm, *Loa loa*. Human loiasis geographical distribution is restricted to the rain forest and swampy forest areas of West Africa, being especially common in Cameroon and on the Ogooné River. Humans contact this disease through the bite of a Deer fly or Mango fly (*Chrysops* spp.), the vector for *Loa loa*. These are blood sucking and day-biting insects found in rain forest in West and Central Africa [2].

The adult *Loa loa* filarial worm migrates throughout the subcutaneous tissues of humans, occasionally crossing into subconjunctival tissue where it can be easily observed— hence the name of African eye worm. *Loa loa* does not normally affect one's vision but can be painful when moving about the eyeball or across the

bridge of the nose [3, 4]. Loiasis filariasis can present as asymptomatic microfilaremia, lymphedema, episodic angioedema (red itchy swellings below the skin called "Calabar Swelling"), painful connective tissue swelling around sheaths of muscle and tendons, urticaria (skin eruptions) as well as pruritis (itching). Gender incidences of eye worms have approximately the same frequency, but it tends to increase with age.

The disease is treated with the drug Diethylcarbamazine (DEC), and when appropriate, surgical methods may be employed to remove adult worms from the conjunctiva. The recommended dosage of diethylcarbamazine is 6mg/kg/d taken three times daily for 12days. The paediatric dose is the same. Diethylcarbamazine is effective against microfilariae and somewhat effective against macrofilariae (adult worms) [5]. Mass Ivermectin treatment of Onchocerciasis can lead to serious adverse events (SAE) in patients who have high *Loa loa* microfilarial loads because of co-endemicity of *Loa loa* and Onchocerciasis in certain areas of West and Central Africa [4].

The first case of *Loa loa* infection was noted in the Caribbean (Santo Domingo) in 1770 by a French Surgeon named Mongin. Localized angioedema, a common clinical presentation of loiasis, was observed by a Scottish Ophthalmologist Douglas Argyll-Robertson in

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1895 in the coastal Nigerian town of Calabar – hence the name, “Calabar Swellings”. The determination of vector – *Chrysops* Spp. – was made in 1912 by the British parasitologist Robert Thomson Leiper [5]. Though humans are the primary reservoir for *Loa loa*, a simian type of loiasis exists in monkeys and apes but it is transmitted by *Chrysops langi*. There is no crossover between the human and simian types of the disease [6].

Antigen detection using an immunoassay for circulating filarial antigens constitutes a useful diagnostic approach. Identification of adult worms is possible from tissue samples collected during subcutaneous biopsies. Adult worms migrating across the eye are another potential diagnostic tool. Identification of microfilariae by microscopic examination of blood samples is a practical diagnostic procedure that is useful in many, but not in all cases, as one third of loiasis patients are amicrofilaremic. By contrast, eosinophilia is almost guaranteed in cases of loiasis, and blood testing for eosinophils fraction may be useful [4].

We highlight in this case report ocular loiasis in a 48-year-old Nigerian. The authors are not aware of similar reports in this part of Nigeria.

Case History

A 48-year-old Nigerian male farmer presented to the Eye Clinic of Federal Medical Centre, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria in September, 2010 with the history of itching in the left eye of twelve days duration, foreign body sensation of six days duration and obvious worm in the affected eye of one day duration.

He was apparently enjoying good vision and health until twelve days prior to presentation when he was awoken from sleep by a sharp needle-prick like pain in the left eye. This was followed few hours later by mild to moderate itching in the affected eye. There was associated redness of the eye with excessive tearing. However, there was no ocular pain, no photophobia, no discharge and no history of trauma.

Six days later, he started having foreign body sensation. There was an associated swelling of both eyelids of the affected left eye, which subsided a day later. However, there was a swelling on the white part of the left eye. There was no reduction in vision. The patient did not apply orthodox or traditional eye medication prior to presentation. There is no history of use of recommended glasses or ocular surgery.

However, early on the day of presentation, he noticed a worm coming out of the swelling on the white part of his left eye and this prompted the patient to present to our Eye Centre. There was no previous episode of generalized itching or swelling in the body. He usually works bare footed on his farm, which is in the forest far away from developed areas and disposes his faecal waste on the farmland. However, he does not swim in the river. He claims to have been bitten by flies regularly on his farm.

On examination at presentation, the visual acuity on the right was 6/12 while that of the left was 6/12-1. The anterior and posterior segments of the right eye were essentially normal. The conjunctiva of the left eye was diffusely hyperaemic, with chemosis about 2cm nasally from the sclerolimbic junction. There was a whitish thread-like structure (worm) exiting from the chemosis, twisting and turning. Other structures of the affected left eye were essentially normal.

The worm was promptly removed with a forcep under local (topical) anaesthesia with the aid of slit lamp bio- microscope. The worm was then sent to the laboratory for macroscopy. The patient was then commenced on conservative management, which included bed rest at home. He was also placed on Tabs Albendazole, Gutt. Ciprofloxacin and Gutt. Diclofenac. The following investigations were requested for namely Full blood count and Eosinophil count. Other investigations done are daytime blood microscopy for microfilaria, skin snip for microfilaria and worm macroscopy.

Worm macroscopy revealed that the worm was the adult form of *Loa loa*. However, both skin snip for microfilaria and day time blood microscopy for microfilaria were negative. The patient also had eosinophilia. The patient was planned to have refraction in a bid to improve his vision as soon as the inflammation in the left eye subsides. The patient was to come to the eye clinic for periodic follow up and the need for the patient to avoid insect bites was impressed on him.

Discussion

Loa loa is an endemic disease in tropical rain forest environment of Central and West Africa with a distribution that stretches from South-Eastern Benin in the west to Southern Sudan and Uganda in the east; and from latitude of 100N to, perhaps, Zambia in the south [7]. Our patient lives in an agrarian community very close to a rain forest in South-West Nigeria.

Loa loa microfilariae are transmitted to humans by the mango fly (also, mangrove) or deerfly vectors, *Chrysops Silicea* and *Chrysops dimidiata* (these vector thrive in tropical rain forest environment). Microfilariae mature to adults in the subcutaneous tissues of the human host, after which the adult worms; male and female worm mate and produce more microfilariae. The cycle of infection continues when a non-infected mango or deerfly takes a blood meal from a microfilaremic human host, and this stage of the transmission is possible due to the combination of the diurnal periodicity of microfilaria and the day-biting tendencies of the *Chrysops* specie [2]. The patient was predisposed to been bitten by mango or deer flies.

Loa loa is unique among human filariae in that adult worms are occasionally visible during subconjunctiva migration.8 Though the adult Loa loa move throughout the subcutaneous tissue of the body but they are most obvious while crossing the conjunctiva. The larvae of Loa loa development into adult worms takes up to six to twelve months following infestation [8]. The adult worms have been reported to be able to survive in humans for up to seventeen years. [8]. The first clinical signs of Loa loa may be apparent within five months of infestation [9]. However the period of clinical latency may last up to thirteen years. The patient presented with pain, redness and itching in the affected eye; which are common presentations of loiasis. However, the spontaneous exiting of worm noted in this patient is not a common presentation. The exiting of the worm through the conjunctiva made the removal with forceps easy.

It is noteworthy that there was no history of Calabar Swelling in our patient. There have been previous reports of subconjunctiva Loa loa by Carbonez G. Et al in Belgium [10], Ajello et al in Italy [11], and Jaksche et al in Germany [12]. The patient highlighted had a negative blood film examination for microfilaria and negative skin snip for microfilaria. This is however not an uncommon finding based on a previous report [13]. Loiasis usually does not adversely affect visual acuity as is noted in this patient. There has however been report of blindness following Loa loa infestation [3]. The anterior chamber in this patient was free of Loa loa worm, which is not unexpected. Cases of Loa loa in the anterior chamber have however been reported [3, 10, 14].

Loiasis can be treated by surgical removal of the worms leading to complete recovery. This

assertion explains our decision to remove the worm from the patient's eye. We actually seized the auspicious time during which the adult worm was moving through the conjunctiva to achieve this. We also placed the patient on albedanzole to address the possibility of systemic loiasis in this patient. The need to avoid the severe side effects associated with the use of ivermectin and diethylcarbamazine in patients infested with Loa loa explains why we decided to avoid placing the patient on any of the drugs.

In conclusion, this case is of particular interest because of the spontaneous exiting of the Loa loa adult worm from the eye, which prompted immediate presentation of the patient at our facility.

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Figure 1: The worm exiting from patient's left eye.

Figure 2: Left eye after removal of the worm

Figure 3: Adult form of Loa loa after removal.

Pineal gland germinoma mimicking choriocarcinoma : A case report

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Abstract

The germinoma represents a less malignant form of germ cell tumor. Depending on the individual's age, this neoplasm constitutes approximately 0.1% to 3.4% of all intracranial tumors. The embryologic origin remains a mystery; however, current theories implicate an aberration in primordial germ cell migration. Clinical presentation depends on tumor location and may involve endocrine, hypothalamic, visual, and cognitive dysfunction. In evaluating midline intracerebral masses, it is imperative that one be aware of the various radiologic appearances, endocrinologic changes, and chemical markers that help to distinguish germinomas from other neoplasms that appear in the pineal region. Only through the careful evaluation of all available studies can the physician institute appropriate therapies such as radiation, and chemotherapy. This article focuses on a young girl presented with pineal gland tumor with markedly elevated β -hCG with radiological examination suggestive of a highly malignant germ cell tumor. Stereotactic biopsy examination revealed a pure germinoma, which was in contrast to the clinical diagnosis of choriocarcinoma.

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Keywords: Germ Cell Tumor, Germinoma, Choriocarcinoma.

Case report

A 17 year old Malay girl, with no previous medical illnesses, normal growth and development appropriate for age presented with progressive worsening headache for past 3 month. Initially mild headache, and later became severe over last 2 weeks prior to admission. She also developed progressive blurring of vision, diplopia, gait ataxia

and tremors. Her condition worsen over last 2 weeks, with severe headache, nausea and vomiting, poor oral intake and developed progressive upward gaze palsy and unable to converge both eyes.

She was lethargic and drowsy. No history of trauma, fever, or limb weakness or sensory loss. Except for the eye symptoms, she had no other cranial neuropathies. No similar history in past and no family history of similar illnesses or malignancies. She had normal regular menses. She was admitted to hospital and fully investigated. Upon arrival to hospital, she was drowsy.

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She had equal and reactive pupils with failure for upward gaze and convergence. Fundoscopy showed bilateral papilledema. No other cranial neuropathies and no motor or sensory deficit. Routine blood investigations were normal. She had markedly raised β -hCG level of 40,000 ng/ml and α -FP of 8.5ng/ml. A CT Brain contrast done showed tumor at pineal region with calcification,

solid and cystic area with obstructive hydrocephalus. MRI brain and spine showed large heterogenous enhancing mixed solid and cystic mass arising from pineal gland with tumor infiltrating the surrounding structures and causing obstructive hydrocephalus. No intratumoural hemorrhage, no psammomatous calcification, no teeth or hair seen. No spinal metastasis seen. (MRI images as shown below).

Figure 1: MRI image of large Pineal Gland neoplasm with irregular margin. Heterogenous contrast enhancement and with marked intra tumoural necrosis.

She underwent endoscopic 3rd ventriculostomy and tumor biopsy. Post-operatively and during the stay in hospital, she had multiple recurrent episodes of intratumoural hemorrhage. Hence, based on the short duration of presentation, radiological images suggestive a malignant tumor with recurrent intra-tumoural hemorrhages and grossly elevated β -hCG levels, a clinical diagnosis of non-germinomatous germ cell tumor was made and most probably choriocarcinoma of the pineal gland. Keeping in mind that, germinoma with syncytiotrophoblastic giant cell can presented with elevated β -hCG level and intra-tumoural hemorrhages.

However, the histopathology report showed presence of round, vesicular and centrally positioned nuclei, prominent nucleoli, discrete cell membrane and relatively abundant clear cytoplasm (figure 2). The cells showed strong cell membrane labeling for c-kit (figure 3). No syncytiotrophoblastic or cytotrophoblastic giant

cell seen. No mitosis or endothelial proliferation seen. This microscopic examination suggestive of pure germinoma.

Figure 2: Large tumor cells with round vesicular nuclei with prominent nucleoli and clear cytoplasm.

Figure 3: Expression of c-kit oncoprotein in tumour cells.

Discussion

The CNS germ cell tumor is rare and accounts for 2-3% of primary intracranial neoplasm. Approximately 80-90% of CNS germ cell tumours afflict subjects younger than 25 years of age, incidence peaking in 10-14 years old, and a clear excess of cases involve males. CNS germ cell tumours preferentially affect the midline: 80% or more arise in structures about the third ventricle, with the region of the pineal gland being their most common site of origin, followed by the suprasellar compartment.

In order of frequency of appearance in the central nervous system in all age groups, lie the subcategories of germinoma (40%); mixed tumor (30%); teratoma (20%); and yolk sac tumor, embryonal carcinoma, and choriocarcinoma (10%). Pure germ line tumors are called germinomas. Differentiated germ cell tumors may be divided into embryonic (embryonal carcinoma and mature or immature teratoma) and extra-embryonic (choriocarcinoma and yolk sac or endodermal sinus tumors) growths. When organized according to increasing malignant potential, these tumors are germinoma, teratoma, embryonal carcinoma, embryonal sinus tumor, and choriocarcinoma [3]. Each tumor represents the malignant correlate of a normal stage of embryonic development [3]. Germinomas arise from the primordial germ cell; teratomas arise from the differentiated embryonic cell layers; embryonal carcinoma develops from a pluripotential cell of the embryo proper; endodermal sinus tumors represent tissue from extra-embryonic yolk sac endoderm; and choriocarcinoma arises from extra-embryonic trophoblastic tissue [3].

Germ cell tumors arise because of neoplastic changes during embryonic development. Intracranial germ cell tumors occur in the pineal region, suprasellar- retrochiasmal area, pituitary fossa, posterior third ventricle, interpeduncular and quadrigeminal plate region, cerebellar vermis, thalamus, and walls of the lateral and third ventricles [8]. Germinomas characteristically infiltrate locally and spread by dissemination through the craniospinal and subarachnoid spaces. Parenchymal metastases and extradural spread are rare [4].

On CT and MRI, germinoma usually appear as solid masses that are iso- or hyperdense relative to grey matter and show prominent contrast enhancement. Pineal region germinoma shows iso to hypointensity on T1-weighted image and hyperintense on T2-weighted image and homogenous contrast enhancement. Intra tumoral cyst and necrosis commonly seen in more malignant variety. Intra tumoral hemorrhage is particularly characteristic of choriocarcinoma and of mixed neoplasms with choriocarcinomatous elements, but may also be encountered in germinoma associated with β -hCG elevation (having syncytiotrophoblastic components).

Tumor markers in serum and CSF can be used for assessment of suspected germ cell neoplasia. Pure germinoma shows isolated elevation of Placental like alkaline phosphatase (PLAP) and positivity to CD117 (*c-kit*) immunostaining, with normal α -FP and β -hCG. Germinoma with syncytiotrophoblastic elements may have modest increase in β -hCG oncoprotein.

Grossly, solid tumor tissue can be soft and purplish-gray. Microscopically, these tumors consist of large polygonal cells surrounded by fibrous connective tissue. Lymphocytic infiltration is most prominent around blood vessels. Cells tend to organize in sheets and lobules and are characterized by large round or oval vesicular nuclei, prominent irregular nucleoli, pale ill-defined cytoplasm, rich stores of glycogen, and coarse or fine granular chromatin. Mitotic figures can be present. Ultrastructurally, germinomas display scanty cytoplasm, few organelles, and abundant glycogen. The cytoplasm contains poorly developed Golgi complexes, distorted and aggregated mitochondria, and moderately developed rough and smooth endoplasmic reticulum. Cell membranes are occasionally fused by desmosomes or tight junctions. Lymphocytic infiltration of germinomas has been demonstrated by light and electron microscopy. Tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes have been characterized

using monoclonal antibodies. In intracranial germinomas, 70% to 80% of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes were T-lymphocytes, and the remainder was B-lymphocytes.

Pure germinoma exhibit a remarkable radiosensitivity foreign to other germ cell tumor types, 10-year survival rate bettering 85% following craniospinal irradiation alone. The addition of chemotherapy to germinoma treatment regimes may effect comparable disease control at reduced radiation doses and field volumes. Germinoma harbouring syncytiotrophoblastic cells or associated with elevated β -hCG levels have carried an increased risk of local failure and modest decrement in survival compared to their pure counterparts after irradiation alone.

Conclusion

Though germ cell tumor affecting the neuroaxis is uncommon, but it carries a better prognosis if prompt diagnosis and treatment is achieved. In our patient, the clinical diagnosis of choriocarcinoma was made based on the markedly raised β -hCG and MRI finding of pineal gland tumor which showed irregular contrast enhancement with marked tumour necrosis and intratumoural bleed. However, the histopathological examination showed pure germinoma. It is well documented that, stereotactic biopsy done may not actually reflect the true tumor characteristics. Hence, multi model management among the pathologist, oncologist and neurosurgeon is mandatory in this situation for optimal management of this patient.

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